

IFRECOR

FRENCH CORAL REEF INITIATIVE

HANDBOOK I

GUIDE TO ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS OF CORAL REEF ECOSYSTEMS

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1 INTRODUCTION

There is a paucity of tools available for the implementation of EIAs in coral reef environments, that are adapted to the specifics of these vulnerable ecosystems. The initial site analysis for the evaluation of impacts as well as proposals for avoidance, reduction and compensatory measures, is often addressed only partially and lacks a systems focus, particularly in the marine environment (Levrel et al., 2012; Guillet et Mermet, 2013; Jacob et al., 2014; Quétier et al., 2014; Vaissière et al., 2014).

On the basis of these findings, the French Coral Reef Initiative's (IFRECOR) working group began to focus on coral reefs within environmental impact assessments. This analysis started with three impact assessments carried out by various consultants in French Overseas Territories, over the past ten years. This was followed up with thematic workshops which were open to EIA stakeholders (state authorities, public bodies, associations, representatives of planners, technical consultants, naturalists, etc.). These discussions enabled issues to be discussed and guidelines developed, which are provided in Handbooks 1 and 2.

While the Guides were developed for French Overseas Territories, the basic principles are the same for coral reef ecosystems and so are applicable in a global context.

1.1 Coral reef ecosystems

Coral reefs are complex and diverse ecosystems that provide many ecological goods and services on which humans depend. They are among the richest ecosystems in terms of biodiversity, containing one third of all known marine species i.e. over 100,000 species (Spalding et al., 2001), are present in more than 100 countries of the world and cover about 600,000 km² of seabed (Jameson et al., 1995). However, in the last 50 years, 20% of coral reefs has disappeared, with an estimated 15% are seriously endangered in the next 10 to 20 years and only 30% are in a satisfactory state of conservation (Wilkinson, 2008). Further, according to the World Resources Institute, approximately 75% of the world's reefs are threatened by a combination of local and global factors (WRI 2011).

According to the The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment¹ (MEA 2003) over the last 50 years, there have been huge and largely irreversible changes to biodiversity in its entirety and this slide is likely to continue if significant changes are not made to “policies, institutions and practices” (MEA 2003).

Following Moberg and Folke (1999), the services provided by coral reefs in general can be categorized into: (i) physical structure services, such as coastal protection; (ii) biotic services, both within ecosystems (e.g. habitat maintenance) and between ecosystems (e.g. biological support through mobile links); (iii) bio-geo-chemical services, such as nitrogen fixation; (iv) information services (e.g. climate record); and (v) social and cultural services, such as aesthetic values and recreation. The more recent MEA has placed ecosystem services into 4 categories: Provisioning, Regulating, Cultural and Supporting. Using this breakdown for ecosystem benefits, coral reefs provide *Provisioning Services* such as food fish, natural shoreline protection, unique flora and fauna for bioprospecting, and numerous goods and services supporting tourism. *Cultural Services* are also provided, evidenced by their importance in the cultural and spiritual practices of many island communities, while *Supporting Services* include providing critical habitat for many species, resulting in high levels of biodiversity (UNEP, 2006).

Although ecologists have made progress in understanding the structure and functioning of reef ecosystems, their dynamic response to stress is still not well understood (Mumby & Steneck 2008). Reef ecosystems exhibit multiple stable states and multiple feedback mechanisms, making the understanding of the variability within each state and the transitions between states difficult (Nyström et al., 2000; Norström et al., 2009).

There are four primary coral reef types; Fringing, which colonise near or on the shoreline, Barriers which are offshore and run parallel to shore (often separated from land by a lagoon), Atolls, which are oval, circular or horseshaped with a coral rim (either partially or fully enclose a lagoon) and Patch, which are small, isolated reefs often found in lagoons. Many functional differences exist among these reef types, which are often connected in varying degrees to other ecosystems, such as mangrove forests, seagrass beds, and the open ocean.

According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), over 60% of the world's population lives in the coastal zone with 3.8 billion people being situated within 150 km of the coast with ongoing coastal migration globally (Hugo 2011) This special attraction that the interface between sea and land holds for humans, has increased greatly over recent decades and this trend is expected to continue well into the future (Neumann B *et al.* 2015). The increased development and use of the coast has resulted in severe environmental and social economic changes. It is estimated that between 5 to 10 km of coastlines globally are impacted daily by human development, , with coastal nursery areas, mudflats and mangroves being polluted or destroyed (Béoutis et al.,

¹ The MEA was carried out between 2001 and 2005 in order to assess what impact ecosystem change is having on humans and to determine the most effective conservation methods for sustainability.

2008). Coral reefs also have undergone significant degradation thus promoting coastal erosion.

Coastal areas are the most densely populated and their populations continue to increase. Within thirty years (1975 to 2005) global coastal populations have grown from 1.6 billion to over 2.5 billion, which represents approximately 38% of the world's population (UNEP, 2014). Even with a lowest growth assumption, Neumann et al. (2015) estimate that the coastal population could increase by more than 40% between years 2000 and 2030 and 60 % by 2060. This population growth is accompanied by significant developments of road, urban and industrial infrastructure, some of which occupy coastal space and are frequently responsible for significant indirect impacts on the coastal environment.

Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) have been around since 1970, introduced by the United States of America. Since then, the concept has spread globally and the majority of countries have EIAs as a legal requirement. By virtue of their nature to assist decision making, they have become an essential phase in the environmental evaluation of development projects. Such assessments have three basic objectives: 1) to design projects with the least impact, 2) to enlighten administrative authorities regarding the decision to be taken, and 3) to inform and involve the public in the decision-making processes.

This guide was developed originally for the French experience in EIAs, however as many of the tenants and policies are the same globally, it is relevant in a global context.

Although there are numerous environmental evaluation tools and the body of regulations and laws relating to the conservation of natural areas is regularly enriched with new texts adapted to current needs, a gap remains between political will and the control of development projects carried out in national territories. The wide diversity of players and competences deployed during the appraisal, implementation and evaluation of EIAs sometimes renders it difficult to translate results into coherent and effective management measures, especially when it comes to evaluating the risks to ecosystems as complex and fragile as coral reefs.

The causes of this gap include: 1) the sometimes questionable reliability of information from which conclusions provided in the EIA are drawn (choice of indicators, expertise of field workers, sampling methods and effort, etc.), 2) an absence of standardization in the acquisition, analysis and collection of environmental data, 3) weak trans-disciplinary and required competencies (sciences, legal, economics, urbanism, etc.), 4) a wide diversity of evaluation methods, some of which require high levels of expertise in the absence of any real qualitative justification, 5) the poor capacity of many public authorities to arbitrate and evaluate submitted studies (water authorities, environmental authorities [EA], prefectures, enquiry commissioners, etc.)

The consequences include: 1) weak understanding of submitted studies, which renders the process incapable of assisting decision-makers 2) difficulty in quantitatively estimating (e.g. surface equivalence) risks to ecosystems, opportunities presented by impact reducing measures, and if necessary, the compensation measures and techniques to be implemented; 3) inability of administrative authorities to determine the competence of studies (legal, technical or methodological) and with decisions often being based on the opinions of small advisory committees (scientific committee).

The purpose of this Guide is not to inhibit nature and spatial planning, but to propose tools that will help in selecting projects with the least environmental impact. This Guide thus aims to: 1) provide background information on the regulatory, historic and ethical foundations of the EIA; 2) outline the specific features of coral reefs and associated ecosystems (seagrass beds, mangroves, etc.); 3) define, according to type of development, the regulatory regime and environmental risks; 4) identify pertinent indicators, choose research methods and define a sampling strategy adapted to the ecological and geographical specificities of coral reefs; and 5) estimate (simply) the likely impacts of a project, the effect of expected reduction measures and, if required, compensatory measures.

1.3 Who is this Guide for?

This Guide is primarily for **public and private project managers**, to assist them in improving their awareness of the environmental issues pertaining to coral reefs and the steps involved in integrating these into their projects

It will also be useful for **technical research firms and independent consultants**, so that they can integrate the outputs into their proposals, that takes into consideration the complexity and fragility of reef ecosystems and is also proportionate to the scale of potential risks in the area under study .

Public Institutions responsible for assessing EIAs, **scientific institutions, managers of natural areas, etc.)** can draw on the necessary elements of the environmental assessment of projects submitted to them. They will thus be able to verify the relevance, the technical aspects and the thoroughness of documents provided in the planning application.

Civil society and their representatives, can rely on the Guide to inform them on the public enquiry process and the technical aspects of the marine environment which are required for the EIA (Fig 1).

Figure 1 Structure of services for this Guide and their interactions

1.4 Limitations

This Guide is one of a series of well documented works on: Environmental impact assessments (e.g. Michel, 2001; Melki, 2002; Rufay, 2013), reef restoration methods (e.g. Porcher et al., 2003; François and Pascal, 2012; Pinault, 2013) and methods to evaluate coral reef health (e.g. Conand et al., 1997; Belaieff et al., 2011; Facon et al., 2016).

It was drafted between October 2014 and January 2016 and utilises the knowledge available at that time. Given the constant evolution of information and regulations, a regular review will be necessary.

The guidelines proposed attempt to reflect the most current knowledge on environment impact assessments. The reader is invited to approach relevant agencies in their countries in order to keep abreast of the latest developments in legislation and policy and to ensure the soundness of the technical measures and strategic direction taken.

1.5 Marine Environments and their challenges

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) which concluded in 1982, is an international agreement that defines the rights and responsibilities of countries to the waters that surround them. The sovereignty of coastal states extends beyond the land and into adjacent waters, not exceeding 12 nautical miles for Territorial Seas, encompassing the sea bed and subsoil of continental shelves (which cannot extend past 200 nm). In the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), countries have “sovereign rights for the purpose of exploring and exploiting, conserving and managing the natural

resources, whether living or non-living, of the waters superjacent to the seabed and of the seabed and its subsoil”. Marine waters are therefore subject to both national laws (for territorial waters e.g.) and international law (continental shelf and EEZs e.g.). Only coastal marine environments are covered in this guide.

Coastal marine environments are especially complex compared to terrestrial environments due to sharing of maritime space and the wide variety of uses that can affect the surface of the water (navigation, sea side activities), the water column (fishing, Scuba diving), the ground (cables, pipelines) and the marine subsoil (aggregates, sand). Assessing the impacts of these uses is complex for the following reasons (CGDD, 2013):

- Primary Issues include:
- The sea is a moving environment and it is difficult to define intangible and uncontested environmental pressure perimeters.
 - Impacts on the marine environment can be very wide and diffuse, in three dimensions.
 - Impacted ecological processes (such as biomass production or complexity of habitats), production of ecosystem services and their beneficiaries all have different spatial distributions.
 - The state of knowledge of the marine environment is particularly deficient, particularly in coral reef habitats, with the exception of specific agencies or initiatives such as the National Ocean Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) in the USA the L'Initiative Française sur les Récifs Coralliens (IFRECOR) in France and the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority (GBRMPA) in Australia.

In many cases, there is also a lack of resources for specialized and new expertise (benthos, phytoplankton, etc.), both in the private and public spheres.

These constraints, specific to the marine environment, particularly for the acquisition of data, do not allow the same level of evaluation accuracy to be reached as in the terrestrial environment. There is also a difference in the spatial scales of intervention with hectares being used for land and often square kilometers at sea (CGDD, 2013).

2.1 Conceptual framework 2.1.1

Impact assessment objectives

An Impact Assessment is defined as “the process of identifying the future consequences of a current or proposed action” by the International Association for Impact Assessment (IAIA) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) considers it a key instrument in attaining the Convention’s objectives on conservation, sustainable use of equitable sharing. It forms the cornerstone of Environmental Impact Assessments (as well as Strategic Environmental Assessments (SEA) and Health Impact Assessments (HIA)) and allows for decisions made in the development process, that would have impacts on the natural environment, to be scrutinized (Honrado et al 2013).

Environmental assessment⁹, a term that comprises EIA and other studies related to the same conceptual framework, refers to the descriptive and functional study of different environmental themes: the biological environment (ecosystems, fauna, flora, natural habitats, bacteriology, etc.), the physical environment (geography, oceanography etc.), the chemical environment (water quality inc. sediments, etc.), the human environment (professional activities and use, etc.) and landscaping (functionality, continuity and connectivity). It integrates the four major principles of the Environment Code, as defined in the 1992 Earth Summit's Agenda 21: integration, participation, precaution and prevention.

The EIA, is an essential step in the environmental assessment of development projects with a primary purpose of facilitating the incorporation of environmental issues into decision making for development processes. This is done by analysing environmental information on potential impacts of specific projects, and proposing preventative or mitigative measures. EIA is a process, which should be integrated throughout the project from the planning to the decision making phases.

It has three primary objectives: 1) **propose** the project with the least impact, 2) **advise** the administrative body empowered to grant authorization and 3) **inform** and involve the public in the decision-making process. The EIA thus enables project initiators to demonstrate they have taken environmental concerns into consideration, and that their projects respect people, landscapes and natural environments, by economizing space, limiting water, and soil pollution and reducing harm to flora and fauna.

According to UN Environment there are 9 general principles of EIA application:

1. A tool to help achieve sustainable development;
2. Integrated into existing development planning and approval processes to minimize disruptions and increase effectiveness;
3. A tool to implement environmental management (rather than as a report to provide project approvals);
4. Integration into the project life-cycle to ensure that environmental information is provided at the appropriate times;
5. Application to all proposed actions, likely to have a significant adverse effect on the environment and human health;
6. Inclusion of analysis of feasible alternatives to the proposed action;
7. Public involvement;
8. Interdisciplinary using best-practicable science;
9. Integration of social, economic and biophysical impacts

Anticipating the administrative decision to approve works or a development, the EIA allows for: 1) exchanges on the content of a project between project managers and the state authorities on environmental issues 2) the definition of prevention, reduction and,

⁹ The environmental assessment is carried out at three levels: 1) planning and programming – with strategic focus on a relatively large territory [SRCE - French acronym for Regional Plan for Ecological Consistency] for the blue belt; SCOT, French acronym for Territorial Coherence Plan for the coastline or the regional development plan sometimes combined with a marine development plan); 2) development projects – it will have a more localized application with specificities according to the environments concerned; 3) specific assessments: habitats or protected species (Natura 2000), or aquatic environments (Water Law) (Fig 12).

if necessary, compensatory (or offset) measures of the project's potentially damaging effects on the environment; and 3) defining of the commitments made by the project manager regarding evaluation and monitoring of impacts in the short-, medium- and long-term (monitoring the consequences of the project during the construction, use and, if necessary, the dismantling phases). It is at this stage that the project manager explains how the environment will be integrated into the project and demonstrates the capacity to take stakeholder concerns into account. The active and continuous participation of the public can also allow for alternative approaches to be made.

2.1.2 Doctrine and guidelines relating to the "prevent, reduce, offset" / mitigation hierarchy sequence

The Prevent, Reduce, Offset (PRO) sequence or the mitigation hierarchy advocated by United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI) and the Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP) are tools to help manage biodiversity risk, through a series of prioritised steps. They start with avoidance/prevention. This is encapsulated by Jacques Weber who stated "The best type of ecological compensation is that which should not exist". Prevention is followed by reduction of impacts and restoration of the ecosystem to its original state. Offsets are only to be considered after these initial three steps, and to address the residual impacts.

Although compensatory measures are often seductive, due to their innovative or job-creating nature, they are still experimental and rarely result in achieving all the specified aims (Chipeaux et al., 2016). In the case of aquatic environments, ecologists propose that at best only 75% of lost ecosystems can be restored (Moreno-Mateos et al., 2012). This means that we are unable to totally compensate for that which is destroyed. It should also be noted that the lack of feasibility of a compensatory measure can, in some cases, jeopardize the implementation of an entire project (MEDDE, 2014).

Mitigation Hierarchy

- **Prevention/Avoidance:** measures taken to avoid creating impacts from the outset, such as careful spatial or temporal placement of elements of infrastructure, in order to completely avoid impacts on certain components of biodiversity.
- **Minimisation:** measures taken to reduce the duration, intensity and / or extent of impacts (including direct, indirect and cumulative impacts, as appropriate) that cannot be completely avoided, as far as is practically feasible.
- **Rehabilitation/restoration:** measures taken to rehabilitate degraded ecosystems or restore cleared ecosystems following exposure to impacts that cannot be completely avoided and/ or minimised.
- **Offset:** measures taken to compensate for any residual significant, adverse impacts that cannot be avoided, minimised and / or rehabilitated or restored, in order to achieve no net loss or a net gain of biodiversity. Offsets can take the form of positive management interventions such as restoration of degraded habitat, arrested degradation or averted risk, protecting areas where there is imminent or projected loss of biodiversity.

(http://bbop.forest-trends.org/pages/mitigation_hierarchy accessed March 17)

In practice, if demands regarding the hierarchy are too harsh, the tendency will be to block projects and development policies. On the other hand, if the demand is too weak, degradation will have a heavy environmental impact. The correct application of the mitigation hierarchy will therefore determine how well the environmental considerations are integrated into the development scheme (Fig 2, Table 1)

Figure 2 Theoretical approach to the PRO and its effect on development projects

Table 1 Primary sequences & definitions guiding the EIA of a development project (Source: MEDDE, 2014)

<p>Preventative measure</p>	<p>A measure that modifies a project or an action in a planning document with a view to eliminating an identified negative impact that this project or action would cause (also known as a suppression measure).</p>
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<p>Reduction measure</p>	<p>A measure carried out after preventive measures, with a view to reducing permanent or temporary negative impacts of a project on the environment, in the construction or operational phases (also known as corrective measures, only in the case of water and aquatic environments).</p>
<p>Compensatory measure (offset)</p>	<p>A measure, the aim of which is to provide a counterpart to significant negative effects (either direct or indirect) of the project, that could not be avoided or sufficiently reduced. It involves priority implementation on the damaged or neighbouring site to guarantee the sustainability of its use. It should allow the overall conservation and, if possible, improvement to the environmental quality of the site.</p>
<p>Accompanying measure</p>	<p>A measure that is not undertaken within an obligatory regulatory or legal framework. It may be proposed to complement compensatory (or preventive or reduction) measures with a view to reinforcing their relevance and efficiency but is not in itself sufficient to ensure compensation (also known as a voluntary measure).</p>

2.1.3 No Net Loss (NNL) of biodiversity

The No Net Loss (NNL) concept addresses the balance between loss and gain in nature. “No net loss, in essence, refers to the point where biodiversity gains from targeted conservation activities match the losses of biodiversity due to the impacts of a specific development project, so that there is no net reduction overall in the type, amount and condition (or quality) of biodiversity over space and time. A net gain means that biodiversity gains exceed a specific set of losses (BBOP 2012).

It is linked to the idea that the sea, and particularly coral reefs, have a finite quantity of functions and thus ecosystem services (ES) for humanity and life on Earth. Thus if a number of given functions of a site are destroyed, it is necessary to recreate an equivalent number of the same functions (preferably simultaneously) on the same site or a site with which it is linked.

Ecologically functional elements are produced both as units of time and surface/volume. If these elements are damaged or destroyed by a project, the quantity of functional units lost increases over time.

Thus, if there is a time delay between the loss (works, various disturbances) and the recovery of the altered functions (offsets, restoration) for different reasons (work processes that prevent access to the site, delays in submission of authorization requests, holdups in administrative or negotiating processes with stakeholders, etc.), a net loss created during this lapse of time should be taken into consideration when determining compensatory measures.

Source: BBOP, adapted from Rio Tinto & Govt of Australia

Figure 3 Prioritization of prevention, reduction and offset measures

This concept underpins two methodological specificities: 1) consideration of losses over time that are accumulated and evaluated, and 2) a strict equivalence in the replacement of losses by gains so as to balance out natural functions. Apart from the fact that the effectiveness of a compensatory measure is not guaranteed (need for a precautionary margin), these specificities support the idea that one cannot simply compensate on a 1 for 1 basis, particularly if this compensation is undertaken after the project. Despite an acceleration of the natural repair process by the restoration of damaged environments, and the recuperation of the full range of initial functions following restoration measures, a shortfall not compensated for, is still noted as a natural asset. Within the spirit of NNL, an additional compensatory measure should be undertaken to compensate for this loss (for example, restoration of a proximal degraded area with identical ecological functions to those degraded by the project within the area under study). The NNL concept (which is the first of ten BBOP principles for well developed biodiversity offsets) has been embraced by several countries, including the USA which has a no net loss policy for wetlands.

According to UN Environment, there are 10 different stages of an EIA, which are encapsulated in the French procedures which follow:

1. Screening – determine if a proposal is subject to EIA as early as possible;
2. Scoping – identify priority issues and impacts to focus the EIA study;
3. Terms of Reference (ToR) – establish clear requirements and timelines for an EIA;
4. Public consultation – provide suitable opportunities for stakeholders to express their views;
5. Impact analysis – use best practicable methods;
6. Mitigation – identify appropriate measures to avoid, minimize or offset impacts;
7. Significance – evaluate the likelihood, range and severity of residual effects;
8. Preparation of EIA report – write in plain English to ensure decision makers and others understand the main issues and impacts and how they can be mitigated;
9. Review of EIA quality – determine if the report meets the ToR and the information is sufficient for decision-making;
10. Impact management and follow up – carry out, as necessary and appropriate, the following steps: – inspection/surveillance to check terms and conditions are implemented – effects monitoring to determine if impacts are as predicted – spot checks and audits to identify and address unanticipated problems – performance review of EIA outcomes and experience.

In the case of France, the procedure required by the legislator is broken down into eleven chapters described in article R 122-5 of the Environment Code. These eleven chapters can be grouped into six steps for the impact assessment of the environmental project, which are described below (Fig 4).

2.2.1 Preliminary framework (step 1/6):

This preliminary step, carried out by the project manager, involves the identification of a large range of potential environmental issues, a limited number of which will be dealt with more thoroughly in the EIA. The project manager may officially request background information (including studies from other projects, data sets etc) from government departments which could help in the identification of priority issues to be addressed. Such information helps determine whether the project should be the object of a declaration or an authorization under the Water Law, regarding the assessed risks of environmental damage and the project's technical and financial characteristics.

This step also allows for the identification of potential serious impacts, most notably on protected species.

The practical implementation of this preliminary scoping is the completion of the EIA design brief, that defines the studies to be carried out and can also serve as the basis for

the choice of a service provider (technical research firm, independent consultant) or internal organization to carry out the work.

Figure 4 : General approach to carrying out an EIA (source MEDDE, 2010)

2.2.2 Initial status (step 2/6):

The aim of this analysis is to establish the baseline in terms of the site's biological, physical, landscape and human environments, prior to the project's establishment. It should provide sufficient data for the identification, evaluation and prioritization of the project's possible impacts¹³ on the environment and allow for the site's rehabilitation at the end of the project's life.

Following preliminary scoping, this part of the study should also enable clarification of the environmental issues on the site¹⁵ in order to ascertain its sensitivity¹⁶. This can be carried out simultaneously with the rest of the EIA by one or several external service providers (technical research companies, consultants, etc.). However, separating the initial status and impact assessments from rest of the steps, runs the risk of a loss of coherence in the studies and is not recommended.

¹³ The effect (or pressure) describes the objective consequence of the project's technical characteristics on the environment. It represents a disruption of normal environmental conditions, of which the intensity and the mitigation (over distance and time) are quantitatively estimated. For example, underwater sounds caused by moving barges are approximately 160-170 dB at 1 m from the source (Nedwell et Howell, 2004).

¹⁵ The issue represents a value regarding ecological, heritage, aesthetic, cultural, patrimonial, ways of life, or economic concerns for a portion of the territory, given its current or foreseeable status. The issues are appreciated on the basis of criteria such as quality, rarity, originality, diversity, wealth, etc. The appreciation of issues is independent of the project: their existence extends beyond the concept of the project itself.

¹⁶ Sensitivity is a function of species' intrinsic characteristics and of the underwater habitats present in the area under study. It is defined by the capacity of species and concerned habitats to undergo change considering their capacity to resist to a given stress (resistance) and their ability to regenerate after having suffered damage (resilience). Sensitivity characterises the site in its initial state and is independent from characteristics of the planned project.

2.2.3 Study of alternatives (step 3/6):

This phase involves either the identification (through multi-criteria analyses) of the project that presents the least environmental impact¹⁷, or allows one to exclude those potential projects which would have unacceptable impacts¹⁸ on the environment. It is primarily based on a comparison of the potential sites for the project and an identification of the sites offering more advantages with respect to the environmental, technical, economic and social criteria described in the initial status analysis.

These studies allow for the identification and clarification of the constraints on potential projects, so as to highlight the project that best minimizes environmental impacts. Efficient implementation of this step, also allows for delays (linked to the need for additional research) to be avoided during project execution. More thorough studies are to be carried out on site to properly characterize the area and potential impacts as well as the necessary mitigatory measures to be taken.

2.2.4 Evaluation of project effects and impacts (step 4/6):

Building on the initial status and the project's technical characteristics, the EIA includes "an evaluation of the direct and indirect, temporary and permanent effects of the project on the environment, and especially on the flora and fauna, sites and landscapes, soil, water, air, climate, natural environments and biological balances, on the protection of goods and cultural heritage and, if needs be, on neighbourhood wellbeing (noise, vibrations, smells, light emissions), or hygiene, health, security and public sanitation" (Article R. 122-3 of Environment Code).

Of the numerous definitions of existing direct and indirect impacts, those of MEDDE (2012b), from the Guide « l'Etude d'impact sur l'environnement » (impact assessment on the environment) (MATE, 2001) are most relevant.

The direct effects and impacts thus translate into immediate consequences for the project, both in time and in space. Direct effects include:

- Structural effects due to the construction of the project itself (use of space under the influence of the project and related activities such as extraction sites and depots of materials, hydrodynamic disruptions, landscape damage, pollution plumes related to works, etc.). The corresponding impacts on the marine coastal environment are primarily related to the recovery or extraction of plants and animals (mangroves, coral reefs, seagrass beds etc.) or disruptions of ecological continuity (habitat fragmentation, deviation of ecological corridors, etc.). Thus the construction of a port could have a direct structural impact involving the destruction of organisms within the area (and where materials are stored) fragmentation of coastal zone habitats, a reorganization of ecological structures and exposure to sea swell and currents, etc.
- Functional effects relating to equipment use and maintenance (emission of a variety of substances, energy, noise, light, waste materials, pollution plumes

¹⁷ Impact is the transposition of the interaction of an effect and of a sensitivity on a scale of values (weak, average, high). Sensitivity combined with an estimate of pressures generated by an activity or the effects of a project allow the qualification and quantification of the level of a project's potential impact on the issue under study (impact = effect x sensitivity). Thus the acoustic impact of barges will be high on whales that are close to a shipping route, and it will be weak if the whales are located far from the shipping route (MEDDE, 2012a).

¹⁸ Some alternatives can, a priori, be prohibited or "off limits" due to regulations or a policy unique to the project manager.

relating to the works, etc.). Their impact may contribute to the disruption of the orientation of organisms, health and public sanitation, etc. Thus, the operation of a wastewater treatment plant discharging into the coastal zone could include among its effects degradation of water and sediment quality, and reduced salinity of surface water, decreasing environmental conditions for organisms living near the discharge pipe.

Indirect effects and impacts result from a cause-and-effect relationship originating from a direct effect. These could involve areas separate from the project or appear over time, but their impacts can be as significant as direct effects. These include:

- Knock-on effects or chain reactions spread, ripple like, through the environment in the absence of further interventions. Such effects may result in a drop or an increase in the size of populations, a drop in fertility, a selective advantage for certain groups of organisms, an accumulation of toxins within the food chain (bioaccumulation¹⁹, biomagnification²⁰), etc.
- The project's effects, particularly at the socioeconomic and lifestyle level (changes to competing activities, evolution of urban areas, impacts on traditional practices and uses). Their ecological consequences are fairly similar to the effects of chain reactions. They are generally differentiated over time and can be distant from the project site (new maritime routes, increased number of cars in circulation, attractiveness to tourists, new areas of activity, etc.)

Always with a view towards evaluating the project's effects and impact on the environment, regulations call for **cumulative effects and impacts** to be taken into consideration. Cumulative effects are defined as "changes to the environment as the result of an action, combined with other past, present and future human actions" (Fig 5). Cumulated effects are those generated by projects known at the time of the assessment (that have been subject to an impact assessment under the Water Law and a public enquiry, or an EIA for which the EA's opinion has been made public [Article R122-5-II of the Environment Code]). It is therefore necessary to determine the effects of a single project that may arise, and cumulative effects, linked to the interaction between several separate projects (MEDDE, 2012b). After this, verification that their combined effects are sustainable and that their activities are not incompatible should be made. Thus, several fish farming projects located close to each other could result in coastal eutrophication as well as attract large predators that would be incompatible with the operation of coastal resorts.

However, we currently have little knowledge of cumulative effects and their impacts on marine ecosystems (that are not necessarily the sum of the effects, as their interactions require further study), and the necessary coordination between project managers (information sharing) is often an obstacle to the successful completion of assessments. The preliminary scoping required of government departments also facilitates access to an inventory of projects that should be taken into account in the analysis of cumulative

¹⁹ Bioaccumulation is the absorption of chemical substances present in the environment, and the progressive concentration of these substances in certain tissues by organisms. In the case of toxic even rare substances in the environment, this phenomenon can result in toxic thresholds being reached and lead to pathologies.

²⁰ Bioamplification or biomagnification, is the increase in the concentration of a pollutant in organisms from the bottom and moving up the trophic or food chain. This phenomenon is the result of products that are not broken (or only very little) in the body of organisms in which they present. The classic examples are organic pollutants (pesticides, PCBs, etc.) and trace metals (mercury, lead, etc.).

impacts. It is important to clearly differentiate between a work programme, that brings together several sub-projects sharing the same purpose, and subject to a single EIA, and independent projects with combined impacts on the same area or ecosystem.

Figure 5 Different types of impacts to be considered in the EIA (source: MEDDE, 2012b)

Independent of the type of effects caused by a project, its temporal aspect should be taken into consideration. While some effects and impacts are associated with transitional phases of the project, others may have longer-term consequences for the environment.

Temporary effects and impacts disappear over time and are often linked with the construction phase of the project and the dismantling of infrastructure (access routes, etc.). These effects can be highly invasive for the environment (soil erosion, noise, water turbidity, light, different types of pollution, etc.) and have intense though short-term consequences for the environment (reduction of photosynthesis and coral reef reproduction due to sedimentation and the re-suspension of particulates, etc.). Such impacts can be defined as acute.

Permanent effects and impacts do not disappear during project operations (project waste and discharges, physical presence of infrastructure, servicing, maintenance, etc.). While their effects can be less intense than temporary effects, they may have a sustained impact on regulatory mechanisms over the long term (depletion of energy reserves, imbalances in demographic and trophic structures, fertility reduction, selective advantages for opportunistic organisms, etc.). These impacts can be characterized as chronic or diffuse in nature.

It should be made clear that some temporary effects can have permanent impacts. Thus, the transient storage of materials or the temporary construction of an access route for construction machinery in coastal areas, for example could result in the permanent destruction of organisms that are buried or crushed by the movement of machinery.

Accidental effects can also contribute to negative impacts via chance/unforeseen interactions. They are therefore not considered within the normal functioning of the project, but may arise due to a series of unfortunate circumstances (risk concept). They can be subject to particular regulations, particularly in the framework of installations classified for environmental protection (*Installations Classées pour la Protection de l'Environnement [ICPE]*) and licenced nuclear facilities (LNF) (see Specific EIA procedure).

2.2.5 Implementation of the PRO sequence (step 5/6):

Preventive measures aim to alleviate some of the predicted impacts, which are expected to persist despite choosing the alternative with the least environmental impact (priority preventive measures). This step is essential and should be the subject of special attention, noting that it is always best to control and often easier to limit damage than compensate for it later. These are followed by the Reducing or minimising step, whose measures contribute to mitigating the effect that causes the impact (eg choice of machines that generate less noise, use of narrow navigation routes, etc.) or reducing sensitivity to the impact such as: phasing the noisiest sequences on the construction site so they fall outside the periods of maximum vulnerability for whales during reproduction or gradually increasing noise pulses prior to the commencement of work, allowing the temporary departure of whales from the impact zone – "ramping up", etc.).

Appropriate provisions can limit certain impacts over time or space when others cannot be reduced ("residual" impacts). Only significant residual impacts, those that are always present despite reduction measures having been taken, or those that cannot be reduced, (and do not hinder the project's continuity), may be subject to compensatory measures. Such measures aim to enhance the overall initial value of the environments impacted by the project. This EIA step also involves the identification of the most relevant follow-up protocols (methods, indicators, sampling plans and strategies) and those that are best adapted to the monitored effects.²¹

2.2.6 Monitoring impacts (step 6/6):

The final step involves the establishment of protocols to monitor the project's effects as well as reduction measures over a period of time. These protocols must include monitoring prior to the initiation of works (i.e baseline assessment) and during each successive phase – construction, operations and in the case of temporary occupation of a Public Maritime Area, for a period of time monitoring following the dismantling of the operational unit (wave generating stations, fish farm, under-water quarry, etc.).

In the case of a project which has no programmed deadline for dismantling (urban infrastructures, port extension), regular monitoring during the operational phase can be planned over a period of time according to the intensity and duration of likely impacts. This period can later be modified according to reported impacts. In some cases this periodicity is defined by the Interdepartmental Water and Nature Mission (*Mission*

Inter-Services de l'Eau et de la Nature [MISEN]) that coordinates the water police and has a wide range of multidisciplinary skills.

When required, monitoring of the efficiency of compensatory measures (specific monitoring) will also take place.

The EIA is an iterative process and these six prioritized steps are not compartmentalized successive steps. In order for the EIA to effectively help decision-making by the project initiator and stakeholders, several iterative reviews of the different sequences are required. These can be carried out simultaneously, or at different times during the project preparation. They generally occur with an increasing level of detail, as a better understanding is acquired of measures at the initial stage of the project or during its implementation.

It is therefore necessary to take into consideration all phases of the project, as early as possible so as to develop comprehensive strategies. The inability to decrease an unacceptable impact after mitigation measures, can result in a re-evaluation of project alternatives. As previously mentioned, the EIA should take place **at the earliest possible stage** and follow a continuous, progressive and iterative process based on a thorough knowledge of the environmental issues at hand.

With regards to prioritizing avoidance/prevention over reduction, existing guidance speaks to the importance of following the hierarchical approach (BBOP 2012) As previously stated, Prevention is the first step, which deals with avoiding the impact at the source via alternate designs, timing or location. As this is only way of **ensuring absolutely no environmental degradation**, Project managers should carry out extensive reviews and employ use of The Precautionary Principle.

Within the sequence, once prevention is not an option, and environmental impacts cannot be avoided, reduction of impacts should follow. This can occur preferably via the implementation of impact mitigation techniques (work procedures and techniques, types of treatment, recycling, effluent treatment, etc.) at a reasonable cost so that residual negative impacts²³ are reduced as far as possible. In the marine environment these reduction measures can also take the form of use of hydrodynamic (tides, currents, upwellings, swells, turbulence, etc.) and hydro sedimentary mechanisms (erosion, accumulation, beach loss, beach accretion, etc.) via phasing of impacts or moving infrastructure in order to significantly reduce negative impacts. Reduction measures can also involve redirecting project discharges to deeper levels, beyond thermoclines or haloclines, so as to mitigate potential impacts on the coast. Such measures could result in project impacts being reversed or mitigated and thus qualify as prevention or reduction.

2.3 Scaling of compensatory measures

When major issues cannot be avoided and residual impacts deemed significant, compensatory measures become necessary. The application of compensatory measures

²³ Residual effects refer to those environmental effects predicted to remain after the application of mitigation measures

²¹ Technical aspects linked to the environmental assessment are dealt with in the chapter on the EIA's technical and methodological framework.

however does not justify damage from an environmental impact that could have been avoided. It should be noted that projects which produce residual impacts that could seriously affect ecosystem functions could still be approved if faced with arguments about the project's importance for the region's economy. It is therefore extremely important that compensation be sought for significant residual impacts, that are at the very least equivalent to the negative impacts on the environment.

The measures aimed at preventing, reducing and offsetting impacts, as well as conditions for the monitoring of their effects on the environment, are often defined in permit orders for development projects. As a result, the conception and planning of compensatory measures should be finalized prior to initiating the site's administrative authorization procedure.

The process of determining how much compensatory restoration is required to offset the discounted interim and perpetual losses of resources and their services is called scaling. The scale of compensatory restoration is conditional upon the choice of primary restoration actions and therefore each restoration alternative will have a different scale. Scales or ratios of compensation are typically greater than one to account for temporal losses of ecosystem services. Regulators generally conservatively inflate the ratios resulting from the assessment methods to account for uncertainties and potential restoration failure. Ratios vary greatly and it is difficult to provide a typical range of variation. It is common to see ratios between 1.5:1 to 3:1 but they can easily increase beyond 8:1 for richer ecosystems or more uncertain situations. The type of the primary restoration actions can be determined first, or scaling can be done for each alternative. Following the U.S. Oil Pollution Act, scaling processes can be organized into three categories: service-to-service, value-to-value, and value-to-cost.

The service-to-service (or resource-to-resource) scaling approaches measure directly the quality of the impacted and restored ecosystems using physical measurements of the ecosystems, and assume that they proxy for all ecosystem services. The metric used to measure the ecosystem may consist of a single indicator or of composite of indicators, in which case there is an additional issue related to the weighing of the various indicators used (Thur, 2006). To account for temporal differences between when the injury occurs and when the benefits of compensatory realization are realized, the estimated levels of ecological quality over time are discounted to the same base unit. Service-to-service approaches are most effective when the injured and replacement natural resources are of the same type and quality, and are of comparable value. The most common service-to-service approach is habitat equivalency analysis (HEA). The State of Florida recently developed an alternative approach, the Uniform Mitigation Assessment Methodology (UMAM).

Scaling options in the value-to-value category estimate the economic value of the lost resources and/or services, including temporary losses, instead of relying directly on the physical measurements. The economic value of a natural asset or a human-made asset and/or the services provided by that asset is the sum of all the present and future benefits that the asset (or the services/functions provided by the asset) provides. This is irrespective of the possibility that the resource (or its services/functions) and its derived benefits may not be valued (e.g. traded) in the market economy (i.e. not priced). This approach therefore relies on market and nonmarket economic valuation techniques, including financial analysis, travel cost, hedonic pricing, contingent valuation, conjoint analysis, and benefit transfer. These methods are used to estimate both the value of the loss and the value of the potential compensatory restoration actions. The monetary

values are discounted in these approaches as well to account for temporal differences between impact and restoration. The actions to be implemented and scale are chosen such that the value of the benefits they provide is equal to the estimated loss.

The third approach, value-to-cost, relies on economic valuation techniques to estimate the value of lost resources and/or services as in the value-to-value approach. However, no effort is made to value the benefits of potential restoration actions. Instead, the value of the injured natural resources becomes the compensatory budget for the restoration. Once recovered, the trustees use this amount to fund selected compensatory projects. Thus, there is equivalency between the value of the loss and the cost of the compensatory restoration projects, but there is no warranty that the benefits of those projects are sufficient to make the public whole from the injuries.

When using service-to-service and value-to-value approaches, the trustees are authorized to seek reimbursement for reasonable damage assessment costs, the cost of implementing the selected primary and compensatory restoration options (including monitoring and contingency costs), and interest on those amounts. When using a value-to-cost approach, however, they can only seek reimbursement for damage assessment costs on top of the payment for the estimated lost value.

- ⇒ Compensatory measures are aimed at providing an **ecological counterpart (equivalence) to the project's residual negative impacts – losses** (including the impacts resulting from accumulation with other projects) that could not be avoided or sufficiently reduced.
- ⇒ They are designed to **produce positive effects on the environment – gains** – that are of a **sustainable nature and are implemented with priority in functional proximity** to the site impacted by the project.
- ⇒ They must ensure **environmental quality is maintained if not improved**, in the case of degraded areas in the natural environments concerned at the pertinent territorial scale.

2.4 Sustainability of reduction and compensation measures

In order to guarantee the results of reduction and compensation measures, the project manager should be in a position to justify the sustainability of their effects: "The management period of the measures should be justified and established in accordance with the foreseen duration of impacts, the type of targeted natural habitat prioritized for the measure, management and the estimated time required to reach the objectives" (MEDDE, 2012a).

Sustainability is expressed specifically through ensuring that the Ecosystem Services of the site where measures were taken are not lost. The sustainability of measures might require the development of interactions with local stakeholders, so as to mobilize the best available tools.

A compensation measure must have long-term effects and any support site of compensatory measures should not be degraded by a new project. To ensure this, there should be implementation of regulatory measures for the preservation of any site impacted by the measure, utilisation of the best management tools, under the guidance of a scientific monitoring committee, etc. Within the framework of the EIA, the cost of

measures should be clearly indicated. This includes the occupation or use of public spaces.

The chosen monitoring programme, should allow for adaptive management of measures and should ensure the sustainability of their effects. The project manager may designate a service provider to oversee the measures, but the he/she remains legally responsible.

Many countries now employ PRO procedures, which were initially institutionalised by the USA with the *National Environmental Policy Act* in 1969 and the *Clean Water Act* in 1972, (Jacob, 2017; BBOP 2010). However, the compensation modalities depend on the country²⁶. The most common method for an environmental planner is to self-calculate the compensation or to entrust it to a third party. Some countries (Brazil, UK or Switzerland) choose to primarily utilise engineering consulting firms while others sometimes use public institutions, as in USA, where the government often uses *Mitigation Banks* for wetlands and *Conservation Banks* for endangered species.

Other countries use financial compensation instead of natural compensation and transfer a sum of money to a public organisation to compensate for the loss of biodiversity. This method can be used for total or partial compensation.

Methods for calculating compensation based on an evaluation of the environment before and after intervention are being developed in some countries such as Australia, USA, UK, Germany and Switzerland. PRO procedures are not used in some countries such as Kenya, where it is considered a right to destroy the environment, or in Vietnam and many Caribbean islands, where the new skills to calculate compensation are required.

As previously described, many countries are incorporating PRO procedures and using a variety of methods to calculate compensation. There is however, no one unified method for the objective analysis of minimization or compensation. Evaluation of ecological losses relies on a variety of methods developed by an equally variable number of consultants.

At the end of this document we propose a method developed by researchers (National Centre for Scientific Research [CNRS], Université Montpellier 3, Université de la Réunion and the French Coral Reef Initiative [IFRECOR], with support from the National Office for Water and Aquatic Environments [ONEMA]) called "MERCY-Cor" [French acronym for Method to Prevent, Reduce and Offset Impacts on Coral], that provides an overview in note form of the functional value of an environment according to the type of development carried out .

2.5 Public Participation within an Impact Assessment

Dialogue with the public, particularly in the early phases of project development is one of the keys to success (Lal et al., 2003). Stakeholder engagement should be carried out throughout the project's life, from the design and planning stage through construction,

²⁶ Rapport sur la réalité des mesures de compensation des atteintes à la biodiversité engagées sur des grands projets d'infrastructures, intégrant les mesures d'anticipation, les études préalables, les conditions de réalisation et leur suivi [en ligne]. Sénat Français [consulté le 01 Février 2018]. <http://www.senat.fr/rap/r16-517-1/r16-517-12.html>

operation and closure and not solely at the scoping and review stages (Landsberg *et al.* 2013). This term Stakeholders includes project developers, people who will be affected by the project (directly or indirectly) and those who have an interest in or can influence the outcome of a project (IFC 2017) Engagement can be enhanced if stakeholders are prepared prior to the official engagement.

Within this framework the EIA is a tool for dialogue among stakeholders so it is therefore important that this be clear, precise, and understandable particularly through its non-technical summary. Dialogue should be considered as crucial for the project's success and exchange with stakeholders will allow the project leader to better determine the issues.

2.6 Risks associated with not achieving impact assessment objectives

In addition to regulatory obligations that, if not met, will impede progress of an EIA, there is also a risk of not fulfilling the objectives of the assessment due to incomplete or incorrect analyses or negligence. The issues encountered include the **methods utilised, data collected and staff expertise**.

The wrong method, for example, not following the iterative sequence of the EIA and not completing each step prior to moving on to the next, could result in choosing an option that would provide undesirable impacts or inadequately compensating for the area under study. In addition, improper sampling or evaluation methods (natural environment, physical, chemical or social) can result in the underestimation of important elements, such as ecological function, traditional use, etc.).

Issues relating to the EIA can also be linked to the quality of the data collected and be especially relevant when disseminating information, particularly during the initial site analysis. Incomplete inventories of flora and fauna, or incorrect descriptions of biological, physical, chemical or social elements could lead to an incomplete or incorrect assessment of the project's potential impacts and/or ignore the presence of protected or keystone species in the area under study. Insufficient research into mitigation techniques best adapted to the proposed project impacts can also result in detrimental impacts, particularly on natural environments, that could have been more effectively dealt with.

Inadequate **expertise and experience**, especially on the part of persons responsible for carrying out the science required for EIA. This can result in errors (incorrect orders of magnitude, incorrect identification of species, confusion with units, etc.) which cannot be corrected *a posteriori*, but which are easily detected by a committee of experts prior to decisions being made. These errors can subsequently affect recommendations provided to and by the project manager. This type of error is usually due to inadequate technical capacities/ experience of staff as well as inaccurate professional references provided by candidates. Such shortcomings could lead to service providers compensating for their failings through more attractive tariffs.

Incomplete or incorrect site descriptions. Accurate site descriptions are clearly important for EIAs but are crucial in situations that call for hydrodynamic models for example. The project manager holds responsibility for the accuracy of information provided, particularly during the first steps in the EIA's implementation. Any inaccuracies will have consequences for the determination and scaling of the project's

effects, primarily the indirect effects which are often difficult to estimate, and could rapidly become speculative.

Finally, some errors are as the result of **incorrect interpretation of EIA results**, particularly during public consultations. These can be due to imprecise or unclear drafting, and the absence of a non-technical summary, among others. Repercussions from these errors can mislead stakeholders in public deliberations and impact users, local residents, naturalist associations, etc.

In all these situations overall EIA objectives can be compromised, leading to poor decisions being made. It is thus essential the project manager ensures support to and continuous monitoring of the agency responsible for carrying out the assessments from the first phase of the EIA, and that he controls all elements of the information provided (including clarity) to and received from this entity.

The following chapters aim to help users of this Guide to reduce the errors frequently observed in coral reef systems' impact assessments. As mentioned under the Section on EIA objectives, EIAs involve the descriptive and functional study of different environmental themes: the biological environment (ecosystems, flora, fauna, natural habitats, etc.), the physical environment (geography, bathymetry, current patterns, etc.), the chemical environment (water quality, sediments, etc.), the human environment (human activities, professional uses, etc.) and the landscape. The main criteria allowing an assessment of the level of issues particular to each environmental issue analysed are developed in the chapter on the technical and methodological framework of EIAs.

3 LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS

3.1 Overarching Policies

Environmental Impact Assessment legislation and policies vary around the world, since their introduction in the 70's, however the components Screening, Scoping, Assessment & Evaluation of impacts, Reporting of the Environmental Impact Statement, Review, Decision Making and Monitoring, Compliance, Enforcement and Auditing (See 3.1.4) are roughly the same. In the 1990s, The Convention on Biological Diversity²⁹ (CBD) (<https://www.cbd.int/convention/>) developed guidelines for the integration of biodiversity considerations into EIAs, which clearly includes those with impacts on coral reef and other marine ecosystems (COP 6 Decision V1/7). In addition to the aforementioned components, the guidelines indicate more clearly what is expected from biodiversity EIAs and the expertise required to do so. Other than these overarching guidelines from the United Nations, there have been regional collaborations to ensure that EIA guidelines and processes are fairly uniform. Take the example of the EIA Technical Review Guidelines³⁰ developed by the United States Environmental Protection

²⁹ Signed by 150 government leaders at the 1992 Rio Earth Summit, the Convention on Biological Diversity is dedicated to promoting sustainable development (<https://www.cbd.int/convention/>)

³⁰ <https://www.epa.gov/international-cooperation/eia-technical-review-guidelines-tourism-sector>

Agency (EPA) with Central America and Dominican Republic Free Trade Agreement (CAFTA-DR) partners for three priority sectors. Priority 2, the Tourism Sector is most relevant to this discussion, but for all three, the internationally recognized components of EIAs were introduced, Terms of References provided and information on requirements and standards, predictive tools and international codes provided.

As indicated in previous chapters, the impact assessment takes into consideration, the environmental sensitivity of the area, the scale and nature of proposed works, projects or schemes and their foreseeable impacts on the environment or human health, as well as the elements that by law are required to be presented in an impact assessment. For coral reefs, this calls for an even more comprehensive approach, including public policies linked to water quality, maritime security and regulations. Although these might not influence project impacts, the project's compatibility with these public policies must be detailed in the EIA (MEDDE, 2013).

3.2 European Policies

The following sections detail specific components from the French or European perspective; which can also be utilised in the environmental policies of other countries.

3.2.1 Titles authorizing the occupation of public maritime domain

Land developments require the issuance of a building permit by the department prefect with the assistance of the territorial departmental directorship [DDT under its French acronym]. At sea, the State being the owner of the Public Maritime Domain (PMD) the developer must obtain a title authorizing its occupation of the domain. This occupation title is temporary, precarious, revocable and gives rise to the payment of a fee. Different occupation titles can be granted according to the type of development. They are described in the 20 January 2012 circular relating to the sustainable and integrated management of the natural PMD.³¹ (Table 2).

These occupation titles are usually of limited duration, the principle of rehabilitation of occupied sites should be implemented and the dismantling of works and installations should take place after expiry of the PMD occupation permit. In order to obtain this authorization the project manager is obliged to carry out an environmental assessment of the site. The case may thus include an EIA and/or an impact study under the Water Law if the project is likely to affect a water resources, and/or a Natura 2000 evaluation of effects, if the project is likely to affect a Natura 2000 site.

Table 2 Different titles relating to Public Maritime Domain (PMD). This table is based on the circular of 20 January 2012 relating to the sustainable and integrated management of the natural PMD. It is not obligatory but provides a useful guide.

Type of works	Petitioner	Title	Type of application	Duration
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³¹ The natural PMD comprises: 1) the seabed and seabed subsoil, from the shore's high water mark; 2) salt ponds in direct, natural and permanent communication with the sea; 3) the sea's foreshore; 4) parties not alienated from the zone known as "*des cinquante pas géométriques*" (literally, "50 geometric steps zone") in overseas departments since the law of 3 January 1986 (Coastlines Act). The artificial PMD comprises port equipment and installations as works and installations relating to security and facilitating marine traffic.

Bridge decks and piles	Collectivities and their groups	Overlapping of effects (art. L2123-7 and 8, and R2122-2 of French CGPPP)	The public body is manager of this domain for a precise aspect, the State remaining competent for the others.	No limit on time imposed. Possible return according to terms of the convention.
Median strips (public areas, roads) Port extension	Collectivities and their groups Government agencies	Management transfer (art. L2123-3 to 6, and R213-9 of CGPPP)	The natural PMD undergoes works that thus grants it an artificial status of public ownership and thus loses its "maritime" character.	No limit on time imposed. Possible return according to terms of the convention.
Individual moorings Infrastructure lacking general interest built prior to the Coastal Law Beach nourishment Experiments Management stretches of coast	Collectivities and their groups Association	Temporary occupation permit (TOP) (art. 2122-1 to 3 of CGPPP)	TOP granted on a personal basis, is precarious and revocable: it can be terminated at any time if the interest of the domain or the general interest so justifies it. Case law also requires that the occupation title and its duration be adapted to the scale of the works undertaken or to the activity carried out.	Revocable at any time.
Offshore wind turbines offshores Submarine cables Outfalls in the sea Canalizations Water intakes and outfalls Defence works against the sea (dikes, rock fills, groins, breakwaters, etc.) Public slipways Artificial reefs	Collectivities and their groups Private individuals and general interest	Concession for the use of PMD outside ports (art. L2124-3 and R2124-1 to R2124-12 of CGPPP)	Installations or works to benefit the general public, a public service or an operation of general interest (in the collective interest)	30 years maximum, renewable
Quay areas and light equipment	Collectivities and their groups	TOP for quay area and light equipment	Articles R. 2124-39 to R. 2124-55 of CGPPP	15 years maximum
Extraction of aggregates or liquid or gaseous hydrocarbons	Corporations, economic interest group	Concessions for the extraction of aggregates	Exploitation of mineral or fossil substances in the sea floor within the public domain for commercial ends.	35 years
Marine aquaculture	Operators	Marine aquaculture concessions	Activities exploiting the biological cycle of marine species..	35 years

3.2.2 Common law and impact assessments

At the European Community level Directive 2011/92/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of 13 December 2011 concerning the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects establishes the principles of projects' environmental assessment. The "public and private works, that by their nature, their dimensions or their localization, a likely to have considerable effects on the environment or on public

health are preceded by an EIA" (Article L. 122-1 of Environment Code, modified by Article 230 of the law regarding national commitment to the environment), but only those projects listed in the Annex to article R. 122-2 of the Environment Code (Annex 6) are systematically subject EIA, irrespective of size or cost.³²

This list distinguishes projects that are subject to compulsory EIAs and those that may be after a preliminary verification on a case-by-case basis carried out by the EA. This case-by-case study concerns the need to carry out, or not as the case may be, an EIA according to the nature of the project, its location or the sensitivity of the environment. For this purpose a form requesting a study on a case-by-case basis is completed by project proponents. The EA has 35 days to present a reasoned opinion. Otherwise, the obligation to carry out an EIA is deemed to be implied.

The carrying out of the EIA and its content fall under the responsibility of project managers who assume all associated costs (field survey, analyses and enquiries, drafting and dissemination of EIA report). They thus decide to carry out studies, chosen among alternatives examined and ensure financing, but they are not compelled to carry out EIAs themselves. If the required competences do not exist among the existing team, it is recommended that private services be sought through research firms or specialized external consultants. With a view to strengthening the credibility of cases and ensure transparency in final decision-making, the final document should in all cases indicate the precise names of EIA authors and data sampling operatives (GEODE, 2014).

In the case of projects having to be declared of public interest (roads, bridges, energy production, water treatment plants, etc.), it is necessary to prepare a dossier (known as dossier of public interest [DUP under its French acronym]) the content of which is established in Article R. 11-3 of the Expropriation Code. This dossier includes an explanatory note presenting legal aspects, materials and geographic elements of the operation: within this framework it should anticipate and describe the set of administrative authorization procedures and the necessary environmental assessment procedures necessary for project implementation (CGDD, 2013).

3.2.3 Procedures specific to impact assessments

Certain specific procedures complement statutory law on previously presented impact assessments. They concern such matters as transport infrastructure, ICPEs and basic nuclear facilities (LNF). EIAs carried out within the framework of these categories of development, projects and works, cited in the Annex to Article R. 122-2 of the Environment Code, must contain certain additional information linked to the specificities of their activities, in addition to information previously cited in this Guide.

Thus, Article R. 122-5 of the Environment Code includes provisions in the case of transport infrastructure under items 5 to 9 of the table annexed to Article R. 122-2 of the Environment Code, the "the EIA will be, among other things, completed with an analysis of the ecological risks and potential risks linked to land development, agricultural and forest development schemes, relating particular to the use of agricultural, natural or forest lands involved in the project, according to the scope of foreseeable works and the sensitivity of the environments concerned" (CGDD, 2013).

³² Since Decree n°2011-2019 of 29 December 2011 reforming impact assessments, the Environment Code has eliminated the financial limit (generally €1.9 million all taxes included) which exempts a series of projects from environmental assessments due to their low cost. It now exhaustively lists projects systematically subject to EIAs on technical grounds (CGDD, 2013). Since 1 June 2012, some permit dossiers, not previously considered, are also subject to EIAs, according to their importance and the nature of their services.

The EIA will be completed within the ICPE framework, by a hazard assessment which one of the items required in the permit application. In the case of INBs, the EIA will be completed by a risk management study (CGDD, 2013).

3.2.4 Permit application or declaration under the Water Law

The procedure of the Water Law dossier relating to the nature of work undertaken in coastal marine environments concerns the plants, structures, works and activities [IOTA under its French acronym] not covered in ICPE regulations that have a potentially important impact on aquatic environments and public security, as defined in Water Law nomenclature³³ (Annex 6).

Projects exceeding certain thresholds mentioned in this nomenclature require a permit or a declaration³⁴ (Article R. 214-1 of the Environment Code). In all instances they are thus subject to an impact assessment of their effects on water and aquatic environments (Articles R. 214-6 of the Environment Code for the permit procedure and R. 214-32 for the declaration procedure). In the framework of the permit procedure and the declaration, the impact document must specify "whether foreseen corrective or compensatory measures apply".

This document should also include an analysis of the project's compatibility, integrating corrective or compensatory measures, as well as the French Master Plan for Water Development and Management [SDAGE under its French acronym] and the Water Development and Management Scheme [SAGE under its French acronym] if the latter exists and has been approved prior to committing to the public enquiry.

The authorization under the Water Law should be acquired for works to be carried out. In the case of IOTAs subject to declaration, works cannot start prior to expiry of the period during which the prefect can object to the planned operation. The Water Police involves all surface and ground water and waters that are public or not, maritime and coastal waters as well as wetlands. The ecological continuities and dependent species of these aquatic environments are also contemplated in the procedure (CGDD, 2013).

3.2.5 Natura 2000 impact assessments

Under Natura 2000 sites, IOTAs likely to have a significant effect on ecological interests justifying the classification of a site must undergo an evaluation of their impacts in light of the site's conservation objectives. This is known as a Natura 2000 impact assessment (Environment Code, Article L. 414-4).

³³ Under the Water Law, plants, structures, works and activities [IOTA under its French acronym] that could have an impact on water or the aquatic environment must involve a declaration or a permit request by the party wishing to carry them out in accordance with headings specified in Article R.214-1 of the Environment Code and under which they fall. The nomenclature includes 34 headings identified under 5 titles: Title 1: Extraction; Title 2: Emissions; Title 3: Impacts on the aquatic environment; Title 4: Impacts on the marine environment; Title 5: Authorization scheme interpreted as authorization under Articles L214-1 and those following of the Environment Code.

³⁴ The procedure for the Water Law dossier relating to the nature of works carried out in an area of coastal water concerns IOTAs that potentially have an important impact on the environment and public safety as defined in the Water Law's nomenclature section. According to the hazards they represent and the seriousness of their potential effects on the water resources and the aquatic environment, these IOTA may be subject to: 1) Authorization: a thorough investigative procedure with public enquiry and terminating with an authorization; 2) Declaration: a simple investigative procedure without a public enquiry and terminating with the issuance of a declaration receipt with the possibility of refusal of the works to be carried out.

A Natura 2000 impact document could be necessary even if the project is not located within a Natura 2000 site. This could be the case of certain projects situated near the site having a significant impact on outstanding ecological elements and having justified the classification of the site within the European Natura 2000 network (Environment Code, Article R. 414-19 – R. 414-29). In the case of a request that is already part of an administrative process (permit request, declaration), the Natura 2000 impact dossier is integrated in the project's permit request or administrative declaration. The complete dossier must then be made available to the service responsible for the procedure (MEDDE, 2014).

In the event of overlapping impact documents the following rules apply (Environment Code, Articles R. 214-6, R. 214-32 and R. 414-22): 1) if a project is subject to an EIA, an impact study under the Water Law and a Natura 2000 impact assessment, the texts specify that the EIA can replace the other two, if the study includes all the information required for these different environmental evaluations; 2) if a project is subject to a Natura 2000 impact assessment and, either an impact study under the Water Law or an EIA, the latter may suffice if it includes all the elements of the former; 3) if a project is subject to an EIA and an impact study under the Water Law, the EIA alone may suffice if it includes all the elements of the impact assessment.

3.2.6 Exemption from strict protection of species

The request for exemption or waivers from the strict protection of species is required when the project is likely to infringe the law when one of the following activities involving these species is carried out: 1) the temporary or definitive capture for ends other than scientific ones; 2) the destruction of eggs or animals; 3) intentional disturbance; 4) the destruction, alteration or degradation of reproduction or resting sites; 5) the cutting, damaging, tearing up, collecting or the removal of plants for ends other than scientific ones; 6) the transport, hawking, use, holding, offering for sale, the sale or purchase of animals and plants (CGDD, 2013).

The attention of the applicant is to be drawn to the fact that waivers granted under Article L. 411-2 of the Environment Code are not, in themselves, authorizations to implement the project. They merely allow, through a waiver, the carrying out of activities relating to protected species that would be legally sanctioned without it. The applicant must thus prepare an exhaustive request for exemption that accurately reflects statutory prohibitions implicated in the project. Respect for protected species' legislation and the eventual possibility of an exemption from prohibitions thereto does exempt them from other statutory prohibitions and the completion of operative administrative formalities regarding environmental and nature protection (MEDDE, 2012b).

In the case of environmental impact assessments, a dossier requesting a waiver or exemption regarding the disturbance or destruction of protected species is necessary as soon as a negative residual impact on a species is noted. This dossier should be particularly well justified if the involved species are of significant interest (IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, CITES' indexed species, ZNIEFF inventories (Natural Zone of Ecological, Animal and Plant Importance), traditional value, etc.). This exemption might also be necessary in the case of incomplete inventories carried out during an initial status analysis, without this choice being justified. It must cover all species and habitats which could suffer from a residual effect, and be established on the basis of inventories that are as thorough as possible. It must specifically explore the importance of the

potential impact on local populations, the absence of an alternative solution, the demonstration of the sustainability of the species after the implementation of compensation proposals and protocols for the implementation of compensation measures (fishing concessions, occupation of the PMD, hiring of scientific monitoring, etc.) The dossier must enable the analysis of experts who may not be familiar with the geographical location of the study area (MEDDE, 2012b).

Government offices and waiver application officials (environmental services within the DEAL³⁵) have to ensure that a precisely defined administrative procedure is followed, and therefore have the mission to check this satisfies legislative requirements. They also play a key role in informing the public and other stakeholders. Project proponents are advised to approach these services as early as possible in the project development process so as to address and integrate the issues pertaining to protected species as soon as possible. It is also a question of ensuring coherence between the exemption procedure and other environmental procedures to which the project may be subjected, such as impact studies (e.g. projects or installations classified for environmental protection), Natura 2000 impact assessments, and impact studies under the Water Law (MEDDE, 2012b).

The ecological relevance of opinions both of experts called upon by the National Council for the Protection of Nature (CNPN under its French acronym) and decisions taken must be clearly understood by the project proponents themselves to ensure the optimum application of resulting measures. Concerned authorities should provide an adequate explanation of the reasons behind their opinions or decisions. Finally, a monitoring and control system of procedures for the implementation of waivers should allow government departments and authorized inspecting officers of regulatory measures pertaining to protection of wildlife and flora to ensure respect for the commitments and obligations of project proponents (MEDDE, 2012b).

3.2.7 Regulation relating to professional diving and nautical facilities

Interventions carried out within the framework of impact assessments or studies involving diving require that site operators have a Hyperbaric Certificate of Aptitude [CAH under its French acronym], issued by the National Institute of Professional Diving [INPP under its French acronym]³⁶ according to the depth of intervention. They also have to undergo a medical check-up according to regulatory conditions specified in

³⁵ The Regional Directorate for Environment, Development and Housing [DREAL under its French acronym] was established to replace the DRE, DRIRE and DIREN of each region with a view to centralizing environmental efforts. A DREAL is thus found for each region in France, with the exception of the Ile-de-France that has a Regional Interdepartmental Directorate for the Environment and Energy [DRIEE under its French acronym] and the French overseas departments and territories of an Environmental, Development and Housing Directorate [DEAL under its French acronym]. There are thus 21 DREALs, 5 DEALs and 1 DRIEE. These directorates have the mission to implement the French environmental pact (Grenelle de l'environnement). They play a role in all areas (housing, transport, land planning, etc.) in reducing to a maximum signs of human action on the environment. Regional prefects supervise the DREALs, DEALs, and DRIEEs in their respective regions.

³⁶ Professional diving for scientific research is interpreted as all underwater diving aimed at "collecting information, data or samples for research or teaching purposes; to place and maintain experimental equipment and the necessary instruments for such activities" (Decree of 30 October 2012). This type of diving falls within mention B "other subaquatic activities", outlined in 2° of II of Article R 4461-28 of Decree dated 11 January 2011. Subaquatic interventions requiring heavy materials, motors driven by a force other than that of the diver, or raising techniques and special works should be carried out by professional divers coming under the mention A, "activities of divers".

Decree N° 2011-45 of 11 January 2011 relating to the protection of divers working in hyperbaric environments. A professional liability insurance policy for operators, specially adapted to the specific requirements of the activity, is also necessary. The project manager is free to request copies of these documents as part of the technical and financial proposals of service providers together with curriculum vitae of those concerned.

The registration of diving support vessels is also subject to a special regulation. While sport diving clubs can benefit from exemption using vessels registered as pleasure craft, the logistics of vessels linked to professional diving involves registration with maritime affairs as cargo-carrying vessels. Nor are fishing and passenger vessels authorized to transport active professional divers. This regulation linked to the status of the vessel can, in certain places, limit the possibilities of an intervention and attention could, after the revision of technical and financial proposals of the service providers intervening in the hyperbaric environment, be provided to logistical collaborators (subcontractors) contemplated within the EIA framework.

3.3 Primary projects subject to environmental impact assessments or Water Law impact assessments

We have seen that, according to Annex R. 122-2 of the Environment Code, certain categories of projects are subject to EIA while others are subject to a case-by-case procedure, or not subject to an EIA under Annex III of Directive 85/337/CE.

Certain projects, likely to present dangers for "the water resource and aquatic ecosystems, specifically taking into consideration the existence of zones and perimeters established for water protection and aquatic environments", are also subject to an authorization regime or declaration under Article R. 214-1 of the Environment Code (Water Law), calling for the preparation of a specific impact document which is to contain details as specified in Article R. 214-6 of the Environment Code for authorization procedures and R. 214-32 for declaration procedures (Fig. 6).

Figure 6 Waste water treatment plant at Sainte Rose, La Réunion (© IPR) – Example of project subject to impact assessment under the Water Law with a pollution load (DB05) of 13.38 kg in 2014

A Natura 2000 authorization regime is created for projects that do not benefit from any other administrative authorization, approval or declaration regime or declaration, and susceptible to having an impact on a Natura 2000 site (CGDD, 2013).

Environmental impact assessments in coral reef environments overseas may thus fall under different regulatory frameworks, specifically according to the type of project, its size and its location with regard to a protected area.

These projects can have quite different technical characteristics, particularly regarding: 1) their constructible surface and geographic range; 2) the quantity and toxicity of substances discharged into the environment; 3) the modification and artificial coastline interventions; 4) the extractive (non-renewable resources or not) or non-extractive nature of the exploitation; and 5) generally, anything relating to effects on the environment, whether these be indirect, temporary or permanent.

Within this context it appears difficult to paint a detailed picture of all cases possibly arising. The types of projects presented in the annex are not exhaustive and do not consider the possible presence of a Natura 2000 site, but they do provide a glimpse at the current regulatory framework and cover the cases most frequently subject to EIAs or impact assessments in French Overseas Territories' marine and coastal environments (Chipeaux et al., 2016). These include:

- industrial and urban waste
- coastal works, projects or schemes
- prospection, extraction and storage of materials from quarries, mines and dredging processes
- exploitation of renewable natural resources

The description of each type of project is completed in the annex by a list of most frequent potential impacts on the natural and human environment which, although not exhaustive, does represent the impacts to be systematically evaluated.

3.3.2 Procedural incidents, accidents and anomalies (unauthorized impacts)

Although Installations Classified for the Protection of the Environment [ICPE under its French acronym] related risks are subject to a specific evaluation procedure, no project is immune from a major failure or a total breakdown of operations. Such failures, involving environmental and health impacts, even human safety, can be extremely serious, affect both production and processing capabilities (industrial, nuclear, petrochemical, chemical breakdowns, etc.), means of transport (total rupture of a pipeline, grounding of a ship, oil spill, etc.) and storage systems (rupture of containers, chemical spills, flows of terrigenous materials, etc.) (Fig. 7).

These incidents are not usually considered in impact assessments that only rarely take catastrophic scenarios into consideration. With the likelihood of such occurrences being extremely rare, this type of damage is covered by other intervention plans no longer involving EIAs (National Plan for the Organization of Assistance in case of Catastrophes [ORSEC under its French acronym], and Maritime Pollution Plan [POLMAR under its French acronym], etc.) and an enquiry procedures are initiated. The origins and responsibilities of these unauthorized impacts are thus studied in court with damages, compensations and other rights being considered as the case may be. Repairs may thus be covered by project managers if they are declared liable (non-respect of procedures, maintenance error, no implementation of reduction measures, etc.).

Figure 7 Grounding of the Chinese vessel Chen Neng 1 on the Australian Great Barrier Reef in 2010 (©Maritime Safety Queensland)

For several countries, the operator whose activity caused the damage is held liable. The USA applies this principle with The Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act of 1980 (CERCLA), and with the Superfund Amendments of 1986. More than twenty years later, the European Commission wrote a White Paper on environmental liability and created a final document: a European environmental liability directive (2004/35/EC) (Ashford, 2010). These documents stipulate that the operator whose activity has caused environmental damage (i.e. accidental impact) or poses an imminent threat of such damage occurring, is held financially responsible for the implementation of compensatory measures, and thus encourages operators to adopt measures and develop clean practices to minimize the risk of environmental damage; in essence invoking the polluter-pays principle.

Unauthorized impacts can also be of a voluntary nature, such as in the case of clandestine dumping of a different of substances, materials or pollutants in the marine environment without previous authorization or in violation of previously established legislation. This is particularly the case of ships' ballast water. Ballasting involves the emptying or filling of ballasts with sea water (Fig. 8). This usually contains solid muddy particles and living animal or plant particles that can still be alive on dumping. They can thus be expelled into different ecosystems and cause damage (CMI, 2003). The International Maritime Organization (IMO) estimated that only in 2004, approximately 10 billion cubic metres of water were transported around the world in the ballasts of 45,000 commercial vessels. Current legislation tends towards obliging vessels to have a management plan for ballast water so as to avoid jeopardising ecosystems with the possible transport of invasive species.

Figure 8 Ship ballasting in process (© P. Sussac)

4 IMPACT ASSESSMENTS: TECHNICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

4.1 Definition of study areas

Although frequently considered as part of preliminary studies, in practice, the definition of study areas can be modified or refined during the study so as to take the results of different EIA sequences into account.

Study area limits should be defined by the project's expected area of influence, likely to have an impact on environments. In the marine environment these limits are difficult to define *a priori* due to the considerable movement of water masses and difficulties in determining functional ecological units. The use of hydrodynamic modelling is often necessary, although numerous studies identify the area on the basis of bibliographic references and disseminated information. Large local current patterns (trade wind currents, tides, emptying and filling of reef passes, etc.), that are often well known and documented, can also provide information on areas potentially impacted by the project. The type of effect can also have a bearing on its distribution and mitigation. Thermal anomalies or halines, for example, will tend to isolate impacted water masses (freshwater lens, thermal convection cell, etc.) and allow their displacement over large distances.

The study area also depends on the thematic areas under study, site conditions and the primary project characteristics. Thus, the presence of an ecological corridor, an outstanding landscape, migratory corridors for whales, fishing areas of strategic interest, etc. could considerably modify the area studied. The general geometry of the project's footprint, whether it be concentrated³⁷ (fish farm, wave generating station, wind farm, etc.) or linear³⁸ (outlet, cable, drinking water pipeline, coastal roads and seawalls, etc.) will determine the methodology to be used in defining the study area.

And finally, the same sampling effort is not required for the entire surface of the study area. The area closest to either the area of influence or its discharges will be subject to a greater intensity of effects than areas further away which will have benefited from dilution and dissemination. Thus, it is often a question of several interrelated project study areas comprising small direct areas of influence and larger areas subject to indirect effects. In the case of large projects, three interlocking levels are often used: close study areas (immediate effects), middle (delayed or distant effects), and distant (cumulated or cumulative effects).

This chapter proposes study area definitions for projects carried out in tropical coral reef areas. In each case the perimeter of the area under study is further refined with the iterative EIA approach.

37 A project is considered concentrated when the area of influence or footprint is basically arranged around its centre of gravity (that develops around one same point), independently of the total area of influence. It might be a case of buildings or collections of buildings, material storage or extraction areas, or energy, port or airport infrastructures.

38 A project is considered linear when the area of influence or footprint is distributed along a narrow stretch (width much shorter than length), rectilinear or meandering, generally over long distances. Examples of linear projects would include main roads and maritime channels, pipelines or channels for fluids, materials, energy, electricity, etc.

4.1.1 Concentrated projects

In such cases, the study area to be considered must cover: 1) potential sites to be established (area of influence or footprint), 2) sectors directly impacted by works and operations, and 3) areas with remote, indirect and secondary effects. The project manager should also propose alternative sites and study areas sufficiently large to cover the entire areas under the influence of each scenario envisaged. This enables adjustments to be made to the project, should priority issues come to light and will allow for either the prevention/reduction of impacts.

The areas under direct influence of operations are delimited in such a manner as to cover all environments likely to be directly disturbed during works (maritime access routes, area for the storage or extraction of materials, dispersion area of turbid plumes, etc.) and during the project's operational phase (direct or treated discharges, noise, light, different types of pollution, etc.). Work involving the extraction of materials, for example could result in coral mortality due to turbidity plumes.

Buffer zones are often advised to be added around the area which is directly affected, in case the impacts are greater than expected. The size of the zone will be site specific but in the absence of complementary environmental data, a circular area with a minimum 500 metre radius, centred on the project's area of influence or outlet discharges is advised. This proposed size should be re-evaluated depending on the technical aspects of the project (dimension, type of discharge, volumes discharged, etc.).

The extent of areas suffering indirect and secondary effects, is based on functional ecological units. The design of this should be based on the type of project and the connectivity between natural habitats in the area. For example, coastal construction could lead to visual and acoustic disruptions, which could hinder the attempts of marine turtles to nest, thus impacting future population numbers.

Generally, if the animals, under study are mobile (fish, turtles, birds, marine mammals) the greater the study area required for the project (evaluation of indirect and secondary ecological consequences of damage). Inversely, the smaller the study area around the project, the greater the need for field research to be carried out in a specific, replicable and exhaustive manner (assessment of the degradation).

4.1.2 Linear projects

Linear projects are generally more complex to define than concentrated projects. The existence of numerous options entails the use of a vast area; however the marine equivalent is barely comparable with its terrestrial counterpart due to limitations caused by conducting work in the marine environment, such as time restrictions. Three successive steps are therefore recommended, moving from preliminary through intermediate to detailed study phases.

The preliminary study phase aims to select (after comparing several possible options) that with the least environmental impact. For this phase the study area represents a place where the different development elements and alternatives exist. This study area is generally very large, as it must allow for extensive research re impacts and thus justify the choice of one measure over another. At this stage, the study of natural environments is fairly general and depends on publicly available documents (regulations, biodiversity inventories, geomorphological and natural habitat maps, etc.) as well as consultations with experts on marine flora and fauna (fish, corals, turtles, marine mammals, etc.).

During the concentrated study phase, the study area should be of a size to include potentially impacted functional ecological units, based on the scale of the project. This allows for the project to be refined (proposal for a stretch of viaduct instead of a sea dike for example) through multicriteria analyses (bibliographic consultations, analysis of aerial photographs, overall site reconnaissance by marine specialists etc.) so as to avoid particularly important or rare habitats (coral reefs, mangroves, protected species habitats, etc.). It is at this stage that ecological corridors and migratory pathways are studied in depth and the overall functionality of the impacted ecosystem addressed in terms of spatial and temporal trends. At the end of this stage, one should be able to determine how the project would develop with the least environmental impact.

The detailed study phase, which is carried out in the most sensitive sites and in each of the areas addressing the issues at hand, must be implemented in the same manner as a concentrated project. In other words, it should consider the project's footprint, the direct area of influence of works and operations, and the areas that are affected at a distance from the project site.

As in the case of concentrated projects, it may be useful to include a buffer zone around the development's footprint, that will encompass all ecological impacts. This buffer zone will be defined according to the same criteria as for concentrated projects, however a strip with a minimum length 500 metres on both sides of the project should be established in the absence of environmental data.

4.2 Study of biotic factors

The term **biocenosis/biological communities** was introduced into scientific language in 1877 by the German biologist Möbius. It speaks to interacting and interdependent organisms, living in the same biotope/habitat at a specific time and which therefore reflect general environmental conditions. According to Möbius, this environmental state would provide conditions favourable for on site reproduction, which ensures the group's survival and ability to maintain its community structure. An **ecosystem** is comprised of the biological community (biocenosis) and the site (biotope).

Each animal or plant species is characterised by its way of life (occupation of space, rate of activity, etc.), its demands (nutritional and physiological) and its adaptive potential (resistance, resilience): together these characteristics define its ecological niche. It is thus not simply a question of location and use of space. The ecological niche represents the role of each species in the ecosystem (Fig. 9). This concept allows for a better understanding of relationship between species (competition, cohabitation, association, etc.) and an interpretation of some evolutionary biological mechanisms. The occupation of new ecological niches can favour the appearance of new species (scope of natural range of indigenous species or colonization by exotic and possibly invasive species). These niches can also be interconnected, either by direct links among juxtaposed habitats (continuous ecosystem) or by relays along ecological corridors (fragmented ecosystem).

Figure 9 Example of a healthy coral reef ecosystem in the French Overseas Territory, Mayotte (© J. Wickel)

In summary, the study of biological communities revolves around three complementary disciplines (Fig. 23) (Lavergne et al., 2005; Spataro, 2008): 1). The Composition of populations includes species name, composition and heritage interest of the species comprising the community; 2) Structure refers to how the elements of the population are organized; and 3) Function relates to an analysis of biological processes from two perspectives: the quantification of individuals and their interdependency (feeding, predation, associations). These three approaches are detailed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 10 Composition, structural and functional approaches of the biocenosis (Spataro, 2008)

4.2.1 Composition of populations

Among evaluation criteria of environmental issues and biological balances, the composition description of populations is probably the most immediate and the most frequently used in EIAs. That pertaining to biocenoses is to be formed by a number of species that can be very high, exceeding thousands or even tens of thousand in complex environments such as coral reefs. It is the coexistence of all these species in the same place of limited scope that characterises diversity. However, for several reasons this apparently simple notion – the number of species – is difficult to specify and quantify, even in its most elementary form that is still referred to as species richness (Lamotte, 1995).

A major difficulty lies in the unconfined character of the biocenosis concept, just as in all complex ecological formations. A biocenosis is an extremely vague entity thus rendering the specific diversity very difficult to measure, making it necessary to consider it at the level of certain taxonomic groups that contribute to this diversity (fish, corals, algae) or certain communities (plankton, sedimentary macrofauna, etc.) reducing it to a sampling effort having been required for its inventory (time, surface, volume). A second difficulty lies in the interpretation of species diversity values. Although it may appear logical that a stable, preserved environment has a greater number of species than the same environment once disturbed and degraded, the reality is more difficult to determine.

It is recognized that a structured ecosystem in a good state of conservation has a more species than an immature or degraded ecosystem subject to frequent and heavy impacts. On the other hand, no linear relationship can be established between the conservation status of an ecosystem and species richness (Odum, 1974). Thus, the introduction of exotic species will cause an increase in species richness, without however

demonstrating an improvement in the environment's conservation status. This diversity increase is usually transient and can be followed, in the case of a proliferation of introduced species, in a drastic reduction in biodiversity (disappearance of certain populations), as in the case of the lionfish in the West Indies.

Furthermore, optimum species diversity appears to be reached when natural disruptions (storm surges, rain fall, etc.) are neither too rare nor too frequent and their intensity is insufficiently strong to result in total ecosystem destruction (regressive ecological successions). In these conditions certain colonizing species, specific to weak ecological structures, can cohabit with more competitive species found in structured ecosystems. This situation, known as the "Intermediate Disturbance Hypothesis" (Connell, 1978), illustrates the difficulty of interpreting variations in the number of species found between monitoring events and the care required when using this single evaluation criterion.

Another aspect of the description of biological communities, is the assignment of a value to certain "outstanding" species (heritage interest etc). This distinction can be given to a species for a single or several characteristics linked to, for example, extractive benefits or benefits generated from not extracting them (interest in fisheries, tourism, scientific, landscape, aquariums, coastal protection, etc.); to their existence and bequeathed values (traditional value, notions of rarity, endemism, aesthetics, etc.); to their interest as bio-indicators (sensitivity to eutrophication, hyper-sedimentation, saline or temperature anomalies, etc.); to their role in the ecosystem (keystone, engineering, facilitator or symbiotic species, etc.); or to their threat level or regional and international conservation status (protected species, ZNIEFF inventories, CITES index, IUCN Red List, etc.) (Fig. 11). Intrinsic or contextual characteristics of outstanding species provide socio-ecological interpretive keys of animal inventories. Nonetheless, these censuses consider neither abundance, maturity, size or conservation status of observed populations and only reflect a preliminary exploratory approach to natural environments.

Figure 11 Hawksbill turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*), Critically Endangered according to IUCN's Red List of Threatened Species and protected nationally, here on the Mayotte coral reef (© J. Wickel)

4.2.2 Community Structure

The structural characterization of communities, whether they are calculated on the basis of their density, biomass or substrate coverage, provides quantitative information (or at least semi-quantitative) complementing the previously described compositional description. This value which involves the relative contribution of species or groups to the sampled community, allows an estimation of their importance or predominance with

respect to other species or species groups present. This estimation allows for a closer analysis of population structures, that could (subject to project effects) allow for some proliferation or reduction in numbers without affecting overall species richness. In the example provided in Fig. 12 for Moorea, although the recovery rate of living corals was significantly reduced, species richness remained largely the same due to the persistence of some living communities (Kayal et al., 2012).

Figure 12 A coral reef in Moorea before and after the proliferation of *Acanthaster planci* between 2007 and 2009

As in the compositional description of populations, this analysis can focus specifically on outstanding species (or groups of species), chosen according to each of the study's objectives (fisheries potential, conservation issues, ecological role, etc.). This approach allows for a "finer-tuned" ecological interpretation than the compositional description of populations, mainly due to the range of analyses available to deal with quantitative ecological information. Nonetheless, it only assigns rare species a poor value in analyses as these species are generally low in abundance. It cannot therefore substitute for the descriptive approach of populations that gives equal attention to each species listed and can thus express the importance of an outstanding species, such as a keystone species, despite its poor representation in the overall population.

4.2.3 Function of biological processes

The functional analysis of ecosystems and biological processes is the final phase in the analysis of biocenoses. It is based on data acquired during the structural characterization of communities, granting each species or group of species (functional group), one or several functional ecological characteristics (feeding regime, demographic strategy, level of maturity, favourite habitat, etc.). These attributes must come from reliable and recognized sources, not always available on the taxa studied. The FishBase website for example (www.fishbase.org) provides scientifically validated

characteristics for the study of fish, allowing species identified in previous phases of the study to be checked against the database.

The analysis carried out of functional groups provides key information on possible interactions among organisms (predation, reproduction, etc.), on the demographic structure of populations (maturity, demographic strategies, size classes, reproduction, etc.) and on the primary features of habitats (nursery, growth, rest, concentration sites, etc.). Such information generally allows certain assumptions to be made on possible connections, whether continuous or fragmented, between habitats.

4.3 Study of abiotic environmental factors and ecological balances

If the functional analysis of populations provides information, on the trophic interactions between organisms (what eats what), the notion of the physical (abiotic) environment provides the elements that help us understand interactions between the organisms and their habitat (what lives where?). This physical structure of the ecosystem is the biotope that largely supports the distribution of the biocenoses. The study of this physical environment requires a multidisciplinary team, as there are a large number of environmental components. As in the case of the biotic factors study, this requires the implementation of often complex sampling and analytical methods. In this study four non exhaustive components are described: 1) climatic and land-based influences, 2) tides and hydrodynamics, 3) bathymetry and geology, and 4) physical chemistry of water and sediments.

4.3.1. Climatic and land-based influences

Hazardous weather conditions (cyclones, strong winds, etc.) and land-based inputs of continental or island origin (fresh water, terrigenous particles, pollutants, organic matter, etc.), often cause significant impacts on the marine environment. These can be either mechanic (sedimentation, levelling, etc.), chemical (nutrients, hydrocarbons, PCBs, etc.), or physico-chemical (temperature, pH, salinity, turbidity, etc.). Their influence is intensified in confined bodies of water or situated near shore and/or close to discharge points (estuaries, mouths of rivers, outfalls).

Due to their dependence on sunlight, scleractinian corals (i.e. reef builders) develop in shallow water (usually 0 to 40 m, sometimes as deep as 80 m), often close to the shore in complex geomorphological structures. Their low tolerance for nutrient enrichment, and variations in temperature, salinity and turbidity, limits their development to tropical coastal zones, away from chronic freshwater flows (permanent river systems, coastal resurgence areas, etc.). The confinement of coastal waters in reef zones in lagoon formations or depressions behind reefs (weak mixing of water masses) tends to accentuate vulnerability of coral populations to these hazards (Pinault et al., 2013). When a hydrographic system remains confined by a lagoon system this usually has a pass or a false pass, illustrating the intolerance of coral reefs to the chronic inflow of terrestrial discharges (Fig. 13).

When climatic and land-based influences do not allow for coral reef formation, other ecosystems often develop, which are generally characterized by biological communities more tolerant to variations in the water's physical chemistry (eurytherm, euryhaline, euriphotic organisms, etc.) and to chronic nutrient inputs (filtering, suspension feeders, scavengers, nitrophilous organisms, etc.). Their biotopes are largely shaped by erosion

events, and the transportation and deposition of materials (slabs, sedimentary plains, mudflats, deposits of alluvial pebbles, etc.). These ecosystems can however form significant structures (mangroves, seagrass beds, etc.) which perform ecological functions such as water purification, breeding and spawning areas, etc.).

Figure 13 Ermitage pass in La Réunion, flowing into the ravine of the same name, illustrates the intolerance of coral populations to the chronic inflow of fresh water (© V. Duvat)

Thus, in order to understand the structure of ecosystems one must at least know the location and if possible, the flow of the primary permanent river systems, the average annual monthly rainfall, frequency and the most likely route/trajectory of cyclonic events and coastal resurgence zones. Such information is generally provided by meteorological services, water authorities and scientific institutions and may also be acquired experimentally (plotters, flow sensors, anemometers, rain gauges, etc.). However, at the scale of an EIA, strong seasonal variability of measured parameters does not usually enable the acquisition of reliable temporal data series. All inflows of fresh water affect the salinity of seawater, creating an indicator which incorporates more and delicate hydrographic and meteorological parameters that require regular measurements.

One should also identify possible historical changes of these influencing factors (sea walls, building or diversion of water courses, waterproofing of soils, changes in the frequency of cyclonic events or temperature increases of water, etc.). Later in this guide, we will see that these characteristics strongly influence the underwater environment and particularly the terrestrial development of projects carried out for impact assessments.

4.3.1 Tidal range and hydrodynamism

The influence of tidal frequency and range on coastal ecosystems is primarily through: 1) the creation of currents; and 2) the submersion and immersion of intertidal zones (subtidal, intertidal and supratidal). Tidal currents in open sea are characterised by their change in direction depending on tidal cycles. They are generally oriented more or less parallel to the shore and can either contribute to or reduce normal flows. The rise and fall of water levels in confined lagoons also draws in currents while filling (rising or flood tide) and emptying (falling or ebb tide). These are often transversal to the coast, are generally drained by passes, lagoons or channels, and transport materials and

nutrients out to sea. These environments, exposed to potentially powerful currents, are often observation sites of large organisms possibly attracted to their ecological richness (sharks, jacks, barracudas, etc.), oxygenated waters or simply a flat, soft bottom allowing temporary visits from resting animals (rays, turtles, marine mammals, etc.) (Fig. 14).

Figure 14 Hammerhead shark in the Tiputa pass, Rangiroa (© C. Albano)

Timetables and tidal ranges can generally easily be checked with military marine organisations such as the Navy/Coast Guard as well as Meteorological Offices, Ports etc. and can also be measured experimentally with sea floor mounted sensors that continuously monitor water pressure and from which water depth can be calculated.

General currentology depends to a large degree on climate conditions found regionally, notably prevailing winds and coastal geomorphology of the territory under analysis. Generally, currents are generated at sea by the action of winds on vast ocean surfaces (the fetch), as well as by density differences in huge masses of oceanic waters (thermohaline circulation). If the components of these currents (speed, direction, course) are generally known at sea, their action closer to shore is usually easier to predict (Piton et Taquet, 1992). In addition, association with local currents, generated by different surfaces, makes the prevision of displacements of masses of surface water all the more difficult. Thus, the analysis of this environmental component which is crucial for the determination of potential impacts on ecosystems within the study area (dilution of substances, energy dissipation, dispersion of plumes, etc.) and also to understand the numerous biological and ecological processes (larval recruitment areas, ecological corridors, migratory routes, etc.), often calls for the implementation of complex hydrodynamic modelling, usually undertaken by specialist service providers. They can nonetheless be estimated temporarily and locally by different experimental devices such as the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) or the Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter (ADV) (Fig. 15) or more simply with floating drogues (Fig. 16).

Figure 15 Submersion of a current metre type Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) (© J. Wickel)

Figure 16 Different types of floating drogues

Like currents, swells are primarily generated by the action of wind on vast ocean surfaces, however they are spread in the open sea in a wave-like manner over long distances (without a net transport of matter) and can be identified by periodic and successive rises and falls in the ocean surface. These characteristics of swells give them a different type of kinetic energy than that of currents. Even though their origin is often identical, their direction and intensity near the coast can be quite different. They are referred to as swell regimes when their origin changes according to the season (trade, monsoon), or specific meteorological phenomena (cyclones, storms from the north or the south). On approaching the coast the lines of crests (wave front) of the swell tend to line up in parallel with depth contours and the curvature on the surface increases (breaking of waves), causing turbulent, elliptical currents near the bottom and laminar currents near the coast, parallel to the shore (littoral drift). These elliptical, or "orbital" currents, can cause a re-organization of surface sediments (destabilization) and transport (erosion, abrasion, accretion). Swells can be very strong, particularly during cyclonic events, and can be felt at a depth equivalent to half the wavelength of the swell (Biesel, 1949). The action of the swell on the coast can also be modified via refraction in the presence of a raised bottom, such as caused by an artificial reef, mooring, wreck, etc. (Fig. 17).

Figure 17 Influence of depth contours in propagating the swell

The study of swells and orbital currents near the sea bottom requires a knowledge of the physical characteristics of the swell (period, height, wavelength, direction). These values can be generated by different mathematical models, some of which are accessible on specialized sites (www.windguru.cz, www.previmer.org, www.meteolamer.re, data.shom.fr). They can be provided experimentally using heave buoys or ADCPs equipped with a module to measure the swell. The underwater observation of ripple marks parallel to the shore, formed in the sediment through the action of orbital currents, will also provide information to site operators on swells' direction, and intensity (depending on direction, height and length of furrows) (Fig. 18).

Figure 18 Ripple marks in the sediment parallel to shore formed by the action of orbital swell currents (© M. Pinault)

Bathymetry is the most direct and objective measure of submarine morpho-sedimentary characteristics. It has a particularly strong influence on: 1) the pressure, relating to the

height of the water column vertically above the point examined (1 bar every 10 m + 1 bar of atmospheric pressure); 2) and variables reducing light and often hydrodynamic energy; and 3) topographic characteristics of the seabed with plains, canyons, faults, cliffs and other falloffs. It can also delimit water masses showing different temperatures (thermoclines) or salinities (haloclines). From the cartographic point of view, the bathymetry provides the 3-D vertical geometric component within the study area. If this function alone is insufficient to identify outstanding habitats and environments, it does provide crucial information on the distribution of biological communities, notably on the layering of populations with reference to their depth (Pinault, 2013). The falloff zones and vertical cliffs favour the presence of suspension feeders and planktivores, while canyon areas might serve as axes for the movement of migratory populations between habitats (corridors, passageways). Finally, the increased pressure at depth will limit the progression of certain organisms, notably air breathers (mammals, reptiles and sea birds). The acquisition of precise bathymetric data of study areas usually requires the purchase of certified marine maps. These data are completed locally by geo-referenced digital terrain models (side imaging, multibeam sonar, Light Detection and Ranging [LIDAR], etc.), of variable levels of precision, sometimes available from government departments or public bodies, or from private contractors. The bathymetry can also be registered with a depth sounder on board a vessel or by hand, and possibly using a line or a graduated pole.

The nature and geological origin of the seabed (coral sand, volcanic rock, estuary mudflats, etc.), once associated with the bathymetric grid, is what is referred to as geomorphology. This is the primary component of the physical habitat or biotope, the organisms (lodge, niche) and might be characterised by certain numeric variables such as the grain size of sediments, the height of surface irregularities, the depth of crevasses or the roughness of hard substrates. These variables contribute to the relationship species have with their habitat and partially conditions their distribution within a study area. Thus an external reef slope will have benthic communities (notably coral populations) different from a volcanic rock dropoff; a sedimentary lagoon zone will shelter fish populations different from those on a sand-accumulating plain at the bottom of a bay, etc. The geological and geomorphological nature of coral reef seabeds is not always accurately known, particularly in shallow areas (0-20 m) where side-scan sonar does not work well (Fig. 19). Under such conditions a description of the geology and geomorphology by divers can be contemplated. It is generally carried out either with the divers' own efforts or via a towed vehicle (boat, scooter) for long distances (manta tow). These surveys can be carried out in parallel with the semi-quantitative analysis of populations, described in the chapter on the structural characterization of communities. Airborne data capture techniques are also possible, using LIDAR remote sensing or hyperspectral imagery.

Figure 19 Working principle of geological and geomorphological cartography at sea (source IFREMER)

4.3.3. Physical chemistry of water and sediments

The description of abiotic factors of the environment would not be complete without the physico-chemical characterisation of water masses and sediments. Although these characteristics are not related to clearly defined geographic elements (movement of water masses, complex hydrosedimentary mechanisms) they are the most directly measurable indicators of external disturbances and, particularly, of the effect of a project on the environment. However, their poor capacity to integrate historical changes in the environment, renders these monitoring indicators erratic and at times, unsuitable for reliable interpretation. They represent a snapshot of environmental conditions only at the time of intervention by on-site operators and do not represent a stable and constant state of these conditions. These parameters are highly dependent on climatic and geological variations and different uses of the water catchment area.

Measuring contaminants in organisms (bioindicators) and passive samplers (Diffusive Gradient in Thin Film [DGT], Polar Organic Chemical Integrative Sampler [POCIS], Stir-bar Sorptive Extraction [SBSE]) can be used to handle such limitations. These methods can detect disturbances over much longer periods and are thus more sensitive to the accumulation of trace elements (Fig. 20). However, the cost of their implementation and analysis is much higher than previously described for hydrological measures and can therefore act as limiting factor.

Figure 20 Deployment of passive samplers (DGT and SBSE) along a line by a scientific diver (© J. Wickel)

The physico-chemical analysis of water masses provides a wide array of environmental indicators likely to provide information both on general and specific characteristics observed in the study area. Some indicators will provide information on the inflow of fresh water (salinity, conductivity, pH, temperature, level of dissolved silica, etc.) while others will highlight possible eutrophic origins (nitrates, nitrites, ammonium, phosphates, etc.) or different types of pollution (petrochemicals, organic matter, etc.). Indicators can also provide information on primary production or the bacterial load of water masses (chlorophyll a, pheopigments, coliforms, enterococci, etc.) and will thus contribute information on biological activity at the base of many food webs (filtering organisms, phytoplankton eaters, etc.) as well as sources of biological contaminants (animal diseases).

A variety of methods can be used to determine the different indicators mentioned above and they should be carried out by laboratories certified for conducting analyses in oligotrophic environments (very low level detection limits). Regarding the methods of hydrological sampling and analysis in the marine environment, good practices can be found in the work of Alain Aminot and Roger Krouel (2004) of the French Research Institute for Marine Research (IFREMER). Since 2010 these are complemented by videos which are very useful for operators as they provide filmed sequences detailing the series of operations and precautions to be respected on site. Interpretation of results must take into consideration other variables which could have an impact such as, season, hydrodynamism, agricultural, industrial and domestic activities, etc.). Consideration of these variables will allow for a determination of whether the measures were carried out over a period of normal conditions or extreme conditions whether less than (dry season, major renewal of water masses, reduced agricultural, industrial and domestic activities) or more than (wet season, confinement of water masses, intense agricultural, industrial and domestic activity). Finally, some gradients (entire coast, north – south, east – west, depth) and some correlations (silica – nitrates, nitrates – phosphates, etc.) can also assist with determining the different sources of the measured parameters

We saw in the previous chapter that sediments can be resuspended in shallow water, exposed to swell events (influence of orbital currents). This frequent reorganization results in the extraction of the majority of fine particles from the sediment, their re-

suspension and subsequent transportation by coastal currents (general currents, swell currents). A strong relationship also exists between sediment levels in pollutants (organic matter, hydrocarbons, trace metal elements, etc.) and the grain size of superficial/surface sediments; fine sediments (< 63 µm) containing higher concentrations of pollutant substances than coarser sediments. The grain size thus contributes to the quality of superficial/surface aquatic sediments by sequestration of pollutant compounds in the finest quantities. A fixation gradient of pollutant compounds thus appears with the level of fine particles contained in the analysed sediment and therefore with the local depth and hydrodynamism. However, most project impacts are found in shallow, exposed coastal areas, which are predominantly comprised of coarse sediments with little possibility of sequestering pollutant compounds. As a result, it is difficult to measure some pollutants in sediments collected from such areas. A further factor limiting sediment analysis occurs with regularly dredged harbour sediments and the time elapsed since the previous dredging event, should therefore be considered in the interpretation of data (Fig. 21).

Figure 21 Diver collecting harbour sediments (© M. Pianult)

4.4 Study of landscape factors and habitat connectivity

4.4.1 Marine landscape

Landscape is the layout of traits, character and forms of a limited space. It is represented or viewed horizontally as well as vertically and may have a strong aesthetic element. It can also reflect land use planning policies. In ecology, the landscape can be defined as the study of spatial variations at different scales (including biophysical and social) and the consequences of landscape ecology, making this an interdisciplinary branch of the sciences.

According to the International Association for Landscape Ecology (IALE), the primary study areas of landscape ecology are: 1) the spatial pattern or structure of landscapes, ranging from wilderness to cities; 2) the relationship between pattern and process in landscapes; 3) the relationship of human activity to landscape pattern, process and change; and 4) the effect of scale and disturbance on the landscape. These studies are based on a knowledge of the spatio-temporal heterogeneity of the given area. They include elements of landscape patchiness, seasons, evolutionary alternations and traits.

The consideration of landscaping aspects of a development project is essential when carrying out an EIA. In France, Communities' Local Development Plans [PLU under the French acronym] must specifically consider the landscape and laws such as the Landscape Law ("*loi Paysage*") which allows for the protection of the landscape. Thus, the majority of development projects, like management plans for natural areas, involve a landscape analysis at the outset. The European Landscape Convention calls for countries of the European Union to inventory their landscapes out of concern for their development, management or preservation. In France this inventory is carried out in the form of a landscape atlas at departmental or regional levels, that includes a marine element in overseas territories. Overall, the inventory of marine landscapes is still at an embryonic⁴⁰ stage and the motivation behind many multidisciplinary studies.

4.4.2 Habitat Connectivity

As occurs in terrestrial ecology (Forman, 2000), the marine environment is also seriously affected by the partial or total destruction of its habitats, resulting in ecosystem fragmentation.⁴¹ In a continuous ecosystem there is free movement of organisms between habitats. However, if the ecosystem becomes fragmented, due to physical barriers or habitat, corridors linking essential habitats can be destroyed or impeded⁴² (Fig. 22). As these habitats are now less favourable for survival, high mortality can result, leading to barriers to connectivity (Garcia, 2012). Habitat changes, destruction and fragmentation are the primary causes of species and biodiversity loss (Viederman et al., 1997).

40 The French Agency for Protected Marine Areas (AAMP) published (Springer) the proceedings of a colloquium on this subject (Musard et al., 2014).

41 The fragmentation is the action, of natural or anthropogenic origin, by which phenomena fraction habitats that were intact in their initial state (Rameau et al., 2000).

42 A habitat is considered essential for a species when it possesses characteristics that are indispensable for its development during a given stage of its life. Many mobile species have life cycles marked by distinct phases and during which they occupy different habitats (spawning, nurseries, feeding, etc.) Each of these specific life stages partly determines the renewal of affected populations that require different conditions as far as habitats are concerned (Ramade, 2002).

Figure 22 Movements between essential habitats of fish: a) continuous ecosystem; b) fragmented ecosystem (according to Garcia, 2012)

Development can impact on the ecological connectivity of sites in the following ways: habitat fragmentation (sea walls and spills at port facilities fragmenting banks of natural debris along the coast) the obstruction of ecological corridors (channels or outfalls perpendicular to the path of organisms) and the destruction or degradation of essential habitat (sea wall or coastal route in nursery areas). The impacts on organisms in the medium to long terms can encompass; progressive reductions in population size, redistribution of depleted populations, population structure characterised by regressive ecological successions and the dominance of opportunistic species which could result in the disappearance of some species.

Connectivity in the marine environment cannot be addressed in the same way as on land. It must consider elements specific to this environment in three dimensions (Kool et al., 2013). Experimental observations of ecological corridors (location, functionality), and an estimation of the permeability of these connections (flux) are extremely difficult, even hazardous, without the implementation of cumbersome and expensive sampling protocols (catch-tagging-re-catch, acoustic telemetry, isotopic and genetic population analyses, etc.) that are often disproportionate when considering the size of projects subject to EIAs. At this level of analysis, collaboration between teams in charge of the study, local research laboratories and managing bodies of natural areas can prove to be beneficial. However, research procedures, financial arrangements, mobilization of human resources and in some cases, the execution of degrees by research laboratories can be longer than the intervention times of teams in charge of the EIA. It is thus necessary, particularly when examining the files of large development projects or within

a large industrial area commonly involved in impact studies, to anticipate requirements of functionality and landscape analyses and initiate research in the medium term, well before the start of operations. Corporate reports (e.g. Industrial Agreements for Training through Research [CIFRE under its French acronym]) can also be envisaged.

4.5 Study of human factors within the environment and ecosystem services

EIAs involve the study of human factors and ecosystem services which represent the interface between ecological balances and the society's interests, in terms of usage, resource consumption, safety and public and environmental health. In other words, if the preceding phases of the assessment provide a biocentric focus on environmental conservation, this phase gives a more anthropocentric approach towards environmental conservation, in which the natural environment acquires an instrumental value (Dietz et al., 2005). This approach thus has a more exploitative and managerial objective rather than environmental conservation (Fig. 23).

Figure 23 Octopus production in the Mayotte lagoon (© J. Wickel)

This anthropocentric approach does not exclude actions contributing to biodiversity conservation and so is complementary with the biocentric approach. This complementarity forms the basis of the ecosystem services (ES) concept, that appears both as a tool for the quantification of economic and social benefits provided by the ecosystems and the enjoyment of benefits provided by the environment in the absence

of human intervention; human action (or deliberate inaction) therefore serves as leverage in the provision of ecosystem services (Aznar et al., 2009).

4.5.1 Public hygiene, health and sanitation

The expression environmental health looks at relationships between environmental variables (biogeographic factors, bacterial and microalgal communities, etc.) and health, hygiene and sanitation, as well as their monitoring. It is recognized that human action, through its effect on the environment, can have major consequences on public health. This negative feedback between human activity, environmental impact and the degradation of living conditions was ignored for a long time by development projects. However, numerous studies, mainly carried out over the last twenty years, confirm cause and effect relations between certain environmental disruptions of anthropomorphic origin (coral mortality, diseases, degradation of water quality, etc.) and phenomena affecting public health (proliferation of toxic micro-algae, staphylococcal infections, bio-accumulation in fish, etc.). It is thus important to evaluate this risk for any EIA (Fig. 24).

Figure 24 Mass mortalities of reef fish in March 2014 on the west coast of Reunion attributed to disease (© IPR)

The difficulty of identifying the public health, hygiene and sanitation-related risks associated with a project depends greatly on the complexity of transmission mechanisms between the effect of the project and its repercussions on the quality of human life. Thus, some direct effects, such as the risk of intoxication or pollution through contact with or ingestion of polluted water, can be easily detected. However, indirect effects, amplified or transmitted by complex ecological mechanisms (bioaccumulation, bioamplification, feedback, etc.), will require a thorough understanding of these and their operational dynamics. For example, the coral mortality caused by project effluents could enable the development of benthic dinoflagellates of the *Gambierdiscus toxicus* species. The toxin produced by this microalgae, responsible for the neuro-digestive symptom known as "ciguatera", can then be stored by primary consumers on the reef, and subsequently transmitted and concentrated along the food

chain reaching dangerous threshold levels for humans in some carnivorous fish (jackfish, barracudas, groupers, etc.) (Hocdé, 2009). Thus, a hot-water discharge in a coral area could indirectly increase the risk of neuro-digestive symptoms in populations regularly consuming products of local artisanal fishers. The concentration phenomena of certain compounds within organisms (bioaccumulation) along the food chain (bioamplification) also involves numerous toxic products, generally presenting a high affinity with living matter and high persistence (trace metals, PCBs, TBT, etc.) (Caumette et al., 2012).

An estimation of the intensity of risks to public health and hygiene linked to a project also depends on the complexity of transmission mechanisms. For example, the risk of direct contamination, through contact with or ingestion of sea water could be estimated by identifying the types of bacteria identified, their densities in project effluents, the purifying property of sea water (T90: time required for 90% of bacteria to be destroyed), current patterns, bathing activities, etc. The risk could also be controlled experimentally during operational phases with regular testing of sea water in bathing areas involving quality analyses. The estimation of indirect impacts is more sensitive as it involves numerous factors, notably of a socio-cultural nature. In the case of ciguatera, that has been particularly well researched, and depends for example on previous references to the regional risk of acquiring symptoms, the consumption frequency of fishery products and the consumption chain of species at risk (subsistence, commercial), etc. This estimation is often imprecise but can nonetheless allow for the prioritization of indirect risks and identification of the most serious. Monitoring through testing of organisms potentially at risk and a tissue analysis of the level of toxic substances could also be implemented in the case of proven risk.

4.5.2 Conflicts of use and maritime safety

There is often conflict between traditional and project activities within the study area, most notably when they are linked to boating (whether traditional or professional). So, for example a project which seeks to prohibit access to a strategic fishing area, runs the risk of antagonising fishers as well as groups of other stakeholders (unions, collectives, associations, etc.) and mobilising them to halt development of the project, unless consensus was previously reached on the matter of compensation. Foreseeing conflict will enable the choice of concessions in areas of less strategic or ecological interest, and thus limit the scope of compensation and risks of appeals (see claims for damages). Likewise an under-sea discharge which damages the landscape of a popular diving site could result in the loss of considerable ecotourism potential for many years. The anticipation of these conflicts thus depends on a spatial-temporal analysis of practices within and near the study area and calls for a show of interest in different stakeholders and current power relationships. Planning documents, atlases and master plans can serve as good reference material, but a site analysis (surveys, censuses, observations) will often be necessary for the identification of possible informal uses. The collaboration of managers of natural areas would be important in the identification of local stakeholders and issues affecting the area.

Regarding safety associated with navigation, maritime authorities oblige developers to respect closed areas, particularly sheltered anchorage areas in the case of severe weather, navigation channels and turning zones. For example, the laying of cables cannot be considered in anchorage areas. Likewise, the height of artificial reefs should

not impede the navigation of any vessel in the area. A minimum clearance of 15 metres above the artificial reef is suggested (Stroud et Massmann, 1966; Moseley, 1974; Bragoni, 1980) or, the highest part of the artificial reef is to be lower than the highest natural relief in the area (Darovec et al., 1975). Although these areas reserved for navigation are referenced and regulated, authorities are not always aware of their existence and specific research through competent state authorities would be highly recommended in the early planning of the EIA.

4.5.3 Ecosystem services provided by coral reefs

This section is based on work carried out by the French coral reef initiative [IFRECOR under its French acronym] on the evaluation of Ecosystem services (ES) between 2010 and 2015. A summary report was prepared (Pascal et al., 2016a). For the purpose of this work, we adhere to the following definition of ESs, these being "the services that human populations derive directly or indirectly from ecosystem functions" (Costanza et al., 1997). Several classifications of ESs are proposed (e.g. Beukering et al., 2007; De Groot et al., 2002) and a classification in the form of value types generated is used.

A distinction is made between "**use values** that include the benefits to the agent: 1) from the consumption of assets, and 2) from practices linked to assets but which do not result in their consumption" and in "**non-use values** that create benefits to others, as long as the use to the agent involves ethical or altruistic preferences" (Chevassus-au-Louis et al., 2009). The set of use values, that are sometimes identified as option values (future use values), and non-use comprise the total economic value⁴³ of services provided by coral reefs (Fig. 25).

Figure 25 The values of ecosystem services (based on the Centre d'Analyse Stratégique (CAS) diagram)

Use values include services resulting from direct use, with and without resource extraction, direct and induced use.

Direct use values relating to activities in which the individual may benefit directly from the resource, by consuming it (e.g. fishing), are referred to direct extractive uses, while benefitting from its presence but not consuming it (e.g. underwater tourism), are referred to as non-extractive uses. They can also be of a commercial nature, if the use involves a market that defines its price (e.g. fish or a tourist service), or non-commercial (e.g. subsistence fishing or underwater tours).

Indirect use values include those ESs that do not involve human intervention (Defra, 2008). For example, coral reefs can provide physical protection against swells or mangroves can contribute to the treatment of wastewater.

Induced use values correspond to uses that incorporate ecosystem processes as production factors for commercial services, such as water, nutrients, etc. Two examples are aquaculture and pearl culture.⁴⁴

Option values refer to future (direct, indirect or induced) uses in which the value of potential of identified, but as yet undeveloped, is evaluated.

Non-use values, also referred to as passive use values (Carson et al., 1992; Carson et al., 1999), involve a series of economic values not linked to use of the natural environment.

⁴³ The notion of total economic value, or TEV, does not represent the total economic value of all the environment, but the series of reasons why human beings might be associated with the environment because of the wellbeing it provides (Chevassus-au-Louis et al., 2009). Attributing a monetary value to coral reefs allows ecology to be integrated in the economic sphere and decision-makers to be addressed using a concrete and tangible language (David et al., 1999).

⁴⁴ In the case of projects based on uses induced by the site (wave-generating stations, fish farm, etc.) the natural processes concerned will be analysed during feasibility studies. The EIA must ensure the maintenance of these processes so as to ensure the project's sustainability.

It is not uncommon to find non-use values in the form of a single aggregate, in which the name differs according to the objective of the economic evaluation of which they are a part. In this case, the non-use value of an environmental resource is sometimes referred to as "altruistic value" (Christie et al., 2004), "bequest value" or "conservation value" (Point, 1998). Nonetheless non-use values often include several composite values according to the type of motivation of the target population. The most commonly mentioned are existence value and bequest value.

Existence value corresponds to the value given to the mere existence of coral reefs (Krutilla et Fisher, 1975).

Bequest value is associated with the preservation of coral reefs for future generations (Pearce et Moran, 1994).

Despite this diversity of services, the majority of social and economic benefits produced by coral reefs and associated ecosystems are provided by the four following ESs (Laurans et al., 2013 ; Moberg, 1999) :

- Services producing edible biomass (commercial, artisanal and recreational fishing),
- Services producing species of high-profile and offering scenic beauty (for underwater and nature tourism),
- Services protecting against erosion and coastal flooding through the partial absorption of swell energy,
- Carbon sequestration services, particularly by seagrass beds and mangroves.

Within the framework of the EIA, the issue is to quickly estimate: 1) the losses potentially caused by the project under study on the main ESs (residual impacts), but also 2) the pressure already exerted by their existence on natural environments and their capacity to withstand additional pressure (notion of ecosystem carrying capacity⁴⁵ and cumulative impacts), and 3) to ensure equivalence between the impacted site and the compensated site with regard to services provided (compensation).

As previously stated, the EIA focuses on the appraisal of in-kind environmental impacts of a project, which means that residual impacts of a given project cannot be appraised and then compensated in monetary terms. The use and non-use values affected by the project should thus be replaced through the restoration of the ecological processes on

⁴⁵ The carrying capacity of ecosystems can be defined as being the threshold beyond which an environmental good or service starts to decline and can no longer contribute to the wellbeing of populations. Beyond this threshold, deterioration caused by ecosystems will prevent certain population groups and future generations from meeting their needs. In the case of seaside tourism, for example, this carrying capacity corresponds to the number of visitors the reef ecosystem can support without suffering irreparable damage (Wielgus et al., 2002).

Regarding fisheries, the concept of renewable resource implies reference to a maximum catch that is sustainable, known as maximum sustainable yield (MSY). The theory is that this yield corresponds to catches and fishing practices that would be considered stable over time as they would not affect the natural renewal rate of the resource (Armada et al., 2009; Dalzell and Adams, 1997).

In the case of services provided to protect against swell, water purification mechanisms and carbon dioxide sequestration, the carrying capacities will come from production functions that take into consideration different ecological variables that have a bearing on the result (health status of coral reefs and associated ecosystems, swell energy absorption capacity, quantity of inputs, etc.).

In any case, it is a question of clearly showing (and directly in parallel with presented values) an indicator that enables analysis of the issue of sustainability of the specific use.

which they depend. This functional approach⁴⁶ involves a thorough knowledge of production mechanisms, resistance (extraction capacity), and resilience (regeneration capacity) of these natural processes so the services on which they depend are permanently safeguarded.

In order to understand the existing links between services and ecosystems (influence of ecosystems on services and vice versa), the identification of basic processes and beneficiaries defined by Balmford et al. (2008) is recommended (Fig. 26). These processes can be exclusive or can contribute to the provision of a service under consideration. The basic processes, such as biochemical or water cycles, are those that support beneficiary processes (such as biomass production or water purification) that are themselves the direct source of ecosystem services.

Figure 26 Non-exhaustive example of basic processes and beneficiary processes associated with ecosystem services provided by coral reefs (according to Moberg & Folke, 1999; MEA, 2005; Balmford et al., 2008; Pascal et al., 2016b)

The value estimation of services provided by coral reefs must also consider the spatial heterogeneity of the study area. In fact, if the majority of estimated values can be applied to the reef as a whole, their relative importance will be greatly influenced by characteristics such as resource production (fish, molluscs, crustaceans, etc.), access (road, parking, depth, etc.), safety (monitoring station, protections from sharks, etc.), distance (to the coast, to a port, etc.) and the conservation status of the area under study (virgin or degraded), but also traditions (fishing and other traditional practices) or scenic beauty (colours and landscapes) that are the characteristics linked to the socioeconomic context. These spatial units comprise a patchwork of territories and are sometimes referred to as space-resources (David et al., 1999).

⁴⁶ This functional approach is also valid for impacts on public hygiene, health and sanitation, especially through the preservation of natural mechanisms (self-purification, coral reef vitality, water filtering) that if degraded could result in risks to users (infections, illnesses, intoxications, smells, etc.).

Table 3 Example of inventory of actors, use and non-use values by the space-resource of a coral reef (David et al., 2007)

Spaces – resources	Actors	Direct use value	Indirect and induced use	Option value	Non-use value
Beaches	Local boaters and tourists Beach and nautical sports clubs Hotel and restaurant owners	Seaside activities Beach-tennis, volley ball, surf, sailing, speed-sail, etc. Collection of shells and shellfish	Filtration of groundwater Nesting (turtles, sea birds)	Future exploitation of filtering potential of sand Development of new sports	Landscape Educational and scientific interest Wellbeing and symbol of holidays
Sandy-silty tidal flats	Artisanal or informal fishers Local boaters and tourists	Fishing with nets and lines, etc. Collection of shells and shellfish	Self-purificating water (mangroves) Carbon sequestration (seagrass, mangroves) Nursery (fish, turtles, shellfish, etc.)	Future exploitation of mangroves' potential for self-purification Development of post-larval capture and culture (PCC)	Educational and scientific interest
Lagoon or large boat channel	Artisanal or informal fishers Local boaters and tourists Fish farmers Underwater tourist guides	Fishing with nets, lines, cages, etc. Berths, mooring Fish farming (algae, molluscs, holothurians, etc.) Visits to underwater nature trails	Nursery (fish, coral, etc.) Carbon sequestration (seagrass) Tidal energy Nutrients and microorganisms Area protected from swell	Future exploitation of tidal energy Development of post-larval capture and culture (PCC) Establishment of coral farms (cuttings)	Landscape Biodiversity reservoir Educational and scientific interest
Coral pinnacle	Artisanal or informal fishers Local boaters and tourists Aquatic sports clubs	Fishing with nets, lines, cages, etc. Underwater diving, snorkelling, hunting, etc.	Oasis effect within lagoon sand-mud plains Reproduction and assembling (fish, marine mammals, etc.)	Underwater tourism and research projects	Landscape Biodiversity reservoir Educational and scientific interest
Internal reef wall	Artisanal or informal fishers Local boaters and tourists Aquatic sports clubs	Fishing with nets, lines, cages, etc. Underwater diving, snorkelling, hunting, etc.	Nursery (reef fish) Reproduction (rays, sharks, etc.)	Underwater tourism and research projects	Landscape Biodiversity reservoir Educational and scientific interest
External plateau	Artisanal or informal fishers Local boaters and tourists Providers of transport at sea	Fishing with nets, lines, cages, etc. Glass-bottomed boat trips	Tidal energy Protection against beach erosion	Future exploitation of tidal energy	Landscape Biodiversity reservoir Educational and scientific interest
Caye or coral islet	Local boaters and tourists	Seaside activities Tourist	Reproduction and aggregation sites	Underwater tourism and	Landscape Biodiversity

	Hotel and restaurant owners Aquatic sports clubs	accommodation Underwater diving, snorkelling, hunting, etc.	Nesting sites (turtles, seabirds)	research projects	reservoir Educational and scientific interest
External reef wall	Artisanal or informal fishers Local boaters and tourists Aquatic sports clubs	Fishing with nets, lines, cages, etc. Underwater diving, snorkelling, hunting, etc.	Tidal energy Protection against beach erosion	Future exploitation of tidal energy Underwater tourism and research projects	Landscape Biodiversity reservoir Educational and scientific interest

The space-resource concept associates a single spatial entity and the resources within it as an object of management and use. Between six and 12 are identified according to the literature and the complexity of reef-lagoon formations studied and broadly corresponding to the reef's large morpho-functional units (Table 3).

The evaluation of a project's residual impacts on human factors and ESs can thus be carried out indirectly (via habitats) and does not require the conversion of services to monetary values.⁴⁷

4.6 Methods, sampling strategies and data analysis

The assumptions made during the assessment of the project's potential impacts on the environment are provisional only, involving the linking of variables (coral cover, nitrate concentration of water, visits to beaches, etc.) and space-time behaviour (control site vs. impacted site, and site before and after project implementation). The sampling protocol is based on the previously made assumptions (Giraudoux, 2004) and must be linked to EIA objectives. Its success depends as well on a sensible sampling plan and data analysis. Many procedures are possible, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. The discussion of possible methods and determination of informed choices is therefore a strategic element, essential in a descriptive scientific process, particularly in the case of an EIA. In addition, in light of the often budgetary limitations regarding personnel and time available for the EIA, the most effective measures coupled with an appropriate sampling effort need to be taken. Many authors have discussed data requirements for EIAs relative to different objectives (Facon et al., 2016). The evaluation objectives determine the type of scientific follow-up required, its characteristics (level of precision, replication effort, analytical capacity, etc.) and the scientific disciplines to be involved in such a study.

⁴⁷ The precise quantification of monetary damage of residual impacts, corresponds to commercial damage suffered by the private sector (e.g. the loss of revenue from fishing or tourism before the compensated site becomes productive), and is not the aim of the EIA. It should be subject to a claim for damages together with or without the involvement of the prefect for the compensation process. This is one of the rare exceptions of monetary (not in kind) payment by the project manager. This procedure is not detailed in this Guide.

Of the three fundamental objectives analysed in the chapter on the EIA conceptual framework, the goal of designing the project with the least impact is that which would determine the methods, sampling plan and analyses carried out. It can be achieved through four specific steps involving: 1) a summary of the characteristics and behaviour of the biological, physical, landscape and human environments at the scale of the study area, 2) the identification of indicator variables of disturbances, adapted to project effects, as well as the sites and periods of high sensitivity, 3) the proposal of prevention measures as well as those aimed at reducing the project's environmental impact and 4) the choice of monitoring sites for each indicator. Each of these specific steps is based on a conceptual data analysis diagram (Fig. 27).

Figure 27 Diagram of decision-making process terminating in the choice of a sampling plan (according to Giraudoux, 2004)

There are therefore four approaches based on a progression, requiring increased sampling and data analysis efforts: 1) a descriptive approach enabling an immediate snapshot (initial status and previous tendencies) of several characteristics of the study area that does not require complex data collection methods or statistical analyses; 2) an

analytical approach focusing on those variables the behaviour of which is likely to be impacted by the project; 3) a comparative approach of variables measured on the impacted and control sites, before and after works having been carried out, requiring analyses including comparisons both in space and in time; and finally 4) in the case of analyses aimed at establishing relations between different processes or making predictions, an inclusive approach calling for more advanced research and data analysis (exploration of causal links).

4.7 Large-scale study: general characterisation of study

The general characterization of the study area takes place during the analysis of initial status, that follows the initial scoping exercise, and involves completing/updating of missing/dated information. The requirements for successful implementation, include the number, quality and availability of previous studies carried out in the study area as well as: the area covered, whether the project is concentrated or linear, and the sensitivity of environment components. This initial approach, that stresses the importance of a cartographic analysis, is not aimed at providing a baseline for the analysis of space-time monitoring (comparative approach), but rather to provide information for the identification of indicators of possible environmental disturbances, as well as the areas and periods of maximum impact to be targeted by priority conservation measures.

The methods carried out involve a summary of the primary components of the natural, human and landscaped environments and the identification of homogenous spatial and possible temporal (seasons) units likely to be identified as management units. These methods can involve a Rapid Assessment Process (RAP) that can be easily carried out at a reasonable cost, of a relatively high number of factors over wide areas (large-scale focus).

Acquiring information from underwater environments can be carried out using underwater visual census (UVC)⁴⁸ methods but might also involve videos from various vessels such as manned submersibles and remote operated vehicles [ROV], glass-bottomed boats or even tourist divers. Apart from underwater observation, data may be acquired using active (sonar) or passive (hydrophone) acoustic devices, by remote sensing (LIDAR, hyperspectral, etc.), manual or bucket, etc. The underwater sampling component can be complemented via ground truthing, (multiple-choice questionnaires) or interviews of users (local boaters, fishers, divers, swimmers, etc.), institutions or management bodies with a regular presence in the study area.

In order to establish the relative importance of certain indicators (recovery rate of substrate by benthic organisms, relative density of certain organisms, etc.) semi-quantitative metrics⁴⁹ (value intervals) (Fig 28) or scales of ordinal measures (single,

48 These methods require both few *in situ* research tools (slate, submersible camera or video camera) and allow, over the course of the sampling, a location in time and space of measures carried out on a large scale (GPS tracking, spatial locat sonar, watch). However, a means of transport, that could be fins in the case of radial cross-section observations on the shore, or a motorized vehicle (boat, underwater scooter) may be necessary when long distances are involved (manta tow – Miller et Müller, 1999). A means of communication with the surface (surface console and transmitter-receiver face masks) frees site operators from having to use bulky equipment for note taking.

49 Metrics required must enable an immediate approximation of the relative dominance of species or groups of species studied, and facilitate the ease of movement of the site operators. These usually involve a graphic representation for visual calibration that can be printed on an underwater slate. Dahl's categories (1981), for example, allow an approximation of the percent cover of benthic organisms. Gratwicke et Speight's (2005) Habitat Assessment Score (HAS) enables a rapid appraisal of the structural complexity of habitats.

few, medium, abundant) (Table 4) can be used. The scales of ordinal measures must however be complemented by a description of each level.

Figure 28 Semi-quantitative metrics of visual census of coastal habitats available on the back of an underwater slate (according to Pinault et al., 2013)

Table 4 Ordinal scale for the semi-quantitative valuation of fish density, clarified with the description of each of the levels and carried out over a given period of time, in this case 15 minutes (according to Schmitt et al. 2002)

Ordinal scale	Description of levels
S : Single	[1] a single individual
F : Few	[2-10] a few scattered individuals
M : Many	[11-100] many individuals
A : Abundant] >100] Dominant/abundant species

Data acquired is then analysed cartographically (biocenoses, geomorphology, uses, etc.) and descriptively (outstanding species and landscapes, the most abundant ecological facies and organisms, frequency of observed phenomena, identified uses and habits, etc.). This enables assumptions to be made on the functionality of habitats (nursery, feeding, reproduction, etc.) and the interconnectivity between environments (ecological corridors, migratory paths, etc.).

4.7.1 Case of a concentrated project:

In the case of concentrated projects, the sampled surface should cover the entire study area, so, both the sectors directly influenced by works and operations, and distant areas influenced by indirect effects. The sampling plan can vary from case to case, and may

involve random routes or a more or less regular grid system within the study area (radial cross sections) and can be carried out on foot, with fins or by being towed by a vessel. It can also introduce an exploration of decreasing effort, particularly relating to extensive distances from possible sites (Fig. 29).

Figure 29 Example of large-scale characterization of management units and radial sampling within the study area of a concentrated project (Sainte-Rose wastewater treatment plant – La Réunion)

4.7.2 Case of a linear project:

In the case of linear projects that can have effects over considerable distances (pipelines, underwater cables, coastal roads, etc.) a preliminary phase, based on the overlapping of assessment scales, will be necessary. This overlapping can be carried out *a priori*, utilising existing documents (underwater and coastal maps) and information from independent experts on priority impact areas. It can also be carried out through the implementation of a pre-sampling study, with the sole purpose of identifying high-impact areas. In particular, detection of impacts can be carried out, in shallow waters, by aerial photography. A survey among users of the study area will also enable more targeted identification (fishing areas, dive sites, etc.). Following this preselection of priority impact areas, the next phase involves proceeding (as in the case of a concentrated project) on each of the areas and issues under consideration. In other words, all potential sectors for location sites, the area directly influenced by works, and the remote area subject to the project's indirect effects are to be considered.

The results of the study area's general characterization should be presented in the form of: 1) a cartographic atlas of the main factors studied (outstanding species, biological

communities, geomorphologies, uses, etc.) and data on occurrences that cannot be mapped; 2) a summary but well illustrated description of ecological facies observed and their conservation issues; 3) an estimate of the uses and cumulative impacts present in the study area; and 4) periodical variations (daily, seasonal, etc.) of ecological, physical and human phenomena impacting the study area. These results are to complement the analysis previously carried out. This process thus enables a preliminary assessment of temporal changes of identified factors and an evaluation of the site's capacity to integrate changes.

4.7.3 Fine-scale study: Identification of sensitive sites, selection of indicator variables and installation of monitoring stations

The **identification of sensitive sites** depends on cross-checking data from the project description and the general characteristics of the study area. Their determination depends on: 1) the identification of a major conservation issue, 2) the assumed risk of being under considerable impact from the project (impacted sites), and 3) their accessibility with resources that are safe, adequate and financially feasible. These criteria will be all the more reliable when the project description (released substances, flow rates, siting of outfalls, etc.) and the general characterization of the study area (hydrodynamism, study of biological communities, geomorphologies, topographies, etc.) are precise, recent and exhaustive. (See Fig 29). These sensitive sites could be subjected to a marking system which would facilitate their observation from the surface, particularly with fishers, boaters and maritime companies in mind. Furthermore, as natural environments are sensitive to numerous sources of stress, the isolation of the project's effects on a specific impacted site might appear difficult. The identification of control site which has the same general characteristics but does not suffer the project's impacts, therefore is an essential component of the monitoring regime..

Indicator variables of environmental disturbances can be selected from those considered overarching (hydrology, sedimentology, currents, etc.) as well as those that indicate disturbances to biological communities (ecological or bio-indicators). These ecological variables must be defined according to: 1) their aptitude to vary spatially and temporally with changes to environmental conditions, 2) their sensitivity to expected project effects, 3) their relationship with an eventual use or non-use value within the study area, and 4) their numerical value (quantification of impacts, possibility of measuring them). This knowledge can be acquired through fundamental work on the behaviour of ecological variables under stressors and is often provided in expert reports and scientific publications.⁵⁰ Depending on the case, socioeconomic variables can also be included (density of bathing resort users, name of fishers, etc.) (Fig. 30.).

⁵⁰ Bibliographic sources used to justify potential causal relations between environmental disturbances (project effects) and spatial or temporal variations of indicator variables must be as robust and recent as possible, certain ecological foundations having occasionally been dismissed by recent works. The recovery rate of coral populations could, for example, be used as an indicator of degradation in water quality (eutrophication, turbidity, sedimentation, temperature, etc.), although some species are much more resistant than others to these types of environmental disturbances. The targeting of species of the *Acropora* genus will increase the refinement and reliability of causal links between disturbance and coral mortality (Facon et al., 2016).

Figure 30 Composition method of environmental indicators (adaptation of OECD table, 1993)

Following these steps the **monitoring sites** can be established so that any significant variation in the indicator variables could be statistically quantified and evaluated (fine-scale approach). This approach requires space-time comparisons, and sites will have to be distributed as uniformly as possible throughout impacted and control sites, before, during and after works are undertaken. They are to be fixed and remain in place, until the end of the post-EIA monitoring process (GPS, pole and floater, galvanized pike, visual cues, etc.)

The location of monitoring sites should be determined by the sampling strategy which is itself based on monitoring objectives (see Frontier, 1983; Scherrer, 1984; Giraudoux, 2004; Facon et al., 2016). Knowledge acquired on the shifting trends of variables in the study area, will enable the definition of optimum intervention periods so as to ensure sampling can be carried out under the best conditions for analysis, while allowing for ecological coherency, safety and site accessibility (Fig. 31 - *From the outside working in: scleractinian corals, bony fish (Osteichthyans), turtles (Chelonia mydas, Eretmochelys imbricata), humpback whale (Megaptera novaeangliae), dolphins (Tursiops spp., Stenella spp.), crown-of-thorns starfish (Acanthaster planci), Triton's trumpet (Charonia tritonis), macro-algae and cyanobacteria (except Sargassaceae and Asparagopsis spp. that develop in winter) (according to Obura, 2016; Durville, 2002; Perrigault, 2010; Dulau-Drouot et al., 2012; Condet and Dulau-Drouot, 2016; Zann et al., 1987; Nugranad et al., 2000; Semple, 1997; pers. com. Mulochau and Zubia)*

Figure 31 Summary of periods considered optimal in La Réunion for the study of specific emblematic taxonomic groups in reef areas.

It is important to note that not all indicator variables will be sampled at all stations and at similar times. For example, carrying out water quality testing at regular and increasing distances from an industrial outflow would make sense even though this systematic sampling plan would not necessarily pick up the project's effect on the richest biological communities; as the most sensitive and those representing the most critical environmental issues, will not necessarily be regularly distributed around the discharge⁵¹ site (Figure 29). However, for statistical analyses of causation (linear regression) being sought between one or several variables, all variables integrated in the analyses have to be measured at the stations at identical times.

Sampling methods of indicator values fall into four categories: 1) visual measurements (underwater visual census or UVC), 2) *in situ* collection and analyses; 3) *in situ* collection and laboratory analyses; 4) measurements and observations by remote sensing and acoustic devices.

Quantitative UVC methods are generally used to measure ecological variables. These methods, which are highly varied (see Labrosse et al., 2002, (Jackson *et al.* 2014) a often involve determining a volume, space, line or points from which selected ecological variables are measured [specific richness, diversity indices (Shannon, Pielou, Simpson, etc.), densities, rate of recovery, etc.] usually within a limited period of time (Fig. 31). The method chosen will depend on the precision required the of expected results, time

⁵¹ In some types of development and certain overseas departments framework documents have been validated for the selection of indicator variables and the location of monitoring stations. This is the case in La Réunion within the framework of impact assessments linked to the installation or extension of treatments plants. A manual was drafted in 2013 with a view to defining a standard sampling plan according to the technical characteristics of the development project (Andral et al., 2013). These documents generally propose critical thresholds beyond which special measures must be taken and keys to the interpretation of measured variables provided.

available for research, study objectives, and the skills of research divers (Facon et al., 2016).

Figure 32 Estimation of recovery rate of hard substrates by different fixed organisms carrying out a UVC using the line-intercept transect (LIT) method (© J. Wickel)

In situ collection and analysis methods are primarily used to measure the following parameters: general water quality (salinity, temperature, pH, etc.), physical (depth, topography), meteorological (wind speed, light intensity, etc.) and oceanographic (water transparency, current velocity). Protocols are standardized and can be implemented by trained technicians. They usually involve the use of a measuring probe (multi-parameter probe, sonar, anemometer, light meter, turbidimeter, current meter, etc.) under conditions required for the correct interpretation and immediate reading of results. These methods can also involve the approximate measurement of certain variables with simple, tested tools (Secchi disk, graduated pole, floating drogue, etc.) (Fig. 32).

Figure 33 In situ measurement of water transparency with Secchi disc (© M. Pinault)

Finally the *in situ* collection and subsequent analysis (office or laboratory) are often more difficult to implement (sensitivity of measures, material collected, costly and cumbersome packaging and conservation, delivery costs, etc.) and require a greater number of different skills (hydrology, hydrodynamics, sedimentology, ecology, ecotoxicology, taxonomy, etc.). They allow for the measurement of the majority of physico-chemical and sediment-related variables, as well as physiological and bacteriological indicators, as well as those related to small-scale or cryptic biological communities (plankton, sedimentary macrofauna). They can also involve the *ex situ* analysis and interpretation of photographs and film sequences taken on site (photographic identification of unknown species, ichthyologic studies with high definition camera (STAVIRO et MICADO © IFREMER type) [Pelletier et al., 2012], establishment of percentage recovery by benthic organisms on quadrat photographs, etc.) (Fig. 33). These analyses might require the intervention of external specialists (approved laboratories, university research units, local specialist agencies, etc.).

Figure 34 Deployment of a rotating-head video camera (STAVIRO) in New Caledonia (© IFREMER). Recorded images will be analysed once the device is recovered

In the case of *in situ* sampling (water, sediment, living matter), each sample should at a minimum be identified with the name of the operator, the date and time of the event, identification of the monitoring station and its coordinates (longitude, latitude, depth) as well as sea state (turbulence, visibility, current, etc.) in addition to meteorological conditions (cloudiness, air temperature, wind, etc.) and the protocol and materials used. This information comprises the metadata which should accompany any information shared about the variables monitored. Standard data and metadata formats are available for the majority of environmental data and should be systematically used so that data can be subsequently integrated into reference bases on the natural environment.

Some methods also allow for the collection of very precise information over vast surfaces. These include, for example, three-dimensional imaging methods of the seabed by multi-beam sounders, often associated with a side scan sonar and reflection-seismic profile measurements, so as to ascertain the geological and geomorphological nature of mapped seabeds or by the airborne Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) method. Some data acquisition techniques can also use wave lengths beyond the visible spectrum (hyperspectral images) so as to accurately characterise the type of seabed (e.g. coral and algal cover) from an aerial overflight. Fisheries can also be evaluated with multi-beam sounders and deductions made on the species of fish and their abundance, from the echo characteristics of individuals which crossed the sounder's emission field. The

deployment of such techniques falls outside the scope of medium-sized environmental service providers (technical researchers, consultants, experts) and is generally carried out by specialized structures working in the field of surveys. These services are particularly called for in the framework of linear projects (cables and underwater pipelines, offshore bridges and viaducts, etc.), where the quality and precision of bathymetric and geomorphological data will determine the reliability of the retained alignment options.

This part of the study should be presented in the form of: 1) a bibliographic compilation, justifying the choice of indicator variables, 2) a simple numeric characterisation (averages, standard errors, reference values, etc.) of indicator variables across the study area, of the region or the biogeographic region, 3) mapping of the ecological issues (weak, average, strong) relative to the different homogenous management units (habitats of outstanding species) within the study area, in view of chosen indicator variables and according to periods of the year (summer, winter), 4) sensitive areas (priority issues potentially exposed to the effects of the project), control areas (priority issues isolated from the effects of the project) and monitoring stations, and 5) an assessment of risks linked to public hygiene, health and sanitation and conflicts of use.

4.7.4 Comparison of results in time and space

Once the indicator variable measures have been implemented, one of the most frequently used data analysis systems for impact assessments is the **Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) method** (Fig. 34). This consists of comparing the results acquired following an identical sampling of stations installed within impacted and control areas before, if possible during, and after the project has been carried out. This comparison of averages is aimed at estimating the project's impact on sensitive sites, considering possible hazards beyond the control of the project (cyclone, strong winds, swells, other projects, etc.) and the hazards of which are also observed on control sites. This seemingly simple method nonetheless requires a knowledge of the limits to the implementation and interpretation of statistical models developed. The choice of the number of stations per site, the sampling methods and the diversity of measured parameters will notably determine the strength of the analyses carried out and will influence the reliability and the robustness of information provided (Facon et al., 2016). Furthermore, certain variables, such as densities of mobile species, such a reef fish, are characterized by a very high variance. This variance is essentially instantaneous, and a function of the random movements of fish and, to a lesser degree, biases in the detectability of species or on the part of the observer (McClanahan et al., 2007). This instantaneous variation renders the detection of temporal changes through comparative analyses of averages and variances difficult. Nonetheless, the drafting of a monitoring protocol should, as far as possible, minimize sources of variation. In this sense, a justification of the sampling plan and the analyses carried out should be provided in the study report.

As a complement to the BACI method, **multivariate analyses** of the multidimensional scaling (MDS) or ascending hierarchical classification allow the characterization of community structures, particularly benthic ones, and reef fish populations. These analyses provide information on possible modifications to densities, biomasses or relative recovery rates among species or species groups of a same population or community. These structural analyses of populations allow for interpretations of the role of certain species or groups of species (foundation, keystone, engineer, facilitator, symbiotic, etc.) and all interspecific interaction. These analyses also allow a

characterization of trophic or populations' demographic structures by assigning each species or group of species an ecological functionality (feeding regime, demographic strategy, type of size, etc.) The classification tools (typological analyses) provide a hierarchical organization of the stations and sampling campaigns according to structural resemblances of their populations. This notion of structural similarity or diversity can be statistically tested (e.g. analysis of similarity [ANOSIM], permutational multivariate analysis of variance [PERMANOVA]) and contribute to the interpretation of compared averages carried out using the BACI method. The analysis of Mandelbrot's rank-frequency diagrams can also complete information acquired on the structure of sampled populations (Cagniant, 1989).

Figure 35 Example of BACI analysis carried out on a sampling between 2006 and 2012 in New Caledonia within the framework of a mining project (according to Adjeroud et al., 2016). These analyses show the impact of work carried out on some stations and limited to A

The comparison of results in both time and space are presented in the form of: 1) comparison analyses of averages according to the BACI method, 2) multivariate analyses of the structure of sampled populations (species, groups of species, food regimes, size classes, etc.), and 3) inventories of flora and fauna identified by zone and monitoring event. These analyses provide a hierarchical and "either/or" approach to the areas (impacted and control) and assessed monitoring events (before and after project implementation), in the light of indicator variables measured. These provide the project manager with information on the project's proven effects on the ecology, habitats and possibly heritage, living conditions, or the economy of the study area. They also provide benchmark results which serves as the basis of post-EIA follow-up. Although this procedure is still infrequent, it is generally desirable that these analyses are integrated in interoperable databases so as to ensure dissemination of results and comparisons with data from follow-up monitoring regimes.

4.8 Prevention and reduction measures and estimation of project impact (residual) on the environment

The measures aimed at mitigating project impacts on the environment are assigned the general term, reduction measures. These come into play during the impact assessment when, despite efforts at prevention, significant impacts remain or are likely to remain (residual impacts). Indeed, despite application of the precautionary principle, every project is susceptible to producing significant impacts. Once an impact, identified as harmful cannot be totally avoided, the project manager is under obligation to implement reduction and compensatory measures and to budget for related expenditures.

4.8.1 Prevention and reduction measures

In the previous chapters we studied prevention procedures, seeking alternatives that have the least environmental impact (following a status analysis of the study area). The decision on what procedure to use, is based primarily on the identification of opportunities, sites and methods (construction, exploitation, dismantling)⁵³ offering the greatest number of advantages with respect to environmental, technical, economic and social criteria. High impact options would be abandoned in favour of those having less of an impact. These "lesser evil" prevention measures while not ensuring the perfect environmental integration of the project, do propose the best alternative, considering the constraints faced by the project manager, as well as integrating those linked to the environment.

Reduction measures on the chosen site are defined after evaluation of the project's effects on the environment. If the idea of prevention is generally the result of a multicriteria analysis of assets, constraints, opportunities and threats of each alternative, the notion of reduction is most frequently associated with a project's specific effect. It therefore requires a previous prioritisation of the effects presenting the greatest environmental impacts. This prioritization could be made on the basis of the initial status analysis, the evaluation of the project's effects and the study of causal links. The reduction measures relate to the project's direct, indirect and secondary effects on the

⁵³ The general guidelines of the PRO doctrine define three types of prevention: 1) prevention during the informed choice, 2) geographic prevention, and 3) technical prevention (CGDD, 2013).

environment and take into consideration both construction and dismantling methods (temporary effects) as well as industrial processes and treatment of discharges during the operational phase (permanent effects). These measures must also consider the project's possible cumulative effects with other past, present and future human actions.

Reduction measures proposed during construction and dismantling works (temporary effects) are usually greater in number. They have no relation to the technical aspects of project operations, but can increase costs and cause delays in implementation and delivery. These measures may apply to: 1) site construction methods, 2) confinement measures of effects, especially outside sensitive areas, and 3) measures to phase the steps having the greatest impacts, particularly outside sensitive periods.

The proposals relating to construction site methods can, for example, involve the establishment of a speed limit for barges, to reduce the effect of noise likely to disrupt marine mammals. They can also involve specific techniques, such as controlling noise generation by gradually ramping up impulse noise prior to the implementation of very noisy works (explosives, geothermic shocks, etc.) likely to damage sensors of certain marine organisms, or the use of watertight bucket-chain dredgers instead of mechanical shovels, so as to limit stirring up suspended material. The confinement measures of projects' effects can involve the installation of filtering dams made of geotextiles (pollution, suspended material, turbidity) or oil absorbent booms. Phasing measures involve, for example, planning the project steps that have most impact during the absence of migratory organisms or outside the most sensitive periods for resident organisms (reproduction, feeding, rest, etc.). They might also consist of taking advantage of natural cycles (tides, diurnal cycles, seasons, etc.) so as to guide general site operations towards a lesser risk of a severe accidental impact.

Proposed reduction measures during project operations (permanent effects) are often more difficult to implement primarily due to technical, human and economic constraints inherent to the feasibility of the project itself and delayed implementation of the EIA in the design approach. Ideally, the technical choices should not be abandoned prior to the termination of the EIA, so that they can assist in the design of the project with the least possible impact. The necessary reduction measures can highlight operational failures during the preliminary scoping phase or in the project's scaling. Their identification can call into question project characteristics regarding technical aspects and their implementation. Such measures can cover: 1) industrial procedures and the treatment of discharges, 2) operational procedures, 3) the siting of discharge outlets, and 4) the landscaping aspect of infrastructure, particularly underwater.

The proposals addressing industrial procedures and treatment of discharges can, for example, include the level of abatement of nitrogen and phosphorous (fixed aquaculture, extensive processes, activated sludge, etc.) from the effluents of a water treatment plant planned in an area identified as sensitive to eutrophication. They can also involve the banning of certain extensive procedures (lagoons, infiltration-percolation beds, etc.) having previously proved their inappropriateness for the climatic, geological or regional ecological contexts (fractured soil not allowing the retention of infiltrated effluents, risk of runoff on the area of influence of a lagoon, etc.) The measures involved in operational procedures can include the implementation of a corporate environmental policy (limiting the waste of materials and energies, optimization of methods, compacting and stocking of waste, recycling facilities, etc.), and additionally, such a policy is usually

associated with accompanying measures and/or adherence to an environmental quality standard (e.g. ISO 14001).

Proposals for the siting of discharge outlets can involve prevention measures within a sensitive area or an outstanding landscape as well as the recommendation of a minimum depth (thermocline, halocline), or a location favouring marine dilution or dispersion of outflow plumes. They are expected in the EIA so as to better address the environmental effects of the project. Finally, the modifications of the landscaping aspect of a project's infrastructure could be proposed in the case of a project's interaction with other previous, present and future human activities, such as the presence of resort areas or diving sites.

4.8.2 Classification of impacts and estimation of residual impacts

Once the project's potential impacts have been identified and prevention and reduction measures proposed, a further impact assessment should be carried out. Indeed, despite efforts to prevent or reduce impacts, some projects result in residual impacts. Once these impacts are significant, the project manager is obliged to implement compensatory measures and budget for associated expenditure. The notion of compensation thus involves a more precise evaluation of losses caused by the project.

The nexus between the project's likely effects on the environment, the environment's sensitivity to these effects and the recommended reduction measure enables a semi-quantitative estimation of residual impacts, generally defined with reference to a scale of values (weak, average, high). This evaluation is based particularly on calculation models of equivalent losses. The causal links between the project's likely effects and residual impacts will be stipulated (Fig. 35), for example, in the form of a table showing, in rows, the project's supposed effects and, in columns: 1) the type of foreseen impact, 2) the indicator variables of degradation, 3) proportionate reduction measures, and 4) the estimation of residual impacts. The rows can be linked hierarchically in descending order of importance of residual impacts. The risks of impacts should be detailed for each foreseen effect stating the type of degradation (benthos, fish, uses, etc.), their scope (surface, intensity), and their duration (temporary, permanent).⁵⁴

The implementation of monitoring measures post EIA will provide an analysis of losses resulting from the project's effects on selected indicator variables (comparison of results in both time and space). These results will provide numerical values, by monitoring station, of the decline in the recovery rate of coral or of fish biomass, with the extrapolation of the effect under consideration to the project's footprint.⁵⁵

⁵⁴ In the case of some effects supposedly temporary, the residual impact can have permanent consequences. For example, a depot of materials in a coral environment, even if it is temporary, has a high risk of permanently degrading the site, suffocating colonies, modifying the nature of the substrate, or generating persistent or eutrophying polluting substances. The concept of temporary or permanent effect is to be considered on the basis of the damaged caused.

⁵⁵ Although compensatory measures should *a priori* be dimensioned within the framework of the EIA and implemented as soon as possible in the project's programme, they can be adjusted depending on post-EIA results. This adjustment is indispensable in considering long-term impacts.

Figure 36 Chart of causal model "pressures - state - responses" (adapted from OECD, 1993)

4.8.3 Planning of monitoring post impact assessment

This monitoring should be carried out independently of any control procedures, so as to provide adequate warning to project managers of thresholds being accidentally exceeded, and the need to halt the project. The measured variables are then selected for the rapidity of their response to any anomalies such as a sharp increase in turbidity following a tear in a geotextile. On the other hand, they are not at all inclusive of chronic extended effects on the site, particularly on the biological communities. In contrast, post-EIA monitoring aims to determine the project's residual impacts.

A project's impact assessment and its quantification *a posteriori* is generally required, under several regulations. This follow-up monitoring enables information to be collected on whether the mitigation measures are effective and for verifying the accuracy of predictions made within the framework of the EIA. The primary aim of monitoring is to verify whether the petitioner is respecting regulatory commitments, but it is also desirable to identify lessons that are useful for similar developments in the future (this implies the availability of data and/or follow-up reports to third parties). The medium- and long-term consequences of some large projects can be monitored by an environmental research group for the long-term follow up of indicator species, monitoring of mortality rates, etc. such as in the case of the Beaufonds sugar factory on the east coast of La Réunion, where long-term monitoring stations have been operating for 20 years by the French scientific interest group, GIS.

4.9 Drafting of impact assessment report: required elements

The drafting phase which follows on from the on-site EIA, is carried out simultaneously with project development, and should faithfully record the project's analysis and conception. It should clearly reflect that all required environmental issues have been considered. The project manager holds responsibility for drafting the EIA report, and should present, at least: "a description of the project, an initial appraisal of the area likely to be affected and its environment, the study of the project's effects on the environment or human health, including the cumulative effects with other known projects, appropriate measures to prevent, reduce, and when necessary and possible offset/compensate for the project's outstanding negative effects on the environment or human health. The EIA also sets out an outline of the main alternative solutions that have been studied by the project leader providing an indication of the reasons for the choices, taking into account effects on the environment or human health; furthermore, in the case of transport infrastructure, it includes an analysis of the collective costs of pollution and disruptions and benefits for the population in general, as well as an evaluation of energy consumption resulting from project operations, mainly as the result of displacements caused or avoided; it includes a non-technical summary of information". This chapter also covers the main phases in the carrying out of the EIA (see Chapter III) and develops the elements that are indispensable and should appear in the technical report provided to the project manager.⁵⁶

The **project description** involves collecting all technical aspects of the project that are likely to be used in establishing its effects on the environment and human health and in the evaluation of prevention, reduction and compensation measures to address these effects. These characteristics mainly include: the cost, the footprint of infrastructure onshore and offshore, an artist's view of the project, the description of the different major technical options (project variants), the conditions of the building site and the project once operational, the nature and quantity of substances or emissions from energy consumption (chemical compounds, abnormalities re salinity, pH or temperature, noise, light, etc.). Temporary phasing of the project should also be outlined, which clearly indicates phases in works, operations, and finally its dismantling. The project's human and economic scale, including the expected levels of operation, the required human resources (employees, direct and indirect beneficiaries), the overall costs of pollutants and disturbances, and the expressed needs of the populations met by the project are also covered in this part of the study. An evaluation of consumption, particularly energy and water, resulting from project operations, could also be completed (obligatory in some cases of transport infrastructure). The quality of this part of the report depends to a large degree on the timeliness, precision and relevance of information provided by the project manager to those responsible for the EIA, and often requires an active approach to researching and cross-checking by the latter. This part, which is often overlooked in impact assessments (Jacob et al., 2014), can however result in serious forecasting errors, inaccuracies or omissions of some project effects on the environment or human health, that will later make it difficult to prevent, reduce or compensate for losses incurred.

The analysis of the **initial status** of the study area describes, on the basis of local, national or even international scientific references, and field observations by recognized

⁵⁶ These elements are detailed in 12 points under Article R. 122-5 of the Environment Code, modified by Article 1 of Decree 2011-2019 of 29 December 2001.

specialists, the geographical context, specific characteristics (outstanding, threatened, rare) and significant (quality of the environment, protection level) of the environmental components of the area under study. It appraises evolutionary trends so as to evaluate the site's capacity to support change. It also involves prioritizing and estimating the importance of different environmental issues (minor, moderate, priority) particularly for the identification of objective indicators (coral cover, presence of protected species, specific wealth, zoning of protected marine areas (PMA), outstanding ecological or landscaping functions, etc.). The spatial unity analysis of issues can be the habitat, characterized by its biotic and abiotic components, and the season representing the temporal unit, characterized in the tropics by temperature, rainfall and the frequency of extreme climatic events. Regarding an animal or plant species, the area under study can be described based on its conservation, or in terms of area of distribution and species occurrence. The initial appraisal also addresses the human context of the area affected by the project, as well as demographic, economic and urban trends. Previous uses and projects will also be identified. For this reason, local policy processes must be considered. For example, political will (expressed in a planning document, development scheme, etc.) to rehabilitate a degraded site will give it a "value" to be considered when establishing environmental issues. Summary cartographic records, particularly showing habitats, issues, primary ecological functions, outstanding landscapes, the status and protection level of environments, the footprints of the project and previous projects, traditional, pleasure and professional uses, land and sea uses, oceanographic (current patterns, hydrology, tides, etc.), climatic (seasonality of processes, rainfall, cyclone frequency and direction, etc.), and geomorphological (substrate, topography, sedimentology, etc.) influences necessary for the interpretation of the project's effects on the environment, should also be included.

The analysis of the project's effects on the environment and human health depends on spatial and temporal cross-checking of the project's technical characteristics and synthesized information from the appraisal of the initial status. The direct and indirect effects, both temporary and permanent, as well as the cumulative effects with other known projects are to be explored later. They can, for example, be completed with a table for each habitat and each season, with linkages made between the project's potential effects and the evaluation indicators of the environmental issue. Thus, transposing the effects onto a scale of values results in the estimation of the project's potential impacts on each evaluation indicator (e.g. low, medium, high; although five level scales are more commonly used). This analysis will at least address the project's impact on the flora and fauna, landscapes, sediments, water, hydrodynamics, biological balances, protection from use and cultural heritage, and if called for, on hygiene, safety and public health. As a result of this analysis, environments, species and ecological processes, with priority environmental issues, exposed to the major potential impacts of the project will be classified as highly vulnerable; inversely, those facing moderate to minor issues, slightly impacted by the project's potential effects, will have a low vulnerability. Periods of maximum sensitivity to pressures will also be specified.

As a result of the analysis of the project's potential effects on the environment and human health, **measures to prevent, reduce and, if necessary and possible, offset/compensate** are proposed. These measures are aimed at ensuring the project's environmental integration and the absence of global biodiversity loss, functionalities and ecological value or "no net loss". They should be proportionate to identified impacts. Corresponding expenditure estimates will also be included in the EIA report. These can

be presented in the form of a table summarizing costs envisaged for each proposed measure, if possible detailing elements of the estimate. On the basis of the survey of potential impacts of the different alternatives considered, prevention measures mainly relate to the choice of the variant with the least environmental impact. They can also involve the location of a discharge, the length or the installation depth of an outlet within a study area. Once the choice has been made, reduction measures will enable the mitigation of some of the project's adverse effects on the environment, notably through a reduction in the intensity of emissions (production method, filtration, decantation, etc.), the wise use of hydrodynamics (areas of high turbulence with high mixing potential), or the phasing of high-impact effects so they fall outside periods of maximum environmental sensitivity (day/night cycle, tides, seasons, etc.). These measures are essential and should always be considered and justified through previous scientific references, models of mechanisms deployed and, as far as possible, illustrated with examples, prior to considering any type of compensation. Certain measures (objectives, resources, effectiveness) are proposed in the chapter on EIAs technical and methodological framework. Following on from the prevention and reduction phases, residual impacts will remain. If significant residual impacts persist, restoration (temporary effects) or compensation (permanent effects) measures will be proposed that are proportionate to the issues at stake in the territory and the project so as to globally conserve the initial value of the environments with no net loss of biodiversity, functionality or heritage.

The **primary monitoring methods** of the project's effects on the environment, uses or human health are explained in a following section. This section of the study should result in a sampling strategy adapted and justified, specifically including: indicators measured (ecological, biotic and abiotic variables, frequency indicators, etc.), the choice of the sampling plan (spatial and temporal), information collection methods, types of restoration, and the possible storage of information (interactive databases, cartographic documents, etc.), statistical processing and analysis methods and means of presenting results. This can also involve the presentation of the results of the first monitoring event ("state zero"), carried out before works started; if this first scientific monitoring of the project's effects is included in the order to carry out the EIA. This phase is clearly distinguished from the appraisal of the initial status by the definition of reference sampling stations and the measure of quantitative indicators of evaluation criteria. Thus fixed measurement stations, located on the basis of general elements identified during the initial status appraisal, will allow a spatial and temporal replication of measures for statistical analysis. These stations must be located in highly sensitive areas (impacted stations). Control stations will also be placed outside the impacted area so as to ascertain the project's effect on external, temporal fluctuations (alternate or natural cycles, impact of other projects, etc.) (BACI method, see 4.7.4). The protocols implemented prior to the onset of works during the first sampling campaign will be repeated and carried out in an identical manner during the construction phase, during operations and, if possible, after the dismantling of infrastructure in the case of a project with a specific duration.

In addition to the afore-mentioned elements the report should include: 1) the **names and detailed functions** of the author(s) of the EIA and of the operators collecting data, 2) a **description of possible difficulties**, of a technical or scientific nature, found by the project manager and service providers in carrying out this study, and 3) a **non-technical summary** so as to render information in the EIA accessible to the public. The

importance of preventive and impact-reduction measures is to be stressed, with compensation, less certain as far as results are concerned, to be contemplated where no alternative exists. The EIA report is then presented to the EA, the administrative authority responsible for studying the request for authorization of waiver, and then to the public in the case of a public enquiry.

5 BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adjeroud, M., Gilbert, A., Facon, M., Foglia, M., Moreton, B., Heintz, T. (2016). Localised and limited impact of a dredging operation on coral cover in the northwestern lagoon of New Caledonia. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 105:208-214.

Agence des Aires Marines Protégées - AAMP (2009). Tome 1 Les cultures marines. Activités - Interactions - Dispositifs d'encadrement Orientations de gestion. Référentiel pour la gestion dans les sites Natura 2000 en mer. 246 p. www.aires-marines.fr/...pour-la...mer/Referentiel-Cultures-marines

Agence des Aires Marines Protégées - AAMP (2011). Les différentes catégories d'aires marines protégées. <http://www.aires-marines.fr/Les-aires-marines-protegees/Categories-d-aires-marines-protegees>

Agence des Aires Marines Protégées - AAMP (2012). Le Parc naturel marin des Glorieuses. <http://www.aires-marines.fr/L-Agence/Organisation/Parcs-naturels-marins/Parc-naturel-marin-des-Glorieuses>

Agence des Aires Marines Protégées - AAMP (2013). Une stratégie nationale pour les aires marines protégées. <http://www.aires-marines.fr/Les-aires-marines-protegees/Strategie-nationale>

Agence des Aires Marines Protégées - AAMP (2014). Parc Naturel de la mer de Corail – Périmètre. http://cartographie.aires-marines.fr/sites/all/modules/cartographie/pdf/_GES_NC_Perimetre_PN_a3pa.pdf

Aminot, A., Kérouel, R. (2004). Hydrologie des écosystèmes marins. Paramètres et analyses. Ed. Ifremer, 336 p.

Andral, B., Cambert, H., Turquet, J., Ropert, M., Duval, M., Vermentot, C., Boissery, P., Talec, P. (2013). Guide méthodologique pour la surveillance des rejets urbains dans les eaux littorales de La Réunion. Rapport pour le compte du MEDDE. 88 p.

Armada, N., White, A.T., Christie, P. (2009). Managing fisheries resources in Danajon Bank, Bohol, Philippines: An ecosystem-based approach. *Coastal Management*, 37:308-330.

Aznar, O., Jeanneaux, P., Déprés, C. (2009). Les services environnementaux fournis par l'agriculture, entre logique sectorielle et logique territoriale: un cadre d'analyse économique. 3èmes journées de recherches en sciences sociales INRA SFER CIRAD - 09, 10 & 11 décembre 2009 – Montpellier, France. 20 p.

Balmford, A., Rodrigues, A.S.L., ten Brink, P., Kettunen, M., Braat, L., de Groot, R. (2008) *The Economics of Biodiversity and Ecosystems: Scoping the Science*. Cambridge, UK: European Commission (contract: ENV/070307/2007/486089/ETU/B2).

Beliaeff, B., Bouvet, G., Fernandez, J.M., David, C., Laugier, T. (2011). Guide pour le suivi de la qualité du milieu marin en Nouvelle-Calédonie. Programmes ZONECO et CNRT Le Nickel. 169 p.

Béoutis, A., Jean, P., Colas, S. (2008). L'observatoire du littoral, démographie et économie du littoral. Les dossiers de l'observatoire du littoral. Rapport INSEE et SOeS. 22 p.

Beukering, P.V., Brander, L., Tompkins, E., McKenzie, E. (2007). Valuing the Environment in Small Islands, in: Joint Nature Conservation Committee, P.P.J.U.T.r., June 2007 (Ed.), 128 p. <http://www.jncc.gov.uk/page-4065>.

Biesel, F. (1949). Calcul de l'amortissement d'une houle dans un liquide visqueux de profondeur finie. *La Houille Blanche*, 5:630-634.

Bragoni, G. (1980). Les récifs artificiels. Analyses et résultats de quelques expériences. Mém. de Maîtrise de Biologie Marine. Univ. Nice. 56 p.

Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP), 2012. Standard on Biodiversity Offsets. BBOP, Washington, <http://www.bbop.forest-DC.trends.org/guidelines/Standard.pdf>.

Cagniant, H. (1989). Essai d'application de quelques indices et modèles de distributions d'abondances à trois peuplements de fourmis terricoles. *Orsis*, 4:113-124.

Carson, R.T., Mitchell, R.C., Hanemann, W.M., Kopp, R.J., Presser, S., Ruud, P.A. (1992). A contingent valuation study of lost passive use values resulting from the Exxon Valdez oil spill (No. 6984). University Library of Munich, Germany. 133 p. http://www.evostc.state.ak.us/universal/documents/publications/economic/econ_passive.pdf

Carson, R.T., Flores, N.E., Mitchell, R.C. (1999). The theory and measurement of passive-use value (pp. 97-130). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Caumette, P., Mouneyrac, C., Guillouzo, A., Hourcade, E., Tournier, A. (2012). Contaminants et environnements: constater, diffuser, décider. Les Cahiers de l'ANR - n°6. Agence Nationale pour la Recherche. 163 p.

Chevassus-au-Louis, B., Salles, J.B., Bielsa, S., Richard, D., Martin, G., Pujol, J.L. (2009). Approche économique de la biodiversité et des services liés aux écosystèmes. Contribution à la décision publique. Rapport du Centre d'Analyse Stratégique - CAS. 378p. <http://www.ladocumentationfrancaise.fr/var/storage/rapports-publics/094000203.pdf>

Chipeaux, A., Pinault, M., Pascal, N., Pioch, S. (2016). Analyse comparée à l'échelle mondiale des techniques d'ingénierie écologiques adaptées à la restauration des récifs coralliens. *Revue d'Écologie (Terre et Vie)*, 71:99-110.

Christie, M., Warren, J., Hanley, N., Murphy, K., Wright, R.E. (2004). Developing measures for valuing changes in biodiversity: Final Report to DEFRA, London, United Kingdom, 178 p.

Commissariat Général au Développement Durable - CGDD (2013) Lignes directrices nationales sur la séquence éviter, réduire et compenser les impacts sur les milieux naturels. 229 p.

Commission Mixte Internationale – CMI (2003). Douzième rapport biennal sur la qualité de l'eau dans les grands lacs. Espèces exotiques. <http://www.ijc.org/php/publications/html/12br/francais/report/biological/ais.html>

Conand, C., Chabanet, P., Quod, J.P., Bigot, L. (1997). Suivi de l'état de santé des récifs coralliens du sud-ouest de l'Océan Indien - Manuel méthodologique. Secrétariat général Commission océan Indien ; programme régional environnement. 32 p.

Condet, M., Dulau-Drouot, V. (2016). Habitat selection of two island-associated dolphin species from the south-west Indian Ocean. *Continental Shelf Research*, 125:18-27.

Connell, J.H. (1978). Diversity in tropical rain forests and coral reefs. *Science*, 19:1302-1310.

Conseil Général de l'Environnement et du Développement Durable - CGEDD (2016). L'Autorité environnementale du Conseil Général de l'Environnement et du Développement Durable. <http://www.cgedd.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/presentation-r169.html>

Costanza, R., d'Arge, R., de Groot, R., Farber, S., Grasso, M., Hannon, B., Limburg, K., Naeem, S., Oneill, R.V., Paruelo, J., Raskin, R.G., Sutton, P., van den Belt, M. (1997). The value of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital. *Nature*, 387:253

Dahl, A.L. (1981). Coral reef monitoring handbook. Rapport de la Communauté du Pacifique - SPC Nouméa. 21 p.

Dalzell, P., Adams, T.J.H. (1997) Sustainability and management of reef fisheries in the Pacific Islands. *Proceedings of the Eighth International Coral Reef Symposium*, 2:2027-2032.

Darovec, J.E., Carlton, J.M., Pulver, T.R., Moffler, M.D., Smith, G.B., Whitfield, W.K., Willis, C.A., Steidinger, K.A., Joyce E.A. (1975). Techniques for Coastal Restoration and Fishery Enhancement in Florida. *Florida Marine Research Publication*, 15:0-32.

David, G., Herrenschildt, J.B., Mirault, E. (2007). Valeur sociale et économique des récifs coralliens du Pacifique insulaire. CRISP (Coral Reef Initiative for Pacific), composante 1A-Projet 1A4 Gestion Côtière Intégrée. 43 p.

David, G., René, F., Tessier, E. (1999). Synthèse du groupe de travail « pêche et aquaculture ». In : Actes du Séminaire Gestion Intégrée et Développement Durable de la Zone Côtière. 14-18 juin, 1999, Saint Leu. Saint-Denis de La Réunion, CLOE, 13-20.

Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs – Defra (2008). An introductory Guide to valuing ecosystem services. Ref: PB12852. 68 p. <http://www.defra.gov.uk>

De Groot, R.S., Wilson, M., Boumans, R. (2002). A typology for the description, classification and valuation of ecosystem functions, goods and services. *Ecological Economics* 41:393-408.

De Wulf, M. (2012). Population Pyramids of the World from 1950 to 2100. <http://populationpyramid.net/>

Dietz, T., Fitzgerald, A., Shwom, R. (2005). Environmental values. *Annual Review of Environment & Resources*, 30:335-372.

Dulau-Drouot, V., Fayon, J., Mouysset, L., Boucaud, V. (2012). Occurrence and residency patterns of humpback whales off Réunion Island during 2004-10. *Journal of Cetacean Research and Management*, 12:255-263.

Durville, P. (2002). Colonisation ichtyologique des platiers de La Réunion et biologie des post-larves de poissons coralliens. Thèse doctorale, Université de La Réunion & Université de Perpignan. 170 p + annexes.

Duval, C., Duclerc, J. (1986). Evaluation des impacts des aménagements récifaux sur la faune halieutique et son exploitation. *FAO Fish Report*, 357:167-175.

Environnement Carrières et Matériaux - ENCEM (2011), Gestion et aménagement écologique des carrières de roches massives, Guide pratique à l'usage des exploitants de carrières, ENCEM, juin 2011, ref: REA A5 11 G (publié en 2011, avec une bibliographie sur Cd-Rom sur les potentialités écologiques des carrières).

Facon, M., Pinault, M., Obura, D., Pioch, S., Pothin, K., Bigot, L., Garnier, R., Quod, J.P. (2016). A comparative study of the accuracy and effectiveness of Line and Point Intercept Transect methods for coral reef monitoring in the southwestern Indian Ocean islands. *Ecological Indicators*, 60:1045-1055.

Forman, R.T. (2000). Estimate of the area affected ecologically by the road system in the United States. *Conservation Biology*, 14:31-35.

François, O., Pascal, N. (2012). Mesures de compensation des impacts pour les récifs coralliens. Rapport IFRECOR. 46 p.

Frontier, S. (1983). Stratégies d'échantillonnage en écologie. Masson, Paris. 494 p.

Gabrié, C. (1998). L'état des récifs coralliens en France d'outre-mer : Nouvelle-Calédonie, Wallis et Futuna, Polynésie Française, Clipperton, Guadeloupe, Martinique, Mayotte, La Réunion, îles éparses de l'Océan Indien. Paris (FRA) ; Rapport IFRECOR pour le compte du Ministère de l'Aménagement du Territoire et de l'Environnement ; Secrétariat d'Etat à l'outre-mer, 137 p + annexes.

Garcia, J. (2012). Influence des facteurs anthropiques et environnementaux sur les capacités de déplacements des poissons coralliens : implications dans le design des Aires Marines Protégées. Thèse doctorale, Université de Perpignan. 204 p + annexes.

Gargominy, O. (Ed.) (2003). Biodiversité et conservation dans les collectivités françaises d'outre-mer. Collection Planète Nature. Comité français pour l'UICN, Paris, France. 246 p.

Giraudoux, P. (2004). Les stratégies d'échantillonnage. Outils méthodologiques. Manuel méthodologique, Agence universitaire de la francophonie, Université de Franche-Comté. 7 p. http://www.infotheque.info/cache/8492/www.univ-fcomte.fr/download/ufr_st/document/masters/tronc_commun_ess_qtebv/echantillonnage0410.pdf

Gratwicke, B., Speight, M.R. (2005). The relationship between fish species richness, abundance and habitat complexity in a range of shallow tropical marine habitats. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 66:650-667.

Groupe d'Étude et d'Observation sur le Dragage et l'Environnement - GEODE (2014). Rédaction des études d'impact d'opérations de dragage et d'immersion en milieu estuarien et marin. Guide méthodologique avec la collaboration du MEDDE. 216 p. http://www.eau-mer-fleuves.cerema.fr/IMG/pdf/Guide_GEODE_Etude_Impact_cle51a3aa.pdf

Guillet, F., Mermet, L. (2013). L'expertise, composante essentielle mais insuffisante des stratégies pour la biodiversité: le cas de la démoustication en Camargue (France), *VertigO - la revue électronique en sciences de l'environnement* [En ligne], Volume 13

Numéro 2 | septembre 2013, mis en ligne le 01 octobre 2013, consulté le 21 avril 2015.
URL: <http://vertigo.revues.org/14025>; DOI: 10.4000/vertigo.14025

Honrado, J.P., Vieira, C., Soares, C., Monteiro, M.B., Marcus, B., Pereira, H.M., Partidário, M.R. (2013). Can we infer about ecosystem services from EIA and SEA practice? A framework for analysis and examples from Portugal. *Environ Impact Asses Rev*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2012.12.002>

Hocdé, A.S. (2009). Accidents traumatiques, envenimations et intoxications alimentaires par la faune marine de Polynésie Française. Thèse pour le diplôme d'Etat de Docteur en pharmacie. Université de Nantes. 125 p.

Hugo, G. (2011). Future demographic change and its interactions with migration and climate change. *Global Environmental Change*; 21, Supplement 1: S21–S33.

IFC (2017). Stakeholder Engagement: A Good Practice Handbook for Companies Doing Business in Emerging Markets. DC. Available at:
http://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/938f1a0048855805beacfe6a6515bb18/IFC_StakeholderEngagement.pdf?MOD=AJPERES (last access:31/03/2018).

Jackson, J.B.C., Donovan, M.K., Cramer, K.L. & Lam, V.V. (2014). Status and Trends of Caribbean Coral Reefs: 1970-2012. Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland.

Jacob, C., Quétier, F., Aronson, J., Pioch, S., Levrel, H. (2014). Vers une politique française de compensation des impacts sur la biodiversité plus efficace: défis et perspectives. *Vertigo - la revue électronique en sciences de l'environnement [En ligne]*, Volume 14 Numéro 3 | Décembre 2014, mis en ligne le 16 janvier 2015, consulté le 21 avril 2015.
URL: <http://vertigo.revues.org/15385> ; DOI: 10.4000/vertigo.15385

Jameson, S.C., McManus, J.W., Spalding, M.D. (1995). State of the reefs: regional and global perspectives. ICRI Executive Secretariat Background Paper, May 1995. NOAA, 32 p.

Jourdan, V. (2010). Livret sur les récifs coralliens de l'outre-mer français. Livret pédagogique de l'Association Te mana o te moana pour le compte de la fondation WWF France et l'IFRECOR. 70 p.

Joyeux, J.C., Camus, P., Boucherau, J.L. (1988). évaluation du peuplement ichthyique des Lavezzi. *Tra. Sci. Parc. Nation. Règ. Res. Nat. Corse, Fr*, 17:1-45.

Kayal, M., Vercelloni, J., De Loma, T.L., Bosserelle, P., Chancerelle, Y., Geoffroy, S., Stivenart, C., Michonneau, F., Penin, L., Planes, S., Adjerdoud, M. (2012). Predator crown-of-thorns starfish (*Acanthaster planci*) outbreak, mass mortality of corals, and cascading effects on reef fish and benthic communities. *PloS one*, 7(10), e47363.

Kool, J.T., Moilanen, A., Treml, E.A. (2013). Population connectivity: recent advances and new perspectives. *Landscape Ecology*, 28:165–185.

Krutilla, J. V., Fisher, A. C. (1975). The economics of natural environments: studies in the valuation of commodity and amenity resources. Baltimore: John Hopkins Press. 301 p.

Labrosse, P., Kulbicki, M., Ferraris, J. (2002) Underwater Visual Fish Census Surveys - Proper Use and Implementation. Secretariat of the Pacific Community Press, Noumea, NC. 54 p.

Lal, P., Lim-Applegate, H., Scoccimarro, M. (2003). The adaptive decision-making process as a tool for integrated natural resource management: focus, attitudes, and approach. *Integrated Natural Resources Management: Linking Productivity, the Environment and Development*. Wallingford: CABI Publishing, 65-86.

Lamotte, M. (1995). À propos de la biodiversité. *Laboratoire d'Herpétologie du Muséum national d'histoire naturelle. Le Courrier de l'environnement n°24*, avril 1995.

Landsberg, F., Treweek, J. & Stickler, N.M.e.a. (2013). *Weaving Ecosystem Services Into Impact Assessment*, Washington, DC: World Resource Institute.

Laurans, Y., Pascal, N., Binet, T., Brander, L., Clua, E., David, G., Rojat, D., Seidl, A. (2013). Economic valuation of ecosystem services from coral reefs in the South Pacific: taking stock of recent experience. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 116:135-144.

Lavergne, D., Duvigneaud, P., Lamotte, M., Peres, J.M. (2005). Structure et fonctionnement des écosystèmes. 16p. 2005 *Encyclopædia Universalis*.

Letourneur, Y., Harmelin-Vivien, M., Galzin, R. (1993). Impact of hurricane Firinga on fish community structure on fringing reefs of Reunion Island, SW Indian Ocean. *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 37:109-120.

Levrel, H., Pioch, S., Spieler, R. (2012). Compensatory mitigation in marine ecosystems: which indicators for assessing the “no net loss” goal of ecosystem services and ecological functions? *Marine Policy*, 36:1202-1210.
<http://esanalysis.colmex.mx/Sorted%20Papers/2012/2012%20FRA%20USA%20-CS%20USA%20FL,%203F%20Phys.pdf>

MEA (2003). Ecosystems and Human Well-being. *Millenium Ecosystem Assessment - Synthesis*. Island Press, Washington, DC. 47 pp.

McClanahan, T.R., Graham, N.A.J., Maina, J., Chabanet, P., Bruggemann, J.H. Polunin, N.V.C. (2007). Influence of instantaneous variation on estimates of coral reef fish populations and communities *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 340:221–234.

Melki, F. (2002). Guide sur la prise en compte des milieux naturels dans les études d'impacts. *Etude Biotope*. 75 p. <http://fr.calameo.com/read/00077694870ecdf163445>

Michel, P. (2001). L'EIE sur l'environnement. *Etude BCEOM*. 157 p.
http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/eia/documents/EIAGuides/france_EIA_complete.pdf

Milana, G. (2013). Rapport sur une stratégie pour la pêche dans la mer Adriatique et la mer Ionienne. Commission de la pêche. Proposition de Résolution du Parlement Européen.
<http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?pubRef=-//EP//TEXT+REPORT+A7-2013-0234+0+DOC+XML+V0//FR>

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment – MEA (2005), Ecosystems and human well-being. *Synthesis*, Ed. Island Press, Washington, DC, 155 p.

Miller, F.P., Vandome, A.F., McBrewster, J. (2011). Câble sous-marin – Fond marin, Câblé, Télécommunications, Énergie électrique, Fibre optique, Modulation de fréquence, Télégraphe, Internet. Alphascript Publishing. 84 p.

Miller, I., Müller, R. (1999). Validity and reproducibility of benthic cover estimates made during broadscale surveys of coral reefs by manta tow. *Coral Reefs*, 18:353-356.

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2010). Guide de l'EIE sur l'environnement des parcs éoliens. Actualisation 2010. 191 p.

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2012a) Doctrine relative à la séquence éviter, réduire et compenser les impacts sur le milieu naturel. 9 p.

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2012b) Guide « Espèces protégées, aménagements et infrastructures ». Recommandations pour la prise en compte des enjeux liés aux espèces protégées et pour la conduite d'éventuelles procédures de dérogation au sens des articles L. 411-1 et L. 411-2 du code de l'environnement dans le cadre des projets d'aménagements et d'infrastructures. 65 p. <http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/userfiles/Esp%C3%A8ces%20prot%C3%A9g%C3%A9es%20V6%20u29-06-202.pdf>

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2014) Eau et Biodiversité - Éviter, réduire et compenser les impacts sur le milieu naturel. <http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/Doctrine-eviter-reduire-et,28438.html>

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2015a). Nomenclature des installations classées – Liste des installations soumises à la TGAP – Direction générale de prévention des risques – Service des risques technologiques. Mai 2015, version 36. 88 p. http://www.ineris.fr/aida/sites/default/files/gesdoc/30296/BrochureNom_v36_public_20150528162908.pdf

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2015b). Stratégie nationale de création et de gestion des aires marines protégées. Synthèse. Direction générale de l'aménagement du logement et de la nature. 24 p. http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/13148-1_brochure-resume-strategie-aires-marines.pdf

Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement Durable et de l'Energie - MEDDE (2016). Le cas par cas. <http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/Projets-de-travaux-d-ouvrages-ou-d.html>

Ministère de l'Aménagement du Territoire et de l'Environnement – MATE (2001). L'étude d'impact sur l'environnement. 153 p.

Moberg, Å. (1999). Environmental Systems Analysis Tools: Differences and Similarities. Institution for Systems Ecology. Stockholm University, Stockholm, 83 p.

Moberg, F., Folke, C. (1999). Ecological goods and services of coral reef ecosystems. Ecological Economics, 29:215–233.

Moreno-Mateos, D., Power, M.E., Comín, F.A., Yockteng, R. (2012). Structural and functional loss in restored wetland ecosystems. PLoS-Biology, 10(1), 45. <http://www.plosbiology.org/article/doi/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001247&representation=PDF>

Moseley, J.C. (1974). Texas' Liberty reef program. Proceedings of the International Conference on Artificial Reefs (Houston, Texas), 78-80.

Mumby, P.J. & Steneck, R.S. (2008). Coral reef management and conservation in light of rapidly evolving ecological paradigms. *Trends Ecol Evol.* 2008 Oct;23(10):555-63. doi: 10.1016/j.tree.2008.06.011. Epub 2008 Aug 21.

Musard, O., Le Dû-Blayo, L., Francour, P., Beurrier, J. P., Feunteun, E., Talassinis, L. (2014). Underwater Seascapes. Springer International Publishing. 291 p.

Nairri, O., Chabanet, P., Donal, T., Tourrand, C., Letourneur, Y. (2000). Regeneration of a reef flat ten years after the impact of the cyclone Firinga (Reunion, SW Indian Ocean). Proceedings of the Ninth International Coral Reef Symposium. Bali. Indonesia, 1.

Nedwell, J., Howell, D. (2004). A review of offshore windfarm related underwater noise sources. Collaborative Offshore Wind Energy Research into the Environment. Rap. 544 R 0308, Subacoustech Ltd. 57 p.

Neumann B, Vafeidis AT, Zimmermann J & R, N. (2015). Future Coastal Population Growth and Exposure to Sea-Level Rise and Coastal Flooding - A Global Assessment. PLoS ONE 10(3): e0118571. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0118571.

Nugranad, J., Chantrapornsilp, S., Varapibal, T. (2000). Feeding and spawning behaviour of the trumpet triton, *Charonia tritonis* (L., 1758) in captivity. Phuket Marine Biological Center Special Publication, 21:51-56

Obura, D. (2016). Guide de suivi du blanchissement des coraux Ouest de l'océan Indien - 2016 Compilé par David Obura. Projet Biodiversité, Commission de l'océan Indien - COI. 12 p.

Odum, E.P. (1974). The strategy of ecosystem development. *Science*, 164:262-270.

Office National de l'Eau et des Milieux Aquatiques - ONEMA (2015). Outre-mer : mise aux normes des stations d'épurations. <http://www.onema.fr/outre-mer-normes-stations-epurations>

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development - OECD (1993). Environment monographs N°83. OECD core set of indicators for environmental performance reviews. A synthesis report by the Group on the State of the Environment. Paris 1993. <http://www.fao.org/ag/againfo/programmes/en/lead/toolbox/Refer/gd93179.pdf>

Parcs Nationaux de France (2012). Les parcs nationaux français, territoires de référence. 7 p.

Pascal, N., Leport, G., Allenbach, M., Marchand, C., 2016a. Valeur économique des services rendus par les récifs coralliens et écosystèmes associés des Outre-mer français. Rapport technique pour l'Initiative Française pour les REcifs CORalliens (IFRECOR), 56 pages

Pascal, N., Allenbach, M., Brathwaite, A., Burke, L., Leport, G., Clua, E., 2016b. Economic valuation of coral reef ecosystem service of coastal protection: a pragmatic approach. Ecosystem Services. Volume 21, Part A, October 2016, Pages 72–80.

Pelletier, D., Leleu, K., Mallet, D., Mou-Tham, G., Hervé, G., Boureau, M., Guilpart, N. (2012). Remote high-definition rotating video enables fast spatial survey of marine underwater macrofauna and habitats. *Plos One*, 7(2), e30536.

Perrigault, M. (2010). Réhabilitation écologique d'un site de ponte de tortues marines à l'Étang-Salé [île de La Réunion]. Mise en place d'un suivi scientifique & Étude pour

optimiser le retour des pontes. Rapport de stage 2eme année – M2IEGB – Université de Montpellier II. 53 p + Annexes.

Pearce, D., Moran, D. (1994). The economic value of biodiversity . London: Earthscan. 104 p. <https://www.cbd.int/financial/values/g-economicvalue-iucn.pdf>

Pinault, M. (2013). Évaluation de la fonctionnalité de récifs artificiels à vocation non extractive, dans un contexte d'habitats naturels fragmentés – Côte nord-ouest de l'île de La Réunion. *Cybium*, 37:262. <http://sfi.mnhn.fr/cybium/numeros/2013/374/08-RT%20Pinault.pdf>

Pinault, M., Chabanet, P., Loiseau, N., Durville, P., Galizin, R., Quod, J.P. (2013). Influence des facteurs environnementaux sur la structure des peuplements ichthyologiques de l'île de La Réunion (Sud-Ouest de l'océan Indien). *Cybium*, 37:95-109.

Piton, B., Taquet, M. (1992). Océanographie physique des parages de l'île de La Réunion (océan Indien). Rapport scientifique ORSTOM. 40 p. http://horizon.documentation.ird.fr/exl-doc/pleins_textes/divers10-06/010025163.pdf

Point, P. (1998). La place de l'évaluation des biens environnementaux dans la décision publique. *Économie publique/Public economics*, 01:13-45.

Pomeroy, R.S., Parks, J.E., Watson, L.M. (2004). How is your MPA doing?: A Guidebook of Natural and Social Indicators for Evaluating Marine Protected Area Management Effectiveness, Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, United Kingdom, IUCN, 2004. 216 p.

Porcher, M., Job, S., Schrimm, M., Morancy, R. (2003). La restauration récifale, Guide pratique à l'usage des décideurs et aménageurs – Ministère de l'Ecologie et du Développement Durable, Proscience Te Turu'Ihi, IFRECOR Polynésie Française – Carex Environnement. 32 p. [http://www.2dattitude.org/ressources/bm/docs/043-La restauration récifale 1.pdf](http://www.2dattitude.org/ressources/bm/docs/043-La%20restauration%20recifale%201.pdf)

Quétier, F., Regnery, B., Levrel, H. (2014). No net loss of biodiversity or paper offsets? A critical review of the French no net loss policy. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 38:120-131.

Ramade, F. (2002) Dictionnaire encyclopédique de l'Ecologie et des sciences de l'environnement. 2e Edition, DUNOD. 1100 p.

Rameau, J.C., Gauberville, N., Drapier, N. (2000). Gestion forestière et diversité biologique. Institut pour le développement forestier. 117 p. https://books.google.com/books?id=KsX2INLJwtcC&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_g_e_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false

Raoul, D. (2010). Les effets sur la santé et l'environnement des champs électromagnétiques produits par les lignes à haute et très haute tension. Rapport n° 506 (2009-2010) fait au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques. 177 p. <http://www.senat.fr/rap/r09-506/r09-5061.pdf>

Rufray, V. (2013). Guide sur la prise en compte des milieux naturels dans les études d'impact en Guyane. Etude Biotope. 178 p.

Scherrer, B. (1984). Biostatistique. Gaëtan Morin Editeur, Boucherville. 850 p.

Scopélitis, J., Andréfouët, S., Phinn, S., Chabanet, P., Naim, O., Tourrand, C., Done, T. (2009). Changes of coral communities over 35 years: Integrating in situ and remote-

sensing data on Saint-Leu Reef (la Réunion, Indian Ocean). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 84:342-352.

Semple, S. (1997). Algal growth on two sections of a fringing coral reef subject to different levels of eutrophication in Reunion Island. *Oceanologica acta*, 20: 851-861.

Schmitt, E., Sluka, R., Sullivan-Sealey, K. (2002). Evaluating the use of roving diver and transect surveys to assess the coral reef fish assemblage off southeastern Hispaniola. *Coral Reefs*, 21:216-223.

Spalding, M., Ravilious, C., Green, E. P. (2001). World atlas of coral reefs. Berkeley (CA); University of California Press. 427 p.

Spataro, T. (2008). Définitions et mesure de la biodiversité. 24 p.

Stroud, R.H., Massmann, W.H. (1966). Artificial reefs as tools of sport fishery management in coastal marine waters. *Sport Fishing Institute (SFI) Bulletin*, 170:1-8.

Union des Aquaculteurs d'Outre-Mer – UAOM (2016). L'aquaculture dans l'outremer français : un potentiel insuffisamment considéré. Rapport UAOM. 2 p.

Vaissière, A.C., Levrel, H., Pioch, S., Carlier, A. (2014). Biodiversity offsets for offshore wind farm projects: The current situation in Europe. *Marine Policy*, 48:172-183.

Viederman, S., Meffe, G.K., Carroll, C.R. (1997). The Role of Institutions and Policymaking in Conservation. In *Principles of Conservation Biology*, 2nd ed. Meffe, G.K., Carroll, C.R. (Eds.), 779 p.

Wielgus, J., Chadwick-Furman, N., Dubinsky, Z., Shechter, M., Zeitouni, N. (2002). Dose-response modelling of recreationally important coral-reef attributes: a review and potential application to the economic valuation of damage. *Coral Reefs*, 21:253-259.

Wilkinson, C. (2008). Status of coral reefs of the world: 2008. Townsville (AUS), Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN) and Reef and Rainforest Research Centre (RRRC). 296 p.

Zann, L., Brodie, J., Berryman, C., Naqasima, M. (1987). Recruitment, ecology, growth and behavior of juvenile *Acanthaster planci* (L.) (Echinodermata: Asteroidea). *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 41:561-575.

6 Annexes

The following Annexes show examples from French Territories. They are primarily either projects subject to environmental impact assessment (EIA), impact assessment under the Water Law, or requiring a dossier Installation Classified for the Protection of the Environment.

6.1 INDUSTRIAL AND URBAN DISCHARGES

6.1.1 Industries (EIA, ICPE or Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Relatively poorly developed in French Overseas Territories, the industry is made up of different types of activities with a highly varied range of technical differences between projects. The agro-food industries (sugar, distilling, dairy products, drinks, etc.), construction (buildings and public works, art projects, housing, pipelines), and fossil fuels (coal, oil, gas) are those that are most developed overseas, mainly due to the choice of agricultural production and fast demographic growth in some territories. However, some industries, closely linked to the insular identity of territories (seawater desalination units), to constraints relating to waste disposal management (sorting, composting, incineration, recycling) or to the supply of fossil energies (renewable energies, biofuels), are developing rapidly.

Projects subject to EIA: Industrial activity is not specifically covered by the annex of the Environment Code's Article R. 122-2. However, it is directly regulated by the declaration and registration⁵⁷ or authorization procedures under nomenclature for Installations Classified for the Protection of the Environment [ICPE under its French acronym] (ministerial decrees relating to provisions applicable to ICPEs subject to declaration, registration and authorization – MEDDE, 2015a). This is divided into two categories: the use or storage of certain environmentally dangerous substances and the type of activity.

Thus industrial projects under the ICPE authorization plan (02/02/98) Decree relating to water extraction and consumption as well as all types of emissions of ICPEs subject to authorization) are this subject to an EIA. Those installations falling under registration requirements are subject to the procedure on a case-by-case basis procedure (Environment Code, section 1 of annex to Article R. 122-2). The EIA then falls under procedures specific to ICPEs and supplemented with a hazard assessment study which is one of the elements required in the application for authorization.

Furthermore, any system for the extraction of seawater (cooling systems, desalination units, holding tanks, etc.) is subject to the case-by-case procedure (section 15 of the same article).

Projects subject to impact assessment under the Water Law: According to section 2220 pertaining to Water Law nomenclature, discharges at sea with a total capacity in excess of 100,000 m³/j must be declared.

⁵⁷ The procedure to register installations classified for the protection of the environment is an intermediate regime between declaration and authorization and for which the procedure for the creation of certain types of projects (service stations, etc.) is subject to specific rules. This regime is the result of a cooperation aimed at refocusing State interventions on certain installations and to streamline procedures applicable to ICPEs (CCI Paris Ile-De-France, 2014).

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of buildings, machines and possible underwater structures (outlets).

- Direct effects: soil destabilization and erosion (soil runoff, organic matter, traces of agricultural fertilizers and/or different phytosanitary products); noise and light pollution; oil leaks and spills (hydraulic oils, motor oils, diesel fuel, industrial lubricants); dispersion of macro waste from construction sites in the case of heavy rainfall (rubble, metals, wood, isolation materials, etc.).
- Indirect effects: disturbance of maritime and motor vehicle transport during certain phases of works (noise, light, hydrocarbons).

Figure 37 Société Réunionnaise de Produits Pétroliers - SRPP (© M. Pinault)

Expected permanent effects: Operations and maintenance

- Direct effects: discharge of different substances according to industrial activity under scrutiny (see ICPE nomenclature – organic matter, hydrocarbons, nutrients, etc.), thermal anomalies (heated or cooled waters), saline anomalies (salinity increases or reductions), coverage of seabed and changes to hydro-sedimentary mechanisms (erosion, accretion, vortex, wave refraction, etc.) by possible underwater structures (outlets, pumps).
- Indirect effects: possible increase in road and maritime circulation due to supplies, deliveries, control or maintenance; possible development of other industries or infrastructures near the project and linked to it (processing and supply chains, etc.); installation of apartment complexes and residential areas for the industry's workers in the case of a project situated in an isolated area; etc.

6.1.2 Water treatment plants (EIA, ICPE or Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: French overseas territories are considerably behind as far as sanitation and even drinking water infrastructures are concerned. In fact less than half the population is connected to sewage network and infrastructure to deal with sewage is either faulty or non-existent, and frequently does not meet requirements of the urban wastewater directive. Although access to drinking water for all has benefitted from considerable efforts, a balance between territories has not yet been struck⁵⁸ (Onema, 2015).

⁵⁸ In 2009, the national office for water and aquatic environments (ONEMA) budgeted over 12 million euros for sewage treatment infrastructure in Mayotte, Guadeloupe, Martinique, Réunion and Guyane. Of a total of 18 projects, five involve construction, extension or rehabilitation of water treatment plants, eight involve sewage

Technically, a treatment plant includes one or several systems to extract different pollutants from the incoming sewage so that discharges do not harm the natural receiving environment. The succession of mechanisms (pre-, primary, secondary and tertiary treatment) is calculated according to the type of water collected within the network and the type of pollutants to be treated. These waters can be of urban, industrial or agricultural origin. Treatment plants can be designed to treat only urban wastewater or both urban and industrial wastewater.

Projects subject to EIAs: Water treatment plants or extensions are subject to an EIA when the project is subject to authorization under the Water Law (section 20 of annex to Article L. 146-4-III of the Urban Code, within the 50 steps (“50 pas”) coastal strip under Article L. 156-2 and L-711-3-II of the Urban Code, or in an outstanding coastal area under Article L. 146-6 of the Urban Code are subject to the procedure on a case-by-case basis.

Water treatment installations or extensions for solely treating industrial or agricultural wastewater or for treating both urban and industrial wastewater and subject to authorization under ICPEs⁵⁹ are also subject to an EIA (Environment Code, section 1 of annex to Article R. 122-2). This is laid down in specific procedures relating to ICPEs and should be completed with a hazard assessment study.

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Under section 2110 water treatments plants of metropolitan areas require authorization when having to treat gross loads of organic pollution ≥ 600 kg of BOD₅⁶⁰, according to Article 2224-6 of the General Local Authorities Code. Those installations with a gross load in excess of 12 kg but less than or equal to 600 kg of BOD₅ are subject to a declaration.

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of buildings, basins and possibly underwater structures (outlets):

- Direct effects: soil destabilization and erosion, noise and light pollution; oil leaks and spills, dispersion of macro waste from construction sites in the case of heavy rainfall.
- Indirect effects: possible disruption of maritime and vehicle traffic during certain work phases.

Expected permanent effects: Exploitation et maintenance

- Direct effects: domestic discharges (organic matter, macro waste matter, faecal bacteria, detergents, etc.), possible industrial pollution and that emanating from animal husbandry (See ICPE nomenclature – hydrocarbons, nutrients, heavy metals, etc.), saline anomalies (desalination), coverage of seabed and changes to hydro-sedimentary mechanisms by possible underwater structures
- Indirect effects: possible spread of urban sprawl (joint development zone [ZAC under its French acronym], housing development) relatively close to water

collection networks, and five involve feasibility studies or analyses of water treatments plants. These projects complement 12 investments made in 2008, of which three were completed in 2009 (Onema, 2015).

⁵⁹ See Decree of 02/02/98 relating to extractions and consumption of water as well as all types of emissions of ICPEs subject to authorization. Installations or extensions to water treatment plants for treating only urban wastewater do not fall under ICPE nomenclature.

⁶⁰ The biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is the quantity of oxygen necessary to biologically oxidize biodegradable organic by bacterial action. This enables an evaluation of the biodegradable fraction of the carbonaceous pollutant load of wastewater. This is usually calculated after a five-day period at 20°C in the dark, hence the reference to BOD₅.

treatment plant; linking up wastewater pipelines; repositories and recovery of purification sludges (amendment, spreading, etc.).

Figure 38 Saint Joseph wastewater treatment plant - La Réunion (© Sogea)

6.1.3 Rainwater outlets (Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Storm events and torrential rains are frequent in tropical areas, particularly in the cyclone season. If rainwaters are natural, the effects of their erosion on arable lands, leaching, transport and runoff as well piping to a network of outlets are largely changed by human activity (clearing, aggressive agricultural practices, development works, sealing of soils, land-use planning, etc.).

Rainwater outlets can be complemented with settling tanks, linked to treatment plants or, on the contrary, serve as outlets for wastewaters that may or may not have been treated. The possible outflow of such outlets in coastal areas that were not naturally exposed to such quantities of fresh water and loaded with multiple pollutants and contaminants, can have catastrophic ecological consequences, particularly in the case of coral ecosystems (Letourneur et al., 1993, Nairri et al., 2000; Scopéltis et al., 2009).

Projects subject to EIAs: There is no specific mention of this type of project in the list of works and developments defined by Article R 122-2 of the Environment Code. It thus appears an EIA is not obligatory in the case of rainwater outlets.

Projects subject to an impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 2120, stormwater overflows that form part of a wastewater collection system with a BOD₅ daily pollutant flow ≥ 600 kg are subject to authorization. They are subject to declaration if the flow ≥ 12 kg but is less than or equal to 600 kg of BOD₅.

Expected temporary effects: Installation of pipelines

- Direct effects: soil destabilization and erosion; noise and light pollution; oil leaks and spills.
- Indirect effects: possible disruption of road traffic during certain work phases.

Figure 39 Rainwater outlets at Saint Gilles port - La Réunion (© M. Pinault)

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: worsening of runoff and surface washing in urban and agricultural areas located upstream from piping system (soil runoff, organic matter, macro waste, bacteria, hydrocarbons, nutrients, phytosanitary products, etc.), saline anomalies (desalinated water).
- Indirect effects: possible increase in vehicle traffic (safeguarding roadways in the face of flooding or seasonal submersion of aprons) or urban sprawl (integration of project as part of a larger development project: Joint Development Zone, housing development, etc.) once works have terminated.

6.2 COASTAL WORKS, PROJECTS OR SCHEMES

6.2.1 Coastal urbanization (EIA)

Brief description: Topographic constraints (craggy islands) and historic reasons linked to the colonization of overseas communities (defence, commerce, fishing, transport, etc.) have focused demographic and urban development close to the coast (Fig. 4). Increasing the density of the largest cities to limit urban sprawl is a challenge.

According to Klein (2003), the mixed results in the protection of coastlines under pressure from urbanization in overseas territories are reflected in three choices: 1) the priority given to metropolises, 2) arbitration in favour of developing coastlines to the detriment of their protection; and 3) insufficient policies to be rigorously applied with regard to local, economic, social, cultural and political contexts.

The consequences of these choices can be attributed to individual projects, but also to the cumulative effects of the interaction of projects that was supposed to have been considered when drawing up development strategies⁶¹ and framework documents for land valuation. In the face of such territorial inconsistencies, regulations relating to impact assessments alone cannot ensure the implementation of controlled urbanization and are often limited to the study of the direct effects of individual projects without effectively taking into account indirect and cumulated effects with other known projects.

Projects subject to EIAs: In accordance with sections 11 and 33–40 of annex to Article R. 122-2 of the Environment Code, the following projects are subject to an EIA or the case-by-case procedure⁶²: 1) all works, projects and schemes carried out in outstanding coastal areas⁶³, 2) jointly planned areas, permits to develop and subdivide an area equal to or exceeding five hectares or creating a floor area equal to or $\geq 10,000 \text{ m}^2$, 3) works or constructions creating a floor area equal to or $\geq 10,000 \text{ m}^2$, 4) cultural, sports or recreational facilities with a capacity for more than 1,000 people, and 5) any project subject to an EIA under the territorial coherence programme [SCOT under its French acronym].

Expected temporary effects: Terracing, servicing requirements and construction

⁶¹ Wherein lies the notion of "work programme" taking place within the same territory over a reduced time period and comprising several interdependent projects.

⁶² On the site of a community with, on the date of the submission of the request, a local development plan [PLU, under its French acronym] or a municipal map, and that has not be the subject of an EIA. Otherwise, see sections 33-40 of the annex to Article 122-2 of the Environment Code.

⁶³ The following small developments can be located on outstanding areas along the coast on condition their placement and features do not alter the character of sites, they do not compromise the architectural and landscaping qualities or compromise environmental conservation: 1) parking areas necessary for the control of vehicle use and to prevent degradation of these spaces by limiting irregular parking, without it causing an increase in effective parking capacities, on condition that these areas are not cemented or asphalted and that no other siting be possible; and 2) apart from any type of accommodation, in fishing areas, marine or lake fish farm, shellfish farming, salt production areas or sheep farming in salt marshes, the constructions and developments requiring the close proximity to water related to activities traditionally located in these areas, on condition that their siting be indispensable due to technical requirements (sections b and d of Article R 146-2 of the Town Planning Code).

- Direct effects: soil destabilization and erosion; noise and light pollution; oil leaks and spills; dispersion of macro waste from the work site in the case of heavy rainfall.
- Indirect effects: possible disruption of motor traffic during some work phases.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: runoff and surface washing of areas that are covered and asphalted (organic matter, macro waste, bacteria, hydrocarbons, etc.), swimming pool overflow and upkeep (chlorine, detergents, desalinated water), development and maintenance of green areas (soil runoff, fertilizer, phytosanitary products).
- Indirect effects: probable increase in road traffic (abandonment and supply of new housing or collective structures), widening or the creation of new transport infrastructure (roads, roundabouts, bridges, covered roads, etc.) and sanitation (connection to collective sanitation systems, pumping station or water treatment plants, etc.), creation of services and associated buildings (schools, kindergartens, commerce, etc.).

Figure 40 Urbanisation of Roches Noires coast – La Réunion (© M. Pinault)

6.2.2 Ports and port installations (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Large maritime ports overseas are located in highly strategic sites due to their role in supplying islands with imported products (petrol, food, materials, vehicles, etc.). They are often large in comparison to the surface area of territories supplied. They are also frequently old and the majority of current work involves deepening, extensions to bodies of water, lengthening of wharves or dredging sediments.

On the other hand, marinas, fishing ports and coastal shelters generally involve smaller structures, but new ones are still considered for future development projects over the next few years. Projects can also involve extensions, sometimes situated in reef areas (see port of Saint-Leu in La Réunion).

Projects subject to EIAs: Every port and installation developed in the PMD, including fishing ports, is subject to an EIA (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, annex section 10, a-d).

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: All works involving the creation of a maritime port or an access channel or technical modifications to an existing access channel (section 4410), as well as all port development works (extensions to bodies of water) and other works carried out in contact with the marine environment and having a direct impact on it⁶⁴ for a sum equal to or $\geq 1,900,000$ euros (section 4120) are subject to authorization. Those port developments involving a sum $\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros are subject to a declaration.

Expected temporary effects: Port excavations and developments

- Direct effects: release of turbid plumes and deposition of particulate matter some distance away during excavations (materials of terrigenous origin, organic matter, pollutants and contaminants potentially found in the soil), noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills (work site machines), dispersion of macro waste from the work site with heavy rainfall.
- Indirect effects: Disturbance of maritime and vehicular traffic during all works.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: runoff and washing of surfaces that are covered and asphalted (organic matter, nutrients, macro waste, bacteria, hydrocarbons, etc.), depositing and re-suspension of silt within the port (ships, dredging), noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills (ships, gantries, projectors, lifting gear, etc.), covering of seabed, artificialization of coast, rupture of ecological continuity and modifications to hydro-sedimentary mechanisms with the construction of dykes, exposures and wave-breaking devices.
- Indirect effects: increase in maritime (more and/or larger ships) and road (delivery lorries, lifting gear, etc.), creation or expansion of industrial installations, processing and storage facilities (industrial-port complex), creation or extension of transport infrastructure (roads, roundabouts, bridges, covered pavements, etc.), and wastewater infrastructure (connection of industrial installations to collective sewage systems, pumping stations or treatment plants, etc.), modification of maritime routes, increased pressure on fisheries (sport and professional), contamination or release of potentially invasive exotic species (ballast water, containers, fouling), increased need within region for imported products.

⁶⁴ The types of development projects and works under section 4120 of the Water Law nomenclature are particularly those that appear in the annex to the Decree of 23 February 2001 (version consolidated on 8 July 2015), laying down the general principles applicable to port development works and other works carried out in contact with the marine environment subject to declaration. This list comprises: access channels and outports (underwater works), external works (causeways and protecting structures; calibration works; shoreline protection, ripraps, banks; beach nourishment), access locks, pumping stations (civil engineering, including defenses and terraces; gates and valves; longitudinal control dams), static or mobile bridges (foundations; civil engineering and including defenses and terraces), inland bodies of water (protection of shorelines and sea floor; infilling; extension of bodies of water), mooring works and development of neighbouring shores (docks; wharfs; shore protection, ripraps, banks), naval repair installations (dry docks; launching docks; careening areas) and other works (artificial reefs; submerged cables and pipelines, etc.).

Figure 41 Large maritime port of La Réunion (© M. Pinault)

6.2.3 Airports and aerodromes (EIA)

Brief description: As in the case of large maritime ports, overseas airports are strategic sites due to their role in supplying manufactured products and transporting passengers. National commitments to territorial continuity with overseas regions and tourist development has required the creation or expansion of numerous airports to receive large aircraft that are able to travel large distances with or without few stopovers from the mainland. The small size and mountainous nature of many island territories requires locating many overseas airports on the coasts.

These two characteristics (long runways and coastal location) sometimes require runways to be extended into the sea (Mayotte) and/or the protection of their surroundings with large-scale embankments (La Réunion). This section only specifies expected effects on coral reef ecosystems caused by the creation and expansion of airports, in the strict sense of the term.

Projects subject to EIAs: Every airport, aerodrome or runway installation is subject to an EIA (Environment Code, Article R.122-2, annex sections 9, a-c), particularly contemplating a prospective analysis of urban development and energy consumption as well as effects of these processes on the environment. Protective measures against sonic pollution are also required, and are required under Articles R. 571-44 to R. 571-52 of the Environment Code.

Expected temporary effects: Development, extension of runways and construction of buildings.

- Direct effects: destabilization and erosion of soils, noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills (motors on the building site), dispersion of macro waste from the building site with heavy rain.
- Indirect effects: modification of air traffic and possible disruption of vehicle traffic during certain phases of work.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: runoff and washing of surfaces that are covered and asphalted (hydrocarbons, tyre debris, metallic residues, heavy metals, etc.), noise and light

pollution (aircraft, projectors, passenger, security and fire fighting vehicles, etc.), covering of seabed, loss of the natural environment, rupture of ecological continuity and modifications to hydro-sedimentary mechanisms with possible exposure and wave-breaking devices.

- Indirect effects: increase in air traffic (more and/or larger aircraft, creation or enlargement of transport infrastructure (roads, roundabouts, bridges, covered pavements, etc.) and tourism (hotels, commerce, services), increase of local requirements for fuel (aviation fuel) and imported products.

Figure 42 Dzaoudzi-Pamandzi airport - Mayotte (© B. Janis)

6.2.4 Road infrastructure (EIA)

Brief description: The mountainous nature of overseas island territories and the historic infrastructure of the largest towns in coastal areas (defence, commerce, fishing, transport, etc.) have contributed to at least one main coastal ring road in the majority of territories. These roads thus cross certain natural coastal areas, particularly mangroves and wetlands, that can extend over vast areas. Some works may also be built directly offshore involving the construction of sea walls or causeways. As in the case of airports, this heading only specifies expected effects generated by the creation and extension of roads, deviations and roundabouts.

Projects subject to EIAs: Substantial construction, modifications or extensions to road infrastructure exceeding three kilometres are subject to EIAs. Non-substantial modifications or extensions to motorways and expressways, including interchanges, and roads less than three kilometres long are subject to the case-by-case procedure (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, annex section 6, a-d). As in the case of airports, the EIA must comply with specific procedures relating to transport infrastructure (Environment Code, Article R. 122-5), integrating a prospective analysis and measures to protect against noise pollution.

Expected temporary effects: Infrastructural development or expansion

- Direct effects: soil destabilization and erosion; noise and light pollution; oil leaks and spills; dispersion of macro waste from work sites with heavy rain.
- Indirect effects: traffic disruption during certain work phases.

Figure 43 Western access of the new coastal road - La Réunion (© M. Pinault)

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: runoff and washing of asphalted surfaces (hydrocarbons, tyre debris, macro waste, organic matter, heavy metal, bacteria, etc.), noise and light pollution (motors, headlights, warning lights, vibrations, etc.)
- Indirect effects: increase in vehicle traffic (fluidisation of traffic, transport arrangements favouring vehicles and lorries, etc.), property development and increase in urban sprawl, creation of associated services and buildings (schools, kindergartens, commerce, etc.).

6.2.5 Bridges, causeways, tunnels and covered cuts (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Structures related to communication routes mainly include overhead structures (bridges and causeways) and underground works (tunnels). These works are numerous in overseas territories, whether they are for crossing topographic obstacles (canyons, rivers, ravines, mountains, isthmuses, etc.) or inlets (bays, lagoons, causeways). These sites are all characterized by their extreme sensitivity to erosion and phenomena involving the transport of sediments. Construction works often involve the building of abutments, piers or the drilling of tunnels and cuttings that are likely to considerably increase the sensitivity of the sites in question. In addition, the sinking of piers in river beds or shallow seabeds can have considerable consequences as far as sediment disturbance is concerned.

Projects subject to EIAs: Works involving the construction of bridges with a length ≥ 100 metres, and tunnels and covered cuts ≥ 300 metres in length are subject to an EIA. Below the respective lengths, projects are subject to the case-by-case procedure (Environment Code, Article 122-2, annex section 7). Projects subject to EIAs are also covered by procedures specific to transport infrastructure (Environment Code, Article R. 122-5) integrating a prospective analysis and protective measures against noise pollution.

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, the building of bridges or causeways offshore is subject to authorization ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros or declaration ($\geq 160\,000$ euros but $< 1\,900\,000$ euros) procedures regarding port development works and other projects carried out in contact with and having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Development or extension of infrastructure

- Direct effects: soil destabilization, drilling, storage and erosion; sound and light pollution; oil leaks and spills; dispersion of micro waste from work site with heavy rain.
- Indirect effects: disruption of vehicle traffic during certain work phases.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: runoff and washing of asphalted surfaces (hydrocarbons, tyre debris, macro waste, organic matter, heavy metals, bacteria, etc.), noise and light pollution (motors, headlights, warning lights, vibrations, etc.)
- Indirect effects: increase of vehicle traffic (fluidisation of traffic, strategic choices in favour of vehicles and lorries, etc.), property development and increase in urban sprawl, creation of services and buildings (schools, kindergartens, commerce, etc.).

Figure 44 : Saint Leu causeway on the Route des Tamarins - La Réunion (© M. Pinault)

6.2.6 Sea walls, breakwaters, jetties and exposures (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Structures protecting the coast, particularly against wave action are characterized by the installation of modular structures to break waves without the transport of sedimentary materials. Reclaimed areas consist of reclaiming and converting land through the immersion of a variety of different terrigenous materials (rocks, gravel, sand, etc.). These reclaimed areas (or reclamation) are usually bordered with coastal protection structures so as to protect their perimeters from the elements. These works are frequently used in the stabilization of coastal infrastructures (ports, airports, roads, etc.), extending activities towards the sea (lengthening of runways, causeways, extension of industrial-port areas, etc.) and, more modestly, in creating bathing areas in the sea. This introduction of artificial structures can result in breaks in

ecological continuity, the destruction of nursery areas or changes in sediment transport processes.

Projects subject to EIAs: Construction, extensions or reconstruction work and coastal developments aimed at preventing erosion; maritime works that may change the coastline through the construction particularly of sea walls, jetties, and other works protecting against the sea and recovering land within the public maritime domain with a footprint equal to or $\geq 2,000 \text{ m}^2$ are subject to an EIA. Construction, extensions, renovations and recovery of lands with a total footprint less than $2,000 \text{ m}^2$ are subject to a case-by-case procedure (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, annex section 10, e and f).

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, works protecting shores, ripraps, banks and sea walls are subject to authorization ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration ($\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) procedures relating to port development works and other works carried out in contact with or having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Construction of protection devices

- Direct effects: liberation of turbid plumes and the deposition of particulate matter during phases of reclamation and the artificial coastline (terrigenous materials, organic matter, pollutants and contaminants potentially found in the soil), noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills, dispersion of macro waste on the site with heavy rains.
- Indirect effects: possible disruption of maritime traffic during some work phases.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: coverage of sea floor, artificial coastline, breakdown of ecological continuity and changes to hydro-sedimentary mechanisms through the construction of sea walls, reclaimed areas and wave protection devices, the generation of turbid plumes and the deposition of particulate matter during the phases involving the refilling of sea walls with modules to protect the coastline (acropods, tetrapods, grooved cubic blocks, etc.)
- Indirect effects: extension of the urban sprawl or industrial activities towards coastal areas.

Figure 45 Reclamation of Pointe des Galets – La Réunion (© IPR)

6.2.7 Underwater pipelines (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Underwater pipelines are made up of lines of different diameters and materials (metal, plastic, concrete, composites, resins, etc.) from the landing area to the extremities of the pipeline (submersion and emergence area), bolts and stabilizers on the seabed. These bolts can also be fixed directly in the rock. The pipeline can also be buried or installed in a furrow on the seabed in some stretches. The different types of fluids at the temperatures at which they are transported will define the type of evaluation to which the project will be subjected.

Projects subject to EIAs: In accordance with sections 18, and 29-32 of the annex to Article R. 122-2 of the Environment Code, the following types of project are subject to an EIA or the case-by-case procedure: 1) aqueduct installations or drinking water pipelines; 2) hot water pipelines; 3) pipelines transporting water vapour or superheated water; 4) pipelines for the transport of inflammable, toxic or noxious gases, of carbon dioxide, and 5) pipelines for the transport of other fluids for which the extrapolation of the external diameter prior to coating by the length is \geq or equal to 500, 5,000, 2,000, 500 and 2,000 m^2 respectively, according to the nature of the fluid transported, or if the length exceeds 2 kilometres.

Projects subject to impact assessments under Water Law: Pursuant to item 3330, piping transporting liquid hydrocarbons or chemical products for distances exceeding 5 kilometres, or if the result of the external diameter times the length $\geq 2,000 \text{ m}^2$ are subject to authorisation.

According to item 4120, underwater pipelines are also subject to authorization ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration ($\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) procedures in the case of port development works and other structures built in contact with or having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of underwater structures (piping, staples, cable landings points, etc.).

- Direct effects: mechanical degradation by organisms adhering to the course of the pipeline, under the staples and covered by the cable landing, noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills, deposit of macro waste from the underwater work site.
- Indirect effects: possible disruption of maritime traffic during work phases.

Figure 46 Deployment of underwater piping (© Nord Stream)

Expected permanent effects: Operation and maintenance

- Direct effects: intentional discharges (e.g. dispersion of an effluent), leaks and losses of fluids carried by the pipeline (hot water, fresh water, hydrocarbons, chemical products, etc.), modification of the thermal and/or chemical structure of the water column, modification of hydro-sedimentary mechanisms through the presence of underwater structures, reduction of tourism potential (diving) of the sites crossed by the pipeline (degradation and artificialisation of landscape).
- Indirect effects: connection works and possible development of domestic and/or industrial activity either side either end of the pipeline, changes to maritime routes and the banning of anchoring near the pipeline.

6.2.8 Underwater cables (Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: An underwater cable is a cable placed on the seafloor for telecommunications or power lines. They are installed and maintained by cable-laying vessels after a process of bathymetric reconnaissance. In shallow areas, and when the seabed permits, cables can be embedded with the aid of a marine tool such as a hollow mould-board plough so as to reduce navigational risks (fishing, anchoring). Telecommunications cables usually have a 69 mm diameter and weigh about 10 kg/m, even if lighter and finer cables are used in sections of deeper waters (Miller et al., 2011). Power cables can reach a diameter of 350 mm and a weight of 130 kg/m (in the case of extra-high voltage – EHV).

The risks of environmental damage associated with the submersion of underwater cables are mainly distinguished from underwater pipelines by their small diameter, their shallow embedding (enhancement of maintenance constraints) and the absence of a risk of spills. However, heat and electromagnetic fields, that increase with the intensity of the voltage, are also emitted by operational power cables. Little is known about the real impact of these fields on organisms (Raoul, 2010).

Projects subject to EIAs: There is no explicit entry for this type of project under the list of works, projects or schemes defined by the Environment Code's Article R. 122-2. The carrying out of an EIA of the submersion of cables would thus appear not to be compulsory.

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, underwater cables are however subject to authorization ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration ($\geq 160\,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) procedures in the case of port development works and other structures built in contact with or having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Cable submersion and recovery

- Direct effects: mechanical degradation with organisms adhering to the course of the pipeline that is simply placed or embedded (on the seabed), noise pollution, vibrations and turbid plumes caused by the plough, leaks and spills of hydraulic oils.
- Indirect effects: possible disruption of maritime traffic during certain work phases.

Figure 47 Deployment of an EDF cable between Saint Denis and La Possession – La Réunion (© IPR)

Expected permanent effects: Operation and maintenance

- Direct effects: heat generation and electromagnetic fields by operational electric cables, modification of hydro-sedimentary mechanisms due to the presence of underwater structures (especially by the thickest cables or those covered with protection or fixing devices), possible landscape degradation, mainly at the cable's extremities (landing areas).
- Indirect effects: connection works and possible development of domestic and/or industrial activity at either end of the underwater cable, changes to maritime routes and the banning of anchoring in close proximity to the cables.

6.2.9 Anchor buoys, beacons and light equipment offshore (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Anchor buoys are permanent anchorage points comprising a floating device (buoy or container), maintained in a fixed position by a dead body (concrete block, riprap), a plate or a screw anchor (helicoidal anchor screwed into the sediment), in a sheltered location. This mooring can be reserved for visiting vessels or belong to an individual or a shipping company. They can be moveable or situated within a port and used for specific purposes (fishing, diving, transfers, etc.).

In the maritime field, tagging (balisage) covers all marks or fixed or floating buoys placed offshore or onshore that signal dangers, regulations (limits of PMAs) and the layout of channels to ports and shelter. Other light devices offshore, such as water lines, beach protection nets, or suspended matter nets are also anchored more or less permanently to the substrate and require procedures relating to the occupation of the PMD.

Projects subject to EIAs: All anchorages, buoys and light equipment installed in outstanding areas along the coast are subject to the case-by-case procedure. They must absolutely be: 1) light devices, 2) necessary for fishing, shell fishing and marine aquaculture, and 3) need to be in the direct vicinity of water. In addition, their localisation and their appearance should not undermine the nature of the site, compromise the quality of architectural or landscape features or disrupt the environment (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, annex section 11).

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, anchorages, buoys and light equipment offshore are subject to authorization ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration ($\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) procedures in

the case of port development works and other structures built in contact with or having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of offshore devices

- Direct effects: mechanical degradation by organisms fixed to the underwater devices (sinker, plate, screw anchor), noise pollution and vibrations (if drilling or beating is necessary), deposit of macro waste from the underwater work site.
- Indirect effects: disruption of maritime traffic during certain work phases.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: eventual degradation of the coastal and underwater landscapes, effect of fish aggregating devices (FADs), possible submerged structures, possible mechanical degradation by benthic organisms due to the deterioration of nearby devices on the seabed (chains, sinkers, metal stakes, shackles, buoys, containers, etc.), introduction or propagation of exotic species (fixed to the hulls, anchors, in ballast water), pollution from wastewater and sewage, and by anti-fouling coatings.
- Indirect effects: increase in maritime activity (pleasure crafts, diving, cabotage), risk of vessels colliding with devices (specially in the absence of a flashing light), possible increase in pressure on fishing (FAD effect, anchoring), reduced impact of vessels' anchors on seabed (due to mooring devices).

Figure 48 Marker buoy in the Passe en S Marine Reserve- Mayotte (© J. Wickel)

6.2.10 Beach nourishment works (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: regeneration with sand, or beach nourishment, describes a process whereby sand is pulverised to replace sediments (generally sand) lost due to erosion. Beach nourishment is one way to protect the shores: a wider beach can reduce damage from storms, by dissipating energy in the wave area and protecting adjacent buildings and lands. It also enables a beach having lost its tourist potential to be returned to its original state (foreshortening, appearance of the underlying bedrock, etc.). The sand for

nourishment can be taken from adjacent areas (at greater depth or downstream) and other marine sites, or else materials from quarries or rubble can be used (e.g. recycling of products from the demolition of concrete buildings).

Projects subject to EIAs: Beach nourishment works involving a volume equal to or above 10,000 m³ are subject to an EIA. Works involving a volume below 10,000 m³ are subject to the case-by-case procedure (Environment Code, Article 122-2, Annex, section 10 h).

Projects subject to impact assessment under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, beach nourishments are subject to authorization (≥ 1,900,000 euros) or declaration (≥ 160,000 euros but < 1,900,000 euros) procedures in the case of port developments and other works in direct contact with and having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Figure 49 Beach nourishment in French Polynesia (© M. Valigursky)

Expected temporary effects: Beach nourishment

- Direct effects: mechanical covering of benthic organisms on the nourishment site, noise and light pollution, turbid plumes (when the unloaded sand has fine particulate matter or "coral soup"), possible microbial pollution or introduction of pathogens contained in imported sediments, changes in beach composition due to imported sand (chemistry, grain size, etc.), disturbance of the place of extraction (change in the slope, destabilization of the coast).
- Indirect effects: disruption of all resort activities during all works.

Expected permanent effects: Use

- Direct effects: possible hardening of imported sand, profound changes to the original ecosystem with a structural reorganization towards a new balanced state (phase shift).

- Indirect effects: increase in the number and diversity of resort activities, attempts to reduce erosion can give a false sense of stability and thus increase urban development along the coast.

6.3 PROSPECTION, EXTRACTION AND STORAGE OF MATERIALS FROM QUARRIES, MINES AND DREDGES

6.3.1 Quarries and mines (EIA, ICPEs or Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: A quarry is a place from which construction materials are extracted, such as stone, sand or other non-metallic or carboniferous minerals. The work site is in the open air, either on a hillside or in a pit. Quarries can be underground or underwater (dredging of materials). They involve the extraction of loose rocks (scree, alluvium) or solid rocks (consolidated sedimentary rocks [limestone and sandstone], eruptive and metamorphic (slates, granites, porphyries, gneiss, amphibolites, quartzites, schists, basalts, etc.]) (ENCCEM, 2011).

The term "quarry" also applies to a complete industrial complex that includes the extraction site of gravel (unsorted primary materials), storage sheds, and workshops where blocks of rock are cut and shaped. The difference between a mine and quarry depends on the type of material extracted (strategic or precious in the case of mines, and of lesser value in the case of quarries).

Projects subject to EIAs: All quarry operations (loose or solid rocks) are subject to EIAs within the framework of authorization procedures for ICPEs (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, annex item 1). This is subject to specific ICPE procedures and should be complemented with a hazard assessment study.

The following activities are also subject to EIAs: 1) prospection works other than for liquid or gaseous hydrocarbons when works cause a total earthworks involving a volume $\geq 20,000 \text{ m}^3$, cause the breaking up of some subsoil layers, or have to be carried out in wetlands or marshes; and 2) mine operations involving substances indicated under Article L. 111-1 of the Mining Code, as well as waste piles and dumps not covered by Article L. 335-1 of the Mining Code, except in the case of operating permits granted in overseas departments under Section 24, items a and b Article L. 611-3 of the Mining Code.⁶⁵

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to items 5140 and 5160, mine prospection covered by item 2, Article 3 of Decree 2006-649 of 2 June 2006, as well as mining operations not covered by operations mentioned under Article 21 of the Mining Code, are subject to authorization. Mining prospectings covered by Decree 2006-649, with the exception of Article 3, item 2, as well as mining operations carried out within the framework of the operational permit granted under Article 21 of the Mining Code are subject to declaration.

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of installations

- Direct effects: soil destabilization and erosion, changes to the slope, noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills, dispersion of macro waste on the work site with heavy rain.

⁶⁵ Apart from concessions or exploitations by the State mentioned under Article L. 131-1 of the Mining Code, in overseas departments, mines, except those involving liquid or gaseous hydrocarbons, can also be exploited with an exploitation authorization or permit. The instrument conferring the exploitation authorization grants the holder, within the established limits, exclusive rights to undertake all prospection and exploitation of substances mentioned therein. However, neither authorisations to exploit seabeds can be granted nor exploitation permits on the continental plateau or within the exclusive economic zone (Mining Code, Article L. 611-3).

- Indirect effects: disruption of motor traffic during certain work phases.

Figure 50 Coastal quarry at La Saline - La Réunion
(© M. Pinault)

Expected permanent effects: Exploitation and maintenance

- Direct effects: noise and sound pollution, and vibrations (mine blasting, lorry transport, crushing equipment, noise of rocks falling into empty lorries, back-up warning alarms, etc.), generation and settling of dust from rocks (movement of machines, crushing and grading, etc.), oil leaks and spills (lorries, machines, thermal divides, etc.).
- Indirect effects: heavy increase in lorry traffic on existing road infrastructures or on new detours for the transport of materials, possible link between the start-up of the quarry and the implementation of a large public works project (causeway, bridge, suspended roads, etc.)

6.3.2 Dredging of materials (EIA, Water Law impact assessment)

Brief description: Dredging is the process involving the extraction of materials situated on the bottom of a body of water. Objectives include ensuring river or maritime channels used by vessels are kept free from sediment, carrying out embankment operations for beach nourishment or land reclamation, working on port engineering projects (digging tanks or channels), or extracting marine aggregates (quarries) for the building sector.

Dredged products are usually stored on land in prepared areas or disposed at sea (piling), usually within defined parameters. When sediments are extracted from areas with high concentrations of industrial or port activities they can be highly polluted by heavy metals. For these reasons, as well as to control the impact of dredging on the environment in a broader sense, dredging activity is rigorously monitored.

In order to avoid redundancy with other previously described activities, this section focuses mainly on dredging carried out for port maintenance and storage on land of dredged sediments. Records relating to sediment extraction and the storage of materials (storage sheds, and transit installations) must be appraised separately.

Projects subject to EIAs: Dredging works and/or discharges relating to the marine environment and subject to authorization under the Water Law are subject to an EIA (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, Annex, section 21 a).

Furthermore, any operation to recover sediments must include a transitional management phase on shore. The development of transit installations (provisional storing areas of sediments on land) for such purposes is thus indispensable. Installations

with a storage capacity above 1,000 m³ are subject to authorization under ICPEs. They thus require an EIA that is supplemented by a hazard assessment study.

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4130, projects related to the marine environment require authorisations for dredging and/or discharges: 1) when the content of extracted sediments exceeds or is equal to reference level N2⁶⁶ for at least one of the elements therein; 2) in which the content of extracted elements falls between reference levels N1 and N2 for one of the elements therein and for which the maximum volume dredged *in situ* over 12 consecutive months exceeds or is equal to 5,000 m³; and 3) in which the content of extracted sediments is below or equal to reference level N1 for all elements therein but for which the dredged maximum volume *in situ* over 12 consecutive months is \geq or equal to 500,000 m³.

Dredging and/or discharges in the marine environment are subject to declarations: 1) when the content of extracted sediments falls between reference levels N1 and N2 for one of the elements therein and when the dredged maximum volume *in situ* over 12 consecutive months is less than 5,000 m³; 2) when the content of extracted sediments is less than or equal to reference level N1 for all elements therein but for which the dredged volume *in situ* over 12 consecutive months is \geq or equal to 500m³ and less than 500,000 m³, or when the discharge is situated less than one kilometre from a mollusc or marine fish farming area.

Expected temporary effects:

- Direct effects: dispersion of turbid plumes and hyper-sedimentation (terrigenous materials, organic matter, pollutants and contaminants potentially contained in the sediments), noise and light pollution, oil leaks and spills (dredgers), destruction of sedimentary ecosystems by dredging, mechanical covering of benthic organisms present on the piling site.
- Indirect effects: disruption of maritime traffic during certain work phases.

Figure 51 Dredging materials in the Pointe des Galets port - La Réunion (© M. Pinault)

⁶⁶ The reference levels R1, R2, S1, N1 and N2, to be considered together with the conditions for exemption are established by joint decree between the ministers holding responsibility for the sea and the environment of 9 August 2006 relating to levels to be considered in analysing discharges in surface waters or marine and estuary sediments, under headings 2230, 4130 and 3210 of Water Law nomenclature.

6.4 EXPLOITATION OF RENEWABLE NATURAL RESOURCES

6.4.1 Creation or extension of artificial reefs (EIA, impact assessment under Water Law)

Brief description: The term artificial reef includes "all physical layout of coastal marine seabeds for the establishment of hard substrates of diverse origins such as boulders, different types of industrial waste or specially manufactured groups of objects, etc." (Duval and Duclerc, 1986). The potential offered by the submersion of artificial reefs can involve fields as varied as the protection of habitats against trawling, the development of fisheries, economic profitability, biodiversity conservation or ecological knowledge, and particularly the colonization processes of a virgin habitat (Pinault, 2013).

The development of a network of artificial reefs is also subject to certain constraints particularly relating to the risks involved: physical changes, destabilization of anchor points, abandonment of structures by fish fauna, or threats to navigation. Such constraints specifically relate to the notion of slope of the seabed, submersion depth, development strategy, structure volume (height, development surface) and habitat complexity (porosity, roughness, etc.). Choices made re these variables will determine how well the established goals are achieved and the impact assessment methods to be used.

Projects subject to EIAs: Any creation, modification or extension to artificial reefs is subject to the case-by-case procedure (Environment Code, Article R.122-2, Annex item 12).

Furthermore, any artificial reef installed in outstanding coastal areas is subject to the case-by-case procedure. It is imperative that: 1) it be a minor development, and 2) it be necessary for fishing, mollusc or marine fish farming. In addition, their placement and appearance should not undermine the character of the site, compromise architectural and landscape qualities or have a negative impact on the environment (Environment Code, Article R.122-2, Annex item 11).

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, artificial reef installations and extensions are subject to authorization procedures ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration ($\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) procedures when relating to port development works or other projects carried out in contact with or having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of offshore devices

- Direct effects: mechanical degradation by organisms fixed on the site where artificial reefs are established, noise pollution and vibrations (if structures are fixed to the substrate), deposit of macro waste from the underwater work site.
- Indirect effects: disruption of maritime traffic during certain work phases.

Expected permanent effects:

- Direct effects: changes to the bathymetry and geomorphology of dredged sites, considerable disruption of dredged and piled ecosystems, with the possible structural reorganisation towards a new state of equilibrium (phase shift), possible bioaccumulation and bioamplification of pollutant substances liberated in surrounding organisms (chronic effects).
- Indirect effects: increase in maritime traffic (more and/or larger vessels) and road traffic (delivery lorries, hoisting machines, operations, etc.)

Figure 52 Artificial reefs in the bay of La Possession – Réunion (© G. Marquis)

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: effect of FADs and the biomass creation of submerged structures, restoration of ecological continuity and connectivity, replacement of degraded natural habitats, possible local, mechanical degradation by benthic organisms due to the deterioration of devices on the sea bed (chains, sinkers, scuppers, shackles, etc.).
- Indirect effects: increase in maritime activity (pleasure crafts, diving, etc.), increased pressure from fishing (exploitation of artificial reefs), possible disruption of surrounding natural ecosystems, particularly through the favouring of certain demersal species to the detriment of other competing species. This might result in the propagation of exotic species due to the relay or "stepping stone" effect, by modifying colonization mechanisms by fish fauna of natural habitats following the submersion of more attractive habitats (concentration effect) or by destabilizing surrounding sedimentary communities. The risk of sedentarization of certain large predators in areas near to the coast can be an issue in regions where there is a proven risk of shark attacks.

6.4.2 Fish farming (EIA, ICPEs or impact assessment under the Water Law)

Brief description: Aquaculture is the generic term referring to all animal or vegetable production in an aquatic environment. It can be carried out on the coast in lagoons, or further out to sea, in which case it is referred to as marine aquaculture, and in rivers or ponds. It involves the production of fish (fish farming), shellfish (shellfish farming), crustaceans (freshwater crayfish and shrimp farming), and algae (seaweed farming).

Marine production systems can be divided into two groups: 1) production in the intertidal and infra-littoral zone (shellfish), where shellfish can be scattered by hand or raised in cages, although they are more usually raised in pockets on a board or using the "bouchot" method in the intertidal zone; and 2) production in open water (in cages in the case of fish or along ropes in the case of shellfish and algae), located either offshore in sheltered areas, close to the coast, or more rarely in open sea fairly distant from the coast and thus not protected by it. Production in cages is of the intensive type, and in France production on ropes remains extensive or semi-intensive (AAMP, 2009).

Worldwide, while fish catches have been stagnating for the past twenty years, the aquaculture sector has been growing at an average annual rate of 8% since 1970. Within the European Union (EU), aquaculture, after considerable growth and a doubling of production between 1981 and 2001, has shown stagnation as the sector's average annual growth is only 0.5% (Milana, 2013). If Polynesian pearls and New-Caledonian shrimps are excluded, the cumulated fish production in French overseas territories did not exceed 150 tonnes in 2012. Despite undeniable advantages (favourable climatic conditions for high growth rates, experience in breeding certain species of high added value, etc.), overseas sectors are poorly developed and fragile. Causes can be attributed to structural and economic constraints (international competition, fluctuation in exchange rates, etc.) (UAOM, 2016).

Projects subject to EIA: Under heading 1 of the Annex to Article R. 122-2 of the Environment Code, marine fish farms with an annual production exceeding 20 tonnes are subject to an EIA within the framework of authorization ICPE procedures (Decree 2006-942 of 27 July 2006 modifying the nomenclature of classified installations). In this case, the EIA is subject to specific procedures relating to ICPEs and should be complemented with a hazard assessment study.

Furthermore, any aquaculture structure installed in outstanding coastal spaces is subject to the case-by-case procedure. It is imperative that it be a minor installation (not covered by ICPE nomenclature). In addition, placement and appearance should not undermine the character of the site, compromise its architectural and landscape qualities or have a negative impact on the environment (section 11 of the same article.)

Finally, regarding onshore installations, any device to remove seawater (hatcheries, nurseries, fish pens, etc.) is subject to the case-by-case procedure (section 15 of the same article).

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, the installation of offshore aquaculture structures are subject to authorization ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration procedures ($\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) regarding port development works and other works carried out in contact with and having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Setting up and dismantling offshore devices

- Direct effects: mechanical degradation by organisms fixed on the site where anchor points are installed (sea cages, nets, tables, etc.), noise pollution and vibration (if structures are fixed to the substrate), deposit of macro waste from the underwater work site.
- Indirect effects: disruption of maritime traffic possible during work phases.

Figure 53 Aquaculture farm in Saint Paul bay - La Réunion (© IPR)

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: loss of solar energy by benthic communities (shade cast by structures), disruption of dystrophic origin of surrounding communities (supply of food), inflows of antibiotics and other health-related products to the marine environment, effect of submerged structures of FADs (cages, ropes, buoys, anchors, etc.), possible inconvenience in the displacement of large cetaceans due to ropes, cables and a variety of other entanglements.
- Direct effects: increase in maritime traffic (operations, maintenance, food), colonization of natural environment by potentially invasive farmed species possibly carrying exotic pathogens; destruction of surrounding natural communities (degradation of coral environments by opportunistic organisms, sciaphiles, filter feeders, scavengers, nitrophiles, etc.). Possible reduction of pressure from fishing if farmed species are for local market. The risk of sedentarization of certain large predators in areas close to the shore can be a problem in regions where there is a proven risk of shark attacks.

6.4.3 Energy from the sea (EIA, impact assessment under the Water Law)

Brief description: Renewable marine energies (RMEs) or energy from the sea is energy extracted from the marine environment (solar, wind, thermal, wave, tidal, etc.). According to the Economic, Social and Environmental Council [CESE under its French acronym], French overseas territories offer considerable potential in the RME field. The success of new energy systems depends particularly on the willingness of overseas communities to become a "national energy mix laboratory", specifically investigating RME technologies.

High growth in the consumption and dependence on imported fossil fuels is driving overseas communities to focus on ambitious projects, with Guadeloupe, Martinique, Réunion and Guyane aiming for energy independence by 2030 (Grenelle I Law). These four regions are also aiming for 100% renewable energy (of which 50% from RMEs) in electricity production over the same period. Even Polynesia, a territory not subject to

the Grenelle I Law, the goal of 50% renewable energies by 2020, and 100% by 3020 has been incorporated in national legislation.

Projects subject to EIAs: All energy-generating offshore installations are subject to EIAs (Environment Code, Article R. 122-2, Annex item 27).

Projects subject to impact assessments under the Water Law: Pursuant to item 4120, infrastructures involving energy generation from the sea are subject to authorization procedures ($\geq 1,900,000$ euros) or declaration ($\geq 160,000$ euros but $< 1,900,000$ euros) procedures regarding port developments and other works carried out in contact with or having a direct impact on the marine environment.

Expected temporary effects: Construction and dismantling of offshore structures

- Direct effects: mechanical degradation by organisms fixed on the installation site of underwater structures (ballasts, anchor points, plates, pylons, etc.) and all along the power cables or conduits, noise pollution and vibrations (if drilling or beating is necessary), oil leaks and spills (if drilling is necessary), deposit of macro waste from the underwater work site.
- Indirect effects: disruption of maritime traffic during certain phases of work, introduction of exotic species, particularly by specialized work vessels.

Expected permanent effects: Use and maintenance

- Direct effects: possible degradation of coastal underwater landscape, the effect of FADs and possibly of artificial reefs of submerged structures, noise pollution (creaking, friction, movement of chains, etc.), leaks and spills of liquids (in the case of pumps and high pressure conduits of fluids), generation of heat and electromagnetic fields (in the case of operational power cables), possible inconvenience in the movement of large cetaceans due to anchor lines, cables and mobile elements (wind generator and tidal turbine blades), deterioration of structures on the surrounding seabed (chains, ballasts, metal structures, shackles, buoys, containers, etc.), light pollution from regulatory beacons, disturbance of wildlife by maintenance vessels.
- Indirect effects: area of exclusive use, closed to all maritime activity (reduction of pressure of fisheries, impact of anchorage, etc.), risks of vessels colliding with devices (despite the presence of signals), risk of the propagation of exotic species (relay effect). The risk of sedentarization of certain large predators in areas close to the shore attracted by FADs in regions where there is a proven risk of shark attacks.

Figure 54 Wave energy generation (© Pelamis Wave Power)

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